

Chapter 6

POLICY OPTIONS FOR GOVERNING SUSTAINABLE USE OF WILD SPECIES¹

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Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	812
6.1 INTRODUCTION	817
6.2 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH	818
6.3 GOVERNANCE	822
6.4 POLICY INSTRUMENTS ADOPTED FOR THE USE OF WILD SPECIES	824
6.4.1 Legal and regulatory instruments	825
6.4.1.1 International agreements and conventions	825
6.4.1.2 Legislation, regulations, and rules	828
6.4.1.3 National standards and planning	832
6.4.2 Economic and financial instruments	833
6.4.2.1 Taxes and Fees	833
6.4.2.2 Subsidies and incentives	835
6.4.2.3 Sustainability finance mechanisms	835
6.4.3 Social and information-based instruments	836
6.4.3.1 Certification schemes and eco-labelling	836
6.4.3.2 Education, training, stakeholder engagement and consultation	838
6.4.4 Rights-based and customary instruments	839
6.4.4.1 Tenure, access, and property rights	841
6.4.4.2 Customary laws: rules norms, and rights	842
6.4.4.3 Indigenous peoples and local communities and taboos	843
6.4.4.4 Human rights-based approaches	845
6.4.4.5 Community-based or co-management	846
6.4.5 Prevalence of policy instruments	849
6.5 EFFECTIVENESS OF POLICY INSTRUMENTS	850
6.5.1 Governance characteristics that enable sustainable use	851
6.5.1.1 Inclusive & participatory process	851
6.5.1.2 Policies aligned across scale and interactions supported	857
6.5.1.3 Robust institutions	858
6.5.2 Institutional arrangements that enable sustainable use	860
6.5.2.1 Tailored to the context	860
6.5.2.2 Clear and aligned ownership rights, responsibilities, and goals	866
6.5.2.3 Broader policies to support sustainable use	868
6.5.3 Rules and institutions that can constrain sustainable use	871
6.5.3.1 Overlooking available breadth of policy options	871
6.5.3.2 Overlooking social context	875
6.5.3.3 Overlooking customary practices, rights & indigenous and local knowledge	876
6.5.4 Power dynamics can impede sustainable use	879
6.5.4.1 Power imbalance	879
6.5.4.2 Neglecting history	882
6.5.4.3 Criminalizing local practices	884
6.6 LEVERS OF CHANGE AND POLICY OPTIONS	887
6.6.1 Strengthen inclusive and participatory decision-making	887
6.6.2 Recognize and support multiple forms of knowledge and rights	887
6.6.3 Ensure fair and equitable distribution of costs and benefits	889
6.6.4 Tailor policies to local social and ecological contexts	889
6.6.5 Monitor social and ecological conditions and practices	889
6.6.6 Coordinate and align policies	889

6.6.7	Build robust institutions, from customary to statutory	889
6.6.8	Enhance capacity building	890
6.7	KNOWLEDGE GAPS	890
	REFERENCES	892

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 6.1	Conceptualizing the interactive governance of wild species use	822
Figure 6.2	The calendar of animal breeding seasons was elaborated in Q'eqchi' and Spanish with drawings and in colloquial language for easier understanding	840
Figure 6.3	The spectrum of co-management arrangements	847
Figure 6.4	Conditions that enable (green) or constrain (red) sustainable use policies	851
Figure 6.5	Linking fishing patterns to governance	859
Figure 6.6	Average global mass production (kg/km ²) by trophic level with superimposed average percent exploitation ratio (catch/production)	872
Figure 6.7	The inshore fishery in Lake Kariba	874
Figure 6.8	Standardized biomass-size distributions in Lake Kariba from experimental fishing surveys 1980–1994	875
Figure 6.9	Harvest relative to total biological production (on logarithm scales) for species harvested in Lake Victoria based on the Ecopath model of 2014	885

LIST OF TABLES

Table 6.1	Articles identified through systematic and expert review guide case study selection for systematic analysis	819
Table 6.2	Number of cases by practice and region that were analyzed in chapter 6	820
Table 6.3	Policy effectiveness coding framework	821
Table 6.4	Examples of policy instruments for each practice (fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting, logging, and non-extractive practices)	826
Table 6.5	Contrasting approaches used commonly for the assessment and management of industrial and small-scale fisheries	848
Table 6.6	Prevalence of policy instruments	849
Table 6.7	Example list of cases from terrestrial animal harvesting regulations	864
Table 6.8	Policy effectiveness of economic, ecological and social sustainability (N=84)	876
Table 6.9	Seven key elements of effective policy for sustainable use of wild species, their presence in current international agreements and examples of policy options	888

LIST OF BOXES

Box 6.1	Non-lethal harvesting: aquarium trade	829
Box 6.2	National and regional recognition of customary law	842
Box 6.3	The International Union for Conservation of Nature environmental law centre principles for assuring human rights in conservation	845
Box 6.4	Inclusion of actors across multiple scales enables sustainability: Morelet's crocodile (<i>Crocodylus moreletii</i>) skins in Mexico	852
Box 6.5	Participatory co-management enables sustainable use: Pirarucu in the Amazon	855
Box 6.6	Pacific halibut case study	862
Box 6.7	Gathering – FairWild (India)	863
Box 6.8	Legal uncertainties and lack of resources constrains hunting policies: Brazil	866
Box 6.9	Transitional policies can pave the way for longer term policies: Bighorn sheep (<i>Ovis canadensis</i>) trophy hunting in Mexico	869
Box 6.10	Balanced harvest in Lake Kariba	873
Box 6.11	Aspects of indigenous rights especially relevant in conservation contexts	878
Box 6.12	Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) certification and state-dominated forestry – Belarus and Poland	880
Box 6.13	Uncertainty or lack of knowledge can undermine sustainable use: Atlantic bluefin tuna case study	881
Box 6.14	Crises and (lack of) transformation towards sustainability – The case of Atlantic cod	882
Box 6.15	Failed interactions constrain sustainable use: Lake Victoria	885

Chapter 6

POLICY OPTIONS FOR GOVERNING SUSTAINABLE USE OF WILD SPECIES

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This chapter reviews the range of policy options available for the sustainable use of wild species. Four broad and overlapping categories of instruments are considered: i) legal and regulatory, ii) economic and financial, iii) social and information based, and iv) customary and rights based. Evidence for their effectiveness in supporting the governance of socio-ecologically sustainable use is evaluated, and key enabling and constraining conditions determined. This information is intended to support decision-makers and society in steering towards a desirable future (see Chapter 5).

A mix of instruments tends to be used in combination and applied across different social and ecological contexts (*well established*) {6.4; 6.5}. Furthermore, evaluations of policy instruments are seldom systematic or controlled, making it difficult to fully disentangle policy effectiveness {6.5.1} or establish causality between implementation of a policy instrument and resulting social-ecological sustainability {6.5.1}. Where effectiveness is evaluated, there is a risk that evaluations are based on normative interpretations of those involved. In order to minimize bias, Chapter 6's experts therefore define effectiveness as 'the ability to support sustainable use', which by necessity includes analyses of the governance context {6.3}. Below are the key messages emerging from Chapter 6, that are expanded in detail in the chapter.

1 Ensuring 'inclusive participation' is an underlying principle of governance and can support more effective sustainable use policies (*well established*) {6.5.4; 6.5.5.1; 6.6.1}. Specific actions to promote inclusive and participatory processes include enacting policies with clear guidance on procedures for decision-making and representation (e.g., specifying membership roles and responsibilities) and building capacity that enables all parties to participate fully (*well established*) {6.5.1.1, 6.6.1}. When processes and procedures support and enable the inclusion of all actors, traditions, knowledges, and contexts, transformative change in sustainable use is possible (*well established*) {6.4.4, 6.5.2, 6.6.1}. Full and effective participation in the sustainable use of wild species can support effective learning and reduce redundancy (e.g., *via* knowledge brokers, mediators, facilitators). Outcomes are also likely to be better supported by communities and all

stakeholders, and damaging power dynamics can be illuminated and navigated (*well established*) {6.5.1.1, 6.6.1}. Such participatory mechanisms are more effective when implemented through inclusive processes that integrate customary and statutory laws, include participation of indigenous peoples and local communities in policy design, recognize gendered differences in the knowledge and practices of uses of wild species and include close follow up through monitoring (*well established*) {6.5.2.2}. Conservation instruments such as protected areas or other effective conservation measures can also contribute to the sustainability of the use of wild species (*well established*) {6.5.1.1}. However, to be effective, protected areas should be inclusive of indigenous peoples and local communities and other people involved, avoid displacing indigenous peoples, local communities, and dependent livelihoods, and be embedded in larger planning processes, and have a full implementation strategy (*well established*) {6.5, 6.5.1.1}.

Legal and regulatory, and economic and financial policy instruments are more effective, when developed through democratic, and participatory processes, that involve representative leaders, transparent institutions, community-based approaches, and collective rights (*well established*) {6.5.1.1, 6.5.2.2, 6.6.1}. Legitimate participatory processes that involve a more equal balance of power, tend to support more effective policies because they draw on diverse perspectives and forms of knowledge, support collaboration, and increase buy-in leading to better self-regulation {6.5.1.1}. This is especially the case for high value species (*established but incomplete*) {6.5.2.1, 6.5.3.1}.

2 Elevating 'respect for multiple forms of knowledge' and 'protection of human rights' as values and principles that underpin governance, can lead to more effective sustainable use policies (*well established*) {6.5.2.2; 6.5.3.3; 6.6.2}. The knowledge of indigenous peoples and local communities, such as on wild species is often undervalued and underrepresented in policy documents (*well established*) {6.4.4.3, 6.5.2.2, 6.6.2}. Yet, this knowledge can provide extensive, additional information about the relationships between living beings and the environment, especially with regards to natural resources and ecosystem services that indigenous peoples and local communities depend on (*well established*) {6.4.4.3} (also see Chapter 1). Retention and contributions of indigenous

and local knowledge is necessarily linked to their rights to natural resources and their access to these resources. The cultural, linguistic, spiritual, and material survival of these knowledge systems is also tied to their recognition (*well established*) {6.4.4.3}. Coproduction of knowledge by indigenous peoples and local communities and scientists can also create robust information about social and ecological conditions and enhance decision-making (*well established*) {6.5.1.1, 6.5.1.2.}. Inclusion of indigenous peoples and local communities in the development and implementation of policies for sustainable use of wild species requires sustained commitment and recognition of both systems as authoritative, but in doing so can be mutually beneficial. It is also important that engagements with indigenous peoples and local communities observe free, prior and informed consent and follow international protocols on access and benefit sharing, for example based on the Nagoya Protocol (*well established*) {6.4.4.2, 6.5.2.4, 6.5.3.3}. Legal and regulatory instruments are more effective when they take into account indigenous and local knowledge and science (*well established*) {6.5.3.3}. The failure to include indigenous and local knowledge and indigenous languages in policy processes and their implementation results in the loss of languages, weakened community cohesion, and diminished indigenous and local knowledge related to species and sustainable use, that can erode sustainable use practices (*well established*) {6.4.3, 6.4.4, 6.4.4.2, 6.6.2}. The sustainable use of wild species is integral to people living well and within their means and also supports human rights, including access to food, work, leisure, and a clean, healthy and sustainable environment (*well established*) {6.4.4}. Thus, international laws, guidelines, and commitments exist to protect local food systems and livelihoods of indigenous peoples and local communities in recognition of both a moral obligation, and pragmatic reality that these can help support the sustainable use of wild species (*well established*) {6.4.4.4}.

3 Embedding ‘benefit sharing’ and ‘equity’ as central elements of governance, can lead to more effective sustainable use policies (*well established*) {6.4.3.1; 6.5.2.1; 6.6.3}. The fair and equitable distribution of benefits from the sustainable use of wild species needs is increasingly promoted in voluntary, state, and private legislation; but its implementation is often incomplete and needs greater support (*well established*) {6.4.1.1, 6.4.3.1; 6.5.2.1; 6.6, 6.6.3}. People’s perceptions of fairness and justice shape their willingness to comply with regulations that govern sustainable use {6.4.3}. Small producers, who lack political or economic power, can easily lose out if measures are drafted in a way that primarily promotes the interests of the advantaged (*well established*) {6.5.2}. There are often gender inequities in how costs and benefits of wild species uses are distributed, with women bearing more of the costs and receiving fewer benefits of use (*well established*) {6.4.3, 6.4.4, 6.5.4.1}. Although penalties can

be effective in some cases, such as hunting fines (*well established*) {6.4.4.3, 6.4.5}, financial and economic policies tend to be more effective when based on incentives (e.g., tax breaks, certification, market access or compensation) rather than penalties (e.g., taxes, fines, or restrictions). Specific actions and plans could include enacting guidelines on access and benefit sharing that are currently common in voluntary agreements, applying governance and institutional frameworks that ensure fair and equitable distribution of costs and benefits. This may ensure that policies do not inadvertently criminalize or deprive local communities or marginalized individuals of access and equitable distribution of costs and benefits, and identify measures that may ensure preventing the misappropriation of genetic resources and associated traditional knowledge (*well established*) {6.4.4, 6.6.3}.

4 Effectiveness of market-based incentives, such as certification and labelling, is mixed and mostly limited to high value markets (*established but incomplete*) {6.4.3.1}. Certification and labelling schemes operate on the premise that providing information to consumers will result in a market shift that favors sustainable products, thereby incentivizing and rewarding sustainable practices by producers through price premiums and increased market share (*well established*) {6.4.3.1, 6.5.1.2}. In general, certification and labelling, when carefully designed and implemented, can promote ecological, economic and to a lesser extent social sustainability, but benefits have largely been for large scale operations and where there is a high market demand (*established but incomplete*) {6.4.3.1, 6.5.1.3}. Mechanisms, such as certifications or regulation, are most effective when they enable the equitable sharing of both monetary and non-monetary benefits, include marginalized communities and indigenous groups, and when the administrative costs of such systems do not exceed their benefits (*well established*) {6.4.3.1, 6.5.2}. Certification and labelling are widely used in large-scale commercial fishing, logging, and non-extractive recreational practices. In the cases of fishing and logging, certification and labelling frequently have been successful in securing and increasing market share, but it is unclear how often certification supports transitions from unsustainable to sustainable practices (*established but incomplete*) {6.4.3.1}. Certification may also lead to a specialization around a few value chains. Furthermore, market-based incentives have generally not delivered price premiums for producers (*well established*) {6.4.3.1}. Relatively high costs to obtain certification, satisfy ongoing reporting requirements and realize market benefits, often place certification beyond the reach of small-scale producers, including indigenous peoples and local communities (*established but incomplete*) {6.4.3.1, 6.5.2}. The viability of market-based incentives such as certifications and labelling, depend also on appropriate design in line with international trade regulations (*established but incomplete*) {6.4.3.1}.

5 Governance processes that are designed to coordinate interactions across scale, including across the spectrum of customary to statutory forms of governance, support more effective sustainable use policies (*well established*) {6.5.1.2, 6.5.2.3, 6.5.3.3, 6.6.4, 6.6.6}. When policy instruments are aligned (i.e., across scales, incentives, or allowable activities) or designed to reinforce one another they result in more positive outcomes (*well established*) {6.5.1.2}. Governance processes that pay attention to coordinating interactions between approaches, actors, and scales can result in more effective outcomes (*well established*) {6.5.2.3, 6.5.1.1}. Policies that are aligned at international, regional, national, sub-national, and local levels can be more effective at supporting sustainable use of wild species, with fewer negative and unintended consequences (*well established*) {6.5.1.2, 6.6}.

6 Governance institutions that are adaptive to changes in social and ecological conditions and robust with clear conflict resolution mechanisms support more effective sustainable use policies (*well established*) {6.5.1.3, 6.6.7}. Institutions that are structured around collaborative and decentralized learning and shared interests in sustainable use can create accountability through social norms, compliance and self-monitoring (*established but incomplete*) {6.3, 6.6.7}. Whereas, centralized systems, that often rely on legal and regulatory approaches, require sufficient investment of resources and capacity for monitoring and enforcement to ensure institutions are robust, which in turn results in more effective sustainable use policies (*well established*) {6.5.1.3}.

The social and ecological conditions under which uses of wild species occur are always dynamic. Consequently, policy instruments and management tools are most effective when they address causes of unsustainable use and adapt to changing circumstances (*well established*) {6.5.2}. Adaptive processes are enhanced by collaborative learning and governance. Successful co-learning is characterized by comprehensive, continuous, iterative and transparent engagement between key actors, including governance institutions and those who depend on wild species for their livelihoods and wellbeing (*well established*) {6.5}. Moreover, adaptive and dynamic institutions, capable of adjusting to changing circumstances are more likely to support the sustainable use of wild species in the face of current and future drivers (*established but incomplete*) {6.6.1, 6.5.1.2}. The integration of conflict resolution mechanisms can make institutions more effective, while transparency initiatives connected to legally mandated measures of accountability can enhance trust in institutions, resulting in more effective policies (*well established*) {6.5.4.1, 6.6.3}. Facilitators trained in conflict resolution can help formulate equitable and viable policies (*established but incomplete*) {6.5.2.3}.

7 Policies that are tailored to the context can support effective policies for sustainable use of wild species (*well established*) {6.4.1, 6.4.1.2, 6.4.3, 6.4.4, 6.5.1, 6.5.2.3, 6.5.2.1, 6.5.3.1, 6.6.4}. Policies are more effective when tailored to local ecological, social and governance contexts (*well established*) {6.4.1, 6.5.2.1, 6.6.4}. Such approaches are more likely to be designed to support equitable benefit sharing, thus providing an enabling environment for indigenous peoples and local communities to benefit (*established but incomplete*) {6.5.1}. For example, the diversity of contexts in which small-scale fisheries operate have often made conventional data-driven fisheries management inadequate and unsuccessful, but when the involvement, participation and empowerment of indigenous peoples and local communities are maintained or promoted, the sustainability of small-scale fisheries can be achieved (*well established*) {6.5.1.1, 6.5.3.1}. In contrast, policies based on assumptions or frameworks from outside a region or local context may lead to unanticipated outcomes (*well established*) {6.4.3, 6.5.2.1, 6.5.2.3}. For example, bans are more effective when they take into consideration species characteristics (e.g., reproductivity, status), local customs, and traditional use (*well established*) {6.4.1.2}. In contrast, policies and regulations that fail to recognize and account for the diversity of uses and benefits associated with a practice, particularly differences between commercial and subsistence or small-scale actors, can lead to negative social and ecological outcomes (*well established*) {6.4.1.2, 6.4.3.1}. Similarly, customary and rights-based approaches can provide a more nuanced and effective approach to regulation where commercial demand is low, and practices and uses diverse (*established but incomplete*) {6.4.4, 6.5.1.2}. The need for policy “fit for purpose” is widely acknowledged but incompletely pursued (*well established*) {6.5.2.1, 6.5.4.2}. For example, community-based and nature-based tourism standards that combine legal and regulatory approaches with social and information-based approaches provide livelihood benefits to communities while protecting indigenous and local cultures and environments (*established but incomplete*) {6.4.1.3, 6.4.4.5}.

8 Policies that are clearly aligned with goals, and that clarify ownership and access rights and responsibilities, support more effective sustainable use policies (*established but incomplete*) {6.4.4.1, 6.5.1.1.2, 6.5.2.2}. For successful policy formation and implementation, policy goals and instruments need to be clearly identified, aligned, and shared with stakeholders (*well established*) {6.5.2.2}. Yet, often legal uncertainties, opaque policies, and a lack of resources inhibit the effectiveness of sustainable use policies (*well established*) {6.5.2.2}. Yet, when land tenure and resource rights are secure, customary law tends to be strong, and local capacity to manage the resource base and deal with commercial pressures exist (*established but incomplete*) {6.4.4, 6.5.2.2}. In contrast, where customary law has

broken down to a significant degree, Governments can offer important and necessary complementary levels of regulation -often requested by local groups (*well established*) {6.4.4, 6.5.2.2}. When policies have clearly stated rather than generic goals, whether short or long term, they can be more effective (6.5.2.2). For example, restrictive hunting regulations are generally most effective at supporting sustainable use (i.e., through species recovery) when used in the transition to a new arrangement such as when conducting population studies for the establishment of harvesting (trade) quotas (e.g., in the case study of bighorn sheep in Mexico **(Box 6.10)**). In other cases, bans are established temporarily while populations recover, and later on, sustainable harvest limits are set.

9 Broader, national, policies that align with sustainable use policies and objectives, can support more effective sustainable policies. Broader policies, including poverty alleviation, national education, and linguistic policies can support sustainable use of natural resources amongst indigenous peoples and local communities, while laws protecting their local food systems and livelihoods will help sustainable use of wild species (*well established*) {6.5.2.3}. National education, communication, public awareness and linguistic policies could positively contribute to the sustainable use of wild resources but are seldom prioritized as policy options (*established but incomplete*) {6.4.3.2}. If well designed, strategic combinations of policies can simultaneously alleviate multiple drivers of unsustainable use and create a supportive environment for sustainable use of wild species (*well established*) {6.5.3, 6.6.4}. Moreover, the representation of livelihoods of indigenous peoples and local communities in schools could promote inter-cultural understanding and respect, community pride and desire to continue with traditional practices (*well established*) {6.4.3.2, 6.4.2.1, 6.5.2.3, 6.6.2}.

10 An over reliance on regulatory policies can impede sustainable use (*well established*) {6.4.5, 6.5.3.1}. A diversity of policy approaches exists and can be applied to various species, practices, and sets of actors or geographical areas (*well established*) {6.5.3.1}. However, Statutory legal and regulatory based instruments are the most commonly applied instruments to regulate wild species use (*well established*) {6.4.5, 6.5.3.1}. These are often applied as single-species regulations without wider ecosystem considerations and in some cases are applied without adequately considering existing customary laws and practices, the *de facto* practices of users, or what other approaches may be more effective {6.5.3.1}. Furthermore, legal and regulatory based instruments, most frequently target high value species, in particular within fishing and gathering practices, despite tending to be less effective than social or information based and customary and rights-based instruments (*well established*) {6.4.5}.

11 Policies that are too narrow or overly focused on economic or ecological outcomes, thus neglecting social and cultural contexts, can constrain sustainable use of wild species {6.4.3.1, 6.4.5, 6.5.1, 6.5.1.3}.

Policies developed for a specific practice, user group, sector, species, or habitat will have impacts beyond the target of the policy that may be undesirable or unexpected {6.5.1}. Yet, policies tend to have a narrow focus, and as a result multispecies interactions, local context, and scale are seldom taken into account (*well established*) {6.5.1}. Indeed, policy instruments are most frequently targeted towards improved ecological, and at times economic, sustainability rather than social, or linked social-ecological sustainability (*well established*) {6.4.5}. For example, economic and financial instruments that secure access rights to land, water bodies, territories, and resources have been widely employed (e.g., individual transferable quotas) {6.4.5}, but are mostly motivated by economic efficiency and often overlook social equity. Similarly, social and information-based certifications have largely focused on large scale operations and where there is a high market demand, but can be successful at promoting ecological, economic and to a lesser extent social sustainability although policies and benefits thus far (*established but incomplete*) {6.4.3.1, 6.5.1.3}. Consequently, negative social outcomes and elite capture that concentrates benefits in the hands of few are common (*established but incomplete*) {6.5.1}.

12 Overlooking customary practices, rights, and indigenous and local knowledge can constrain sustainable use of wild species (*well established*) {6.5.3.3}. Policies that support secure tenure rights and equitable access to land, fisheries and forests as well as poverty alleviation, create enabling conditions for sustainable use of wild species (*well established*) {6.4.4.1}. When national sectoral policies are aligned with targeted policies to support local tenure of land, fisheries and forests, the synergy creates enabling conditions for the sustainable use of wild species. For example, policies that alleviate poverty, can also empower local customary institutions that, in turn, support sustainable use of wild species (*well established*) {6.5.1}. Historical policies on land tenure, land rights, and rights contain inadequate protection of access and rights to indigenous lands and water but national policies seldom align with customary laws and policies; which negatively affects sustainable use of wild species {6.5.3.3}. This precludes indigenous peoples and local communities from securing greater social-ecological benefits, reduces incentives for sustainable use, ultimately undermining policy effectiveness. Furthermore, the knowledge of indigenous peoples and local communities, such as on wild species, is often undervalued and underrepresented in policy documents {6.5.3.3}. This knowledge can provide extensive and additional information about the relationships between living beings and the environment, especially with regards to natural resources and nature's contributions to people that

indigenous peoples and local communities depend on. Continuity and contributions of indigenous and local knowledge is necessarily linked to rights, access, recognition, and survival (cultural, linguistic, spiritual, and material). The failure to include indigenous and local knowledge in policy processes results in loss of language, community cohesion, and indigenous and local knowledge related to species and sustainable use.

13 Strengthening customary institutions and rules often contributes to the sustainable use of wild species (*well established*) {6.4.4.2}. Attention to customary institutions and rules governing uses of wild species can reduce conflicts and increase policy effectiveness (*well established*) {6.5}. Customary approaches can lower transaction costs for monitoring and enforcement compared with formal governance systems. For example, taboos limit use of individual species. Such customary approaches can support the ecological and economic dimensions of sustainability but are particularly effective at supporting its social dimensions. However, historical and cultural systems, such as taboos, have seldom been incorporated into policies for managing use of wild species (*well established*) {6.4.4.3}.

14 Policies that fail to adequately account for historical context can undermine sustainable use. The historical context into which a policy is developed and implemented affects policy outcomes (*well established*) {6.6.4}. Yet most laws are built incrementally and lack an overall strategy or clear objectives, consequently seemingly unrelated areas of law directly and indirectly impact the use of wild species, their management, and trade. New policy instruments that are added to a mix of existing instruments may work differently depending on historic and current conditions (*well established*) {6.5.3.2, 6.6.4}. Implementation can exacerbate pre-existing tensions, creating conflicts even where other enabling conditions are present (*well established*) {6.5.4.2}. A lack of alignment between current and historic policies undermines their effectiveness in supporting sustainable use {6.5.4.2, 6.6.3}.

15 Power imbalances can undermine sustainable use policies, creating conflicts and allowing corruption and abuse of power to persist (*well established*) {6.5.2.3, 6.5.4.3, 6.5.2.6}. Power imbalances need to be addressed and conflicts managed to guard against elite capture or the domination of a few powerful actors that undermine policy effectiveness. Power imbalances between different actors can shape their involvement in decision making, creating barriers to participation. For example, processors and traders often control sectors with small-scale producers and harvesters having limited power over, and access to, commercial trade and pricing. Small producers and harvesters, who lack such political or economic power, can easily lose out if measures

are drafted in a way that does not fairly represent their interests (*established but incomplete*) {6.5.4.3}. Legitimate participatory processes that involve a more equal balance of power support more effective policies because they draw on diverse perspectives and forms of knowledge, support collaboration, and increase buy-in leading to better self-regulation (*well established*) {6.5.2.3, 6.5.4.3}. This is particularly important for species that are heavily traded with strong economic interests (*well established*) {6.5.4.3}. For example, regulations that follow voluntary codes of conduct, can have positive social effects but are dependent, for example, on the existence of strong norms, which are strengthened by actor participation {6.5.2.3}. Inequities and inequalities both within governance structures and across sustainable use actors can undermine sustainable use policies. For example, where corruption is allowed to emerge within governance processes this creates conflict and hampers implementation of regulatory measures.

16 Policies can inadvertently criminalize vulnerable people and local communities, which in turn constrains sustainable use policies. Policies may inadvertently criminalize harvesting activities, further marginalizing producers and constraining effective outcomes (*well established*) {6.4.1.2, 6.5.4.3}. Lack of clarity of regulations and the field knowledge give negative impacts to policy enforcement and effectiveness. In many countries, violations of many sustainable use regulations, such as the abuse of quotas, are treated as administrative offenses or misdemeanors, rather than as criminal offenses {6.4.1.2}.

6.1 INTRODUCTION

People are an integral part of nature and depend on its resources for survival. Therefore, for millennia, societies across the world have used a wide variety of wild species, from a range of ecosystems, and in different ways (see Chapter 1 and Chapter 2). However, increasing land use changes and subsequent degradation of natural habitats, as well as recent trends in the use of wild species (see Chapter 3) raise concerns for the future sustainability of these practices (IPBES, 2019b). In each region, different direct and indirect drivers influence those desired and undesired patterns (see Chapter 4). A greater understanding of the effectiveness of governance and policy options (Chapter 6) can support the transition towards more sustainable and desirable future trajectories (see Chapter 5) for the sustainable use of wild species.

According to the Convention of biological diversity, states are responsible for ensuring biological resources are valued and used in a sustainable manner. States, together with stakeholders, are expected to establish and implement biodiversity management policies. An improved understanding of the direct and indirect drivers behind these trends (see Chapter 4), should be used to inform the governance of wild species use. Biodiversity policy options and strategies implemented by a State, must co-exist with a broader set of strategies initiated by a range of actors from grassroots users and citizens through to inter – and multinational institutions, with varying levels of interaction and co-ordination between them. Consequently, the broader social (i.e., governance, economic, cultural, technological), and well as historical, and ecological contexts of each locality, influences how effective policies are likely to be in enhancing the sustainable use of species. This chapter explores the governance context, policy options, and responses available (Section 6.4) for the sustainable use of wild species. In doing so, it identifies key governance elements that support sustainable use, as well as enabling and constraining conditions (Section 6.5). The overarching goal is to elucidate levers to changes and policy options (Section 6.6) that hold promise or pose challenges to a sustainable future.

Evaluating the effectiveness of policies for the sustainable use of wild species requires an understanding of the governance landscape in any given setting. Chapter 6 draws on interactive governance theory (Section 6.3) to support its analyses of policy effectiveness with a particular focus on the interactions that occur among multiple actors. Building on an understanding of interactive governance, section 6.2 describes the methodological approach used for evaluating effectiveness.

Section 6.4 presents the range of policy instruments available to support the sustainable use of wild species,

at a range of spatial scales (local, national, international), and across five key practices (fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting, logging, and non-extractive practices). Four groups of policy instruments are explored: i) legal and regulatory, ii) economic and financial, iii) social and information based, and iv) rights-based and customary instruments.

Section 6.5 synthesizes evidence on the governance context and effectiveness of policy instruments to identify key enabling and constraining conditions. Evaluating the impact and effectiveness of available policy instrument is crucial to ensure that limited financial and human resources available are used to maximize outcomes (Karousakis, 2018). The options explored include a combination of policy instruments and their integration with other environmental policy tools for promoting the sustainable use of wild species and their habitats. This includes consideration of the interests and rights of multiple actors including indigenous peoples and local communities, and ways in which conflict can be managed between different actors. Enabling and constraining conditions to policy effectiveness are identified, such as existing and emergent limitations, challenges, and opportunities.

Section 6.6 presents levers of changes learned of in the policy assessment and presents options for tested and emergent solutions for ensuring the sustainable use of wild species in diverse contexts.

Section 6.7 summarizes knowledge gaps identified in the assessment of policy effectiveness for the use of wild species.

6.2 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

Three iterative strategies and approaches were used to identify and assess relevant literature through which the status of knowledge on policy use and effectiveness was evaluated. This section therefore describes the methods used in this chapter in order to: i) assess what policy instruments are available to support the sustainable use of wild species; ii) determine how effective the policy instruments that have been used are across different practices; iii) establish what are key enabling and constraining conditions, including those that relate to governance contexts; iv) illuminate levers of change and policy options, and; iv) identify knowledge gaps.

1. General Review: Three strategies were pursued in tandem. First, all lead authors conducted an expert led review of the literature to gather, and synthesize available information on the application and effectiveness of policy options for the sustainable use of wild species. This broad search of the literature continued for the entire duration of the assessment. This was primarily used to summarize information on the availability and characteristics of policy instruments, and patterns of use (section 6.4). However, literature gathered was also used to supplement information on the effectiveness of policy options (section 6.5).

2. Mixed methods (systematic) review: Understanding what policy options are available, and evaluating the effectiveness of these options is an important stage in the policy cycle (Giorgi, 2017; E. Young & Quinn, 2002). Effectiveness refers to whether a policy works as intended and meets the purpose for which it was designed (Sadler, 1996). Policy effectiveness can be assessed in terms of objectives, outcomes and impacts (Broc *et al.*, 2018). Establishing when and why particular policy approaches are most likely to succeed is key to enabling the sustainable use of wild species. Because effectiveness is context specific, variables through time, practice, place, and culture, are considered to establish the conditions enabling or constraining policy effectiveness. The concept of “enabling conditions” centers on conditions that facilitate approaches to addressing social and ecological challenges. They can be defined as factors that increase the likelihood of an intended change in the governance approach, strategy, or management regime. The presence of enabling conditions can facilitate the emergence of a particular environmental policy, whereas the absence of key enabling conditions can present a barrier to management or sustained policy action (Huber-Stearns *et al.*, 2017). Assessing policy effectiveness contributes to understanding what worked as planned and providing inputs to the redesign or improvement of policies at the stage of policy evaluation. It contributes to narrowing a knowledge gap given the science-based justification for policy decisions (Artelle *et al.*, 2018). A systematic

review process follows four steps: identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion (Moher *et al.*, 2009). Chapter 6’s experts followed, and where necessary adapted, the IPBES guidelines for a systematic review of the literature.

The initial literature search was conducted in English, in March 2020, in a bibliographic database, SCOPUS, which is one of the largest citation databases, but it does not include grey literature and is geographically biased to industrialized countries. Chapter 6’s experts chose SCOPUS for its broad scope and accessibility across all experts, although other sources were used at a later date. Search fields included article title, abstract, and keywords. The search strings were a combination of the two major topics: use practices of wild species (terrestrial animal harvesting, fishing, etc.) and policy instruments (legal & regulatory, economic & financial, etc.) and designed in order to capture all forms and derivatives of the root word (e.g., fish* would capture fishing and fisher) (see data management report at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4663236>). The search included all articles published during the whole period provided by database, which spanned the years 1975 to 2019. 1975 was the year when the experts found the firstly published article from the database.

Once articles had been identified from the search, the abstracts, and where necessary full article, were screened in April 2020 for initial eligibility by experts. Articles were retained if they: i) addressed the use of wild species; ii) were about one of the practices (terrestrial animal harvesting, fishing, gathering, logging, and non-extractive practices), and iii) contained information on the effectiveness of a policy response that fell under one of four policy instrument categories (legal & regulatory, economic & financial, social & information based, rights-based & customary); and, iv) reflected a positive example.

The initial systematic review identified a total of 4729 articles by practice and policy instrument. There were a number of duplicate articles due to the nature of our search terms. For example, a single article or case study could evaluate two or more policy instruments in which case it was picked up twice.

Following the initial screening of articles focusing on their relevance for policy effectiveness and use of wild species, only a few (**Table 6.1**) were selected as appropriate. This number indicated a lack of articles focused on assessing or measuring policy effectiveness in use practices of wild species. Because of lack of articles focused on evaluating policy options, or potential bias (Estes *et al.*, 2011; Isaksen & Richter, 2019), the experts conducted a supplementary expert review to supplement the initial list of articles with additional key cases.

Experts supplemented papers gathered in the first search with an additional expert led search of the field drawing on

expert experience, extensive reading, and the collective network of international collaborators. This second phase included literature published in languages other than English, including Spanish, Portuguese, Russian, and Hindi.

Cases were selected from the systematic and expert review for further systematic analysis based on three criteria; i) causal leverage, ii) diversity, and iii) data accessibility. Causal leverage captures the extent to which effectiveness is demonstrated (Seawright & Gerring, 2008). The cases should include relevant information on the influence of policy effectiveness under the research framework. In this assessment, the cases should offer information on positive impacts and effects of policy instruments in use on practices or wild species and specific governance mode. Second, diversity is a major criterion of selecting cases (Seawright & Gerring, 2008). Diversity can reduce bias of selection. In this assessment, the cases were selected to consider geographical balance. Experts sought for representation across continents, climate zones, countries, policy characteristics, and characteristics of the practices (e.g., within fisheries we included industrial and small-scale case studies). A number of cases were cross scale- e.g., reflected two or more of local, national, regional, international or transnational issues. Third, data accessibility

was for practical reasons a criterion for inclusion. Experts were only able to use case studies that were accessible in online databases, whether peer reviewed, grey literature, or open access databases.

Through the combination of systematic and expert searches the experts identified 100 policy-relevant cases, across all practices, spanning the range of policy approaches, for in-depth systematic analysis (Table 6.1) of the application and effectiveness of policy instruments across practice for the sustainable use of wild species. Each case study represented a body of knowledge, and therefore could contain a number of articles from the peer reviewed or grey literature.

The experts coded the 100 selected case studies, to allow for a systematic analysis to compare individual cases across policy instrument, practice, and geography (Table 6.2), allowing them to postulate that certain attributes can be taken as criteria for assessing causality, e.g., (1) strength of association between the policy instruments application and sustainable use outcomes; (2) consistency of association in various conditions across ecosystems, practices and local contexts; (3) plausibility of causal explanations; (4) coherence with paradigms and knowledge of each practice;

Table 6.1 Articles identified through systematic and expert review guide case study selection for systematic analysis.

The number of articles searched, screened, and selected in systematic and expert review.

Practice	Instrument	Identification (Systematic Review)	Retained (Systematic Review)	Added (Expert Review)
Fishing	Legal and regulatory	321	4	9
	Economic and financial	151		
	Social and information-based	148		
	Right-based and customary	326		
Gathering	Legal and regulatory	51	5	28
	Economic and financial	50		
	Social and information-based	19		
	Right-based and customary	82		
Terrestrial animal harvesting	Legal and regulatory	275	7	8
	Economic and financial	166		
	Social and information-based	164		
	Right-based and customary	360		
Non-extractive practices	Legal and regulatory	773	7	21
	Economic and financial	212		
	Social and information-based	258		
	Right-based and customary	1114		
Logging	Legal and regulatory	77	0	11
	Economic and financial	41		
	Social and information-based	46		
	Right-based and customary	95		

and (5) temporality, where presence of attributes preceded success) (see data management report at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4663236>).

Experts read all 100 case studies and coded them qualitatively, or based on a 3 points scale, to capture three case study characteristics, evaluate how effective the policy is at supporting four dimensions of sustainable use, specify enabling and constraining characteristics, comment on dimensions of the governance systems, and include any additional comments (Table 6.3). Case study characteristics include: i) the most dominant practice it relates to (i.e., fishing, gathering, etc.); ii) policy instruments being evaluated (at least one of legal and regulation, economic and financial etc.); iii) relevant policy scale(s) (temporal, governance, and spatial).

Chapter 6's experts drew on the sustainable use indicators reviewed in chapter 2, criteria for effectiveness from selected publications (Alatorre-Frenk *et al.*, 2016; Arnstein, 1969; Diaz *et al.*, 2015; EUROSTAT, 2017; Gagnon & Berteaux, 2009; Lakon *et al.*, 2008; Ostrom & Ahn, 2003; Putnam, 2000), and the experts review to identify four dimensions of sustainable use and define effectiveness as 'the extent to which a policy supports sustainable use, whilst minimizing any adverse effects to external systems. Sustainable use was evaluated along four dimensions:

- A. Ecological sustainability** is where ecological objectives are met, including maintaining or improving species, habitats, diversity, and abundance.
- B. Social sustainability** is where social objectives are met including supporting equity, material, relational, and subjective wellbeing.
- C. Economic sustainability** is where economic objectives are met including sustaining income, livelihoods, and trade.

D. Institutional sustainability is where institutional objectives are met including enabling cost effective, participatory process, incorporation of indigenous and local knowledge, and integration between international and national regulations.

Each sustainable use dimension- ecological, social, economic and institutional- were coded as positive (+1) (i.e., policy manages to maintain or increase dimension), neutral (0) (i.e., mixed or no effect of policy on dimension), negative (-1) (i.e., despite, or because of policy dimension declines) or not enough evidence (n/a). Social and economic dimensions were separated for the purpose of analysis to illuminate common trade-offs and evident bias.

Effectiveness of a specific policy approach is likely to be influenced by enabling, constraining, and governance conditions. Enabling and constraining conditions, increase or decrease the likelihood of policy effectiveness, and we include social, ecological, technological, and cultural factors (e.g., resources, indigenous and local knowledge, species life history characteristics). For governance conditions the experts drew on our adapted interactive governance theory framework, to evaluate: i) interactions among actors; and, alignment is the ii) values, iii) rules, and iv) tools (Huber-Stearns *et al.*, 2017). This coding system allowed us to analyze policy effectiveness across all practices, policy instruments, and contexts, to evaluate effectiveness and determine common enabling and constraining conditions.

After coding all 100 cases, Chapter 6' experts found that 16 cases did not reflect a positive value in any aspects of sustainability. Because the focus of the assessment is on policy effectiveness, rather than ineffectiveness, these 16 cases were excluded from further evaluation of effectiveness. Consequently, all practices included

Table 6.2 Number of cases by practice and region that were analyzed in chapter 6.

Practice	Region							TOTAL
	Asia	Africa	Europe	Oceania	North America	Central & South America	Other	
Fishing	1	4	1	1	2	2	2	13
Gathering	12	6	6	0	1	6	2	33
Terrestrial animal harvesting	2	3	1	2	1	6	0	15
Non-extractive practices	6	8	2	7	0	3	2	28
Logging	3	1	4	0	1	1	1	11
TOTAL	24	22	14	10	5	18	7	100

more cases with positive effectiveness than with negative effectiveness. In total 84 cases of effective sustainable use policy, covering any aspect of sustainability, all practices and a range of geographies (Table 6.3) were coded, ready for analysis.

The systematic review focuses on providing evidence-based knowledge, acknowledging that not all wild resource practices are equally well covered, as for example the large discrepancy between the large-scale and small-scale fisheries practices. The systematic review followed IPBES guidelines and drew on the broader literature on systematic reviews (see the data management report at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4663236>). The focus of studies that address policy effectiveness – be it implicitly or explicitly – is often focused on a subset of the three aspects of sustainability (ecological, economic, social), with the ecological natural science literature often looking more at the effects on the stock status or habitat protection, while more social science versatile authors are more likely to include information about economic and especially social consequences of an implemented policy. Thus, the measure of success is often discipline biased and the full information on any particular case study may also be dispersed across many different publications with

differing levels of visibility and accessibility. The assessment depends on authors’ evaluation and interpretation from the selected cases.

A variety of policy options have been introduced to control, or support, sustainable use of wild species. These are reviewed in section 6.4. Experts used the mixed methods review to first add to this evaluation by establishing the prevalence of application of each policy instrument based on the proportion of case studies across each practice that included each policy instrument (see section 6.4, Table 6.6). Section 6.5 next synthesizes the evidence gained on effectiveness of policy for the sustainable use of wild species, to pull out the key enabling and constraining conditions, including how governance characteristics support or enable these processes.

3. Illustrative boxes. Finally, similar to previous chapters, experts drew on the evidence they had compiled through the two review processes, and their expert knowledge in different geographies, policies, and practices, to identify a range of illustrative boxes. These boxes span different geographies, practices, policy instruments, and time, and illustrate key aspects of policy responses, contexts, and enabling conditions relevant to Chapter 6.

Table 6.3 Policy effectiveness coding framework.

Coding applied to 100 selected case studies (see the full dataset in the data management report at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4663236>).

Category Group	Sub-Category
Practice	Fishing
	Gathering
	Terrestrial animal harvesting
	Non-extractive practices
	Logging
Policy instruments	Legal and regulatory
	Economic and financial
	Social and information-based
	Right-based and customary
Scale	Temporal
	Spatial
Effectiveness	Ecological
	Social
	Economic*
Enabling conditions	Economic/technological/cultural/ecological condition and interactions
Constraining conditions	
Governance	Interactions among actors and alignment among values and tools
Reference	Information of the article

* Economic and Social are treated separately to identify whether policy options create trade-offs between different subcomponents of sustainability.

6.3 GOVERNANCE

Governance is commonly understood as ways of organizing government and other public institutions, civil society, and private actors in order to create opportunities or solve problems (Kooiman & Bavinck, 2005; Meuleman, 2008). Governance has recently taken center stage in efforts to understand threats to biodiversity and its loss, with growing consensus that inadequate or inappropriate governance is the most significant obstacle to achieving sustainable development and the sustainable use of natural resources (Allison *et al.*, 2012; Cahill, 2010; Cronkleton P. *et al.*, 2008; Ribot, 2004; Sowman & Wynberg, 2014). Closely related, governability is the capacity of a system to govern or to be governed. Governability is influenced by the interactions that exist between the system to be governed and the governing system. Analysis of policy effectiveness requires the interrogation *inter alia* of the nature and role of all actors involved in natural resource use, the way in which these actors interact, and the nature of those interactions. It also requires analysis of the evolving systems of rules, norms,

values, knowledge, and incentives that shape different actions. Many different social and legal systems exist, often alongside one another, ranging from statutory through the customary regulation, with multiple approaches along the spectrum, including informal arrangements (Figure 6.1). These plural governance systems have introduced complex tools and frameworks that actors must navigate to access and use wild species.

Various modes of governance exist and have been conceptualized in different ways, from hierarchies (state-centric governance), networks or co-governance (a constellation of actors in varying partnership arrangements), markets (market-based instruments and incentives), voluntarism (non-binding agreements and instruments) and self-governance (including customary governance) (Sowman & Wynberg, 2014). However, elements of one form of governance are often found in another, such that categorization is fluid and ideal rather than actual (Treib *et al.*, 2007). An overriding common element among these frameworks, which distinguishes governance from

Figure 6 1 Conceptualizing the interactive governance of wild species use.

In the context of this IPBES assessment, the system to be governed includes the social-ecological system within which wild species are used (e.g., gathering in a forest, fishing in the ocean). Adapted from (Jentoft & Bavinck, 2014) under license number 5260851125678 CC-BY NC.

government and management (which is the day-to-day activities (e.g., monitoring) designed to achieve objectives), is that governance is concerned with interactions and processes which occur between a diverse group of actors, including non-state actors often with diverging interests (Bavinck *et al.*, 2005; Kooiman & Bavinck, 2005; Torfing *et al.*, 2012).

Interactive governance theory presents a useful approach to the analyses of governance focused on these interactions. Interactive governance theory divides societal systems into three parts: a system-to-be-governed, a governing system, and the interactions that take place within and between them (Jentoft & Bavinck, 2014) (**Figure 6.1**).

All three parts of the system (system to be governed, governing system, interactions) are understood to be structurally diverse, complex, and dynamic, and operate at various scales. Interactive governance theory therefore encompasses multiple modes of governance, involving the market, state, civil society, and hybrid forms of these. Such a conceptualization captures the polycentricity of actors and arrangements, but also the plurality of the forms of governance (Bavinck & Gupta, 2014). This approach can recognize both *de facto* practices and rules in use, whether formal or customary, and *de jure* practices and rules in law. This is beneficial because customary *de facto* modes of governance developed to guide the use of wild species are often not recognized or accommodated in formal state-centric systems state (Kozanayi, 2018; Sowman & Wynberg, 2014; Sunde, 2014; R. Wynberg & Laird, 2007). Indeed, in many contemporary settings, local or customary forms of law emerge in response to largely ineffective forms of formal law (Karnad, 2017). An approach that can simultaneously analyze statutory and customary governance is needed for evaluations of the governance and use of wild species.

The governing system (*de facto*), whether formal or informal, is comprised of three core orders (Jentoft & Bavinck, 2014):

1. The **values, norms and principles** that underlie governance, and can be understood as ethical principles linked, for example, to social justice and environmental sustainability. The values, norms, and principles related to the sustainable use of wild species are those which would reflect both the range of world views and different ways of knowing among users and communities, as well as the scope of use – which might vary from subsistence use through to recreational use or local or global trade.
2. The **rules and institutions** of governance, including for example, the rights that people have to access resources, their entitlements, and the rules or policy instruments prescribing access and use. The rules and institutions of relevance to the sustainable use of

wild species can be categorized into four categories of policy instruments: legal and regulatory, economic/financial, social and information based, and rights-based and customary approaches typically employed under different governance configurations that are not mutually exclusive.

3. The day-to-day **actions and tools** taken to implement rules, including customary or formal management actions or harvesting regulations. The actions and tools, relevant to the sustainable use of wild species refer to the day to day legal and illegal actions that are used to either enforce or navigate the rules.

Power is a core consideration of interactive governance theory, for power reflects the ability to influence or control the beliefs or actions of others. Power is thus central to understanding interactions within and between the governing system and system to be governed. Power can be exerted in overt (e.g., state control) or diffuse (e.g., hegemonic ideas) ways, shaping the interactions. In interactive governance theory, Jentoft and Bavinck (2014) characterize power differentials as symmetrical or asymmetrical, using these terms to explain the coherence between components of the system. Symmetrical power exists where actors hold equal influence, whereas asymmetrical power exists where one can exert control over the other with no consequence. Where there is compatibility, and symmetrical power differentials, between norms, values and principles, rules and institutions, and the day-to-day actions and tools, conflict is less likely and there are increased opportunities for mutual support. The corollary is that where these elements differ legally, there are fewer opportunities for cooperation and harmonization.

Multilevel governance includes the implementation of public policy across diverse spatial scales from subnational and national to global (Forsyth, 2009). Vertical links could connect actors at the national and subnational levels according to international framework for achieving the shared goals such as climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation (Forsyth, 2009). The structure and operation of nested governance across the scales can fortify more effective natural resource management (Hudson, 2011). Nested governance can contribute towards the robustness of social-ecological systems involving large-scale common pool resources (Marshall, 2008).

The actors involved will similarly vary depending on the type of use, the value of the resource, and the context. These may involve, state and parastatal organizations (e.g., government agencies, United Nations agencies, and intergovernmental bodies), market and commerce (e.g., small business and, multinational corporations), and various civil society (e.g., community groups, non-governmental organizations, and harvesters).

Against this background, and mindful of the legal pluralism that characterizes the use of many wild species, an interactive governance theory approach was adopted to analyze the effectiveness of policy instruments applied to support the sustainable use of wild species (Figure 6.1). Governance was broadly conceptualized to involve various combinations of and interactions between customary law and statutory legislation, as well as everyday approaches in-between, that vary according to the geographical and temporal context, as well as between the three orders of governance (values, norms and principles; rules and institutions; and actions and tools). The analyses of governance thus focus on interactions between the actors, including the state, market, and civil society, involved in the various forms and stages of governance, whether in the system to be governed, the governing system, or both. Chapter 6's experts pay attention to both the symmetries and asymmetries of power as they influence and are influenced by the shape and form of governance arrangements, interactions between statutory and customary approaches, and alignment between the three orders of governance.

6.4 POLICY INSTRUMENTS ADOPTED FOR THE USE OF WILD SPECIES

A policy option reflects a combination of instruments strategically selected and implemented to achieve a specific policy goal. Policy instruments can be defined as “the set of tools and techniques by which governmental authorities wield their power in an attempt to ensure support for an effect or to prevent social change” (Vedung, 2017). Although governments often exert their power independently to introduce and implement policy, governments govern in existing and emerging contexts where grass roots and customary systems of governance co-exist with formal systems of government, multilateral governance, and emerging private, public, and market-based systems. Policies are thus adopted within a governing system, as a set of rules and institutions (Figure 6.1). As highlighted in the previous section, governance is a critical determinant of policy effectiveness and thus forms the overarching framework within which policy effectiveness was evaluated in section 6.5. To begin, the experts review the range of policy options available to support the sustainable use of wild species. In doing so the experts draw on examples from across five practices (fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting, logging, and non-extractive practices) to describe common policy instruments and interventions, across four policy categories (legal & regulatory, economic & financial, social & information based, and rights based & customary instruments) at international, regional, national and subnational scales (Table 6.3).

Importantly, this separation of governance, policy, and practice supports the analysis, whereas it is recognized that in reality:

1. Categorizations of policies may overlap with governance, for example community-based management can be viewed as a policy instrument or as a governance approach.
2. Categorizations of policies may overlap across categories, for example ecolabels and certification schemes reflect both economic financial instruments as well as social and information-based instruments.
3. Categorizations of policies may overlap within categories, for example, some fees can be thought of as payment for ecosystem services schemes – therefore policies in one category can relate to others – however, here each policy option are dealt primarily under one category.
4. Although policies are often developed with a particular practice in mind, they can affect other practices (e.g., a

national park legally designated to limit terrestrial animal harvesting, may also limit non-extractive practices).

5. Finally, policies are often designed to be applied together and thus reinforce one another; however, here the experts present and examine them independently.

The experts therefore acknowledge that the treatment of policy options and the categories they fall into is more rigid and reductive than occurs in reality.

6.4.1 Legal and regulatory instruments

Legal and regulatory-based approaches comprise interventions that formally influence social and economic action through binding rules or ‘regulations’ (Krott, 2005). Legal and regulatory approaches traditionally comprise the most commonly used instruments of government for solving social and economic conflicts (M. S. Park, 2009), or regulating patterns or intensity of use. Legal and regulatory based approaches develop rules for acceptable behavior and limit certain activities in a society (Lemaire, 1998). Legal and regulatory-based instruments include agreements, legislation, regulations, rules, standards, and planning, and are developed and applied at international, regional, national, and local scales (Table 6.4). Although some scholars consider planning a separate type of policy instrument (Jang *et al.*, 2015; M. S. Park, 2009), here planning instruments was included with other regulatory based instruments because of their focus on statutory obligatory guidance. At an international scale, the use of wild species can be regulated through international treaties, pacts, agreements, conventions, and laws or legislation. At all scales (international, regional, national, local) the use of wild species can be further regulated through laws or legislation, standards, regulations, rules, and planning.

6.4.1.1 International agreements and conventions

A treaty is a written international agreement, between states, governed by international law, whether embodied in a single instrument or in two or more related instruments regardless of designation (Article 2 of the Vienna convention). Treaties contain conventions and agreements. An international environmental agreement (sometimes environmental protocol) is an intergovernmental document intended to be legally binding, with a primary stated purpose of preventing or managing human impacts on natural resources (Mitchell, 2019). An international convention is an agreement which becomes legally binding to a particular state when that state ratifies it. If an environmental agreement is among three or more nations, it is referred to as a multilateral environmental agreement. A recent analysis of multilateral environmental

agreements found 90% with fewer than 10 signatory parties, and only 30 agreements with more than 100 parties (Mitchell *et al.*, 2020). Of 1,300 agreements analyzed, one third was directly related to species (e.g., regulating overharvesting of wild animals), the rest indirectly through pollution and energy, or other issues (Mitchell *et al.*, 2020).

Voluntary guidelines are non-legally binding documents, often developed in extended consultation with rights holders, and can be powerful in moving policy discourse and practice towards desired or aspirational goals for sustainable use. For example, in fishing, the voluntary guidelines for securing sustainable small-scale fisheries (FAO, 2015) were co-developed through extensive engagement, over ~20 years, with diverse groups of actors. Voluntary guidelines can lay the foundations, resulting in the enactment of, legally binding multilateral agreements. For example, in gathering, voluntary guidelines on access and benefit sharing preceded the development of the Nagoya protocol on access to genetic resources and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from their utilization to the Convention on Biological Diversity (Nagoya Protocol).

Many of these international efforts to promote sustainable use or protect wild species relate to multiple practices or take an integrated view of species use. Although some have a greater relevance to individual practices. For example, the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES) and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) include policy statements on the sustainable use of wild species that affect fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting, logging, and non-extractive uses. In contrast, the United Nations convention of the law of the seas primarily affects fishing, with lesser effects on gathering (at sea), and non-extractive uses.

Trade is one of the primary channels through which practices involving wild species are regulated at an international scale. The Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora is the premier international instrument, which through species listings in its Appendix I, II, or III, has the capacity to monitor, limit, or prohibit international trade of specimens of wild species to ensure that it does not threaten the survival of the species. Through these mechanisms, the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora is heavily involved in regulating terrestrial animal harvesting, and logging practices, but is also relevant for fishing and gathering practices (see Chapter 2). Other international agreements that exist, and can together with the Convention on international trade in endangered species of wild fauna and flora, work to control the trade of wild species include the Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of wild animals, the Agreement on the conservation of African-Eurasian migratory waterbirds, the Convention on Biological Diversity, and the Forest Law enforcement, Governance and Trade action plan.

Table 6 4 Examples of policy instruments for each practice (fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting, logging, and non-extractive practices).

Pictograms represent (from left to right): fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting, logging and non-extractive practices. Abbreviations: CBD: Convention on Biological Diversity, CBT: Community-based tourism, CITES: Convention on international trade in endangered species of wild fauna and flora, CMS: Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals, CMT: Customary Marine Tenure, FAO: Food and Agriculture Organization, FLEG: Forest Law enforcement, Governance and Trade, FSC: Forest Stewardship Council, HRBA: Human rights-based approach, IWC: International Whaling Commission, MSA: Magnus-Stevens Fisheries Conservation Act, MSC: Marine Stewardship Council, MSP: Marine Spatial Plans, PA: Protected Areas, PES: Payment for Ecosystems Services, REDD+: Reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation, SSF: Small-Scale Fisheries, UNCLOS: United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, UNDRIP: United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, US: United States of America.

Category	Instruments	Description and scale (if relevant)																								
Legal & Regulatory	Treaty/ Agreement/ Convention	International legally binding (or with intent) commitment by states to prevent or manage human impacts on wild species, to be enacted by national and regional bodies	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>CITES</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>CBD's Nagoya Protocol</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>UNCLOS/CMS</td> <td></td> <td>CMS</td> <td></td> <td>FLEGT</td> </tr> <tr> <td>CBD</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>				CITES					CBD's Nagoya Protocol					UNCLOS/CMS		CMS		FLEGT	CBD				
	CITES																									
	CBD's Nagoya Protocol																									
	UNCLOS/CMS		CMS		FLEGT																					
	CBD																									
	Legislation/ Law/ Act	International, regional, national, or local legislation for the sustainable use of wild species	Magnus-Stevens Fisheries Conservation Act	Forestry Law	Wildlife Restoration Act	Forest code	Park Management Act																			
	Rule/ Regulation	Rules and regulations used to enact legislation	Restrictions on gear, species, or place	Novel food regulation	Harvesting and/or Trade bans	Logging Ban	Visitor Limit																			
	Standard/ Planning	Quality standards and planning tools to support and coordinate decision making around sustainable use	MSP	Food Safety Regulation/PA	PA	Forestry legislation Quality standards/PA	CBT/PA																			
	Enforcement & Sanctions	Sanctions are intended to deter future violations, reducing repeat offenses and signaling to the broader population that illegal action has repercussions	Fines, imprisonment, asset forfeiture, revocation permits, law suits																							
	Tax/ fee	Instruments seek to incentivize sustainable use or disincentivize unsustainable use through penalty, while generating funds for improved management	License fee	Tax (medicinal plants)	Tax (ammunition)	Penalty (illegal logging)	Entrance fee																			
Subsidy/ Incentive/ Compensation	Instruments seek to incentivize sustainable use or disincentivize unsustainable through reward	On fuel		Damage compensation																						
PES/ Bonds/ Offsets	Instruments aim to internalize externalities through new financial transactions for environmental goods and make sustainable use economically logical, while generating funds for improved management	Blue bonds	PES	Livestock insurance to avoid hunting wild predators	REDD+																					
Certification	Instruments use information to shift consumer choice to demand more sustainable products and hence practices	MSC	FairWild		FSC PEFC																					
Rights-based & customary	Customary law	Customary laws are intended protect customs, ensure over-use is prevented, and that sufficient wild species will be left for future generations	CMT	Native lands	Communal forest rights	Water rights																				
	Tenure, Access, Rights	Communal ownership of land and wild species is widespread among indigenous peoples and local communities who have developed practices, TEK, and social norms	Tambu	Taboos			Right to roam																			

The Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of wild animals is the global environmental treaty specialized in the Conservation of Migratory Species. Parties to the Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of wild animals “strive towards strictly protecting these animals, conserving or restoring the places where they live, mitigating obstacles to migration and controlling other factors that might endanger them” (CMS, 2021). Although the Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of wild animals does not specifically address sustainable use of these species, the Convention text, Article III paragraph 5 specifies that Parties that are range states of a migratory species listed in Appendix I (migratory species that are endangered) shall prohibit the taking of animals belonging to such species. It can also contribute to sustainability of fishing and terrestrial animal harvesting of migratory species through its joint work program with the Convention on international trade in endangered species of wild fauna and flora, and on the frame of the memorandum of understanding signed between the secretariats of both conventions and the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (Res. Conf. 13.3 in this regard).

The Agreement on the Conservation of African-Eurasian Migratory Waterbirds is an intergovernmental treaty dedicated to the conservation of migratory waterbirds (AEWA, 2018; Madsen *et al.*, 2015) and has the sustainable use of the wild species it targets as one of the main objectives of its strategic plan for 2019–2027 (objective 2: To ensure that any use and management of migratory waterbird populations is sustainable across their flyways) (AEWA, 2019). The Conference of the parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity encourages parties to the convention to develop, revise or update, as appropriate, their regulatory systems to differentiate among subsistence uses, illegal hunting, and domestic and international trade of specimens of wild species and products. Through resolution 2/14 on illegal trade in wild species and wild species products the United Nations environment assembly (2016) urged member states to prevent, combat and eradicate the supply, transit and demand related to illegal trade in wild species and wild species products (United Nations Environment Assembly of the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEA), 2016). Decision XII/18 of the Conference of the parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD, 2014) emphasizes sustainable use of biodiversity in the context of both hunting of wild meat and sustainable wild species management (see Chapter 2).

Although voluntary partnership agreements are developed on a voluntary base, they are legally binding on both sides. The new concept of Forest Law enforcement, Governance and Trade emerged to control illegal timber-harvesting and international trade in illegally harvested timber in 2000s (Brack, 2005). For implementing Forest Law enforcement, Governance and Trade (FLEGT), voluntary bilateral

agreements between producer and consumer countries were introduced. European union adopted the Forest Law enforcement, Governance and Trade action plan including voluntary partnership agreements. The voluntary partnership agreement require that producer countries develop verifying systems to exclude illegal timber and consumer countries import only licensed timber from that country. The voluntary partnership agreement, as a voluntary scheme, supports to avoid biodiversity loss by illegal timber-harvesting. Forest Law enforcement, Governance and Trade has a strong emphasis on the central government and the privileging of regulatory instruments over market-based forms of governing (Van Heeswijk & Turnhout, 2013).

A number of international agreements exist that focus on logging or gathering practices including the International Convention on Temperate and Boreal Forests (Montreal Process) and the Pan-European Forest Process (formerly the Helsinki Process). Furthermore, and as seen above, several global environmental conventions contain provisions to regulate certain activities related to wild forests and logging. For example, the Convention on Biological Diversity contains provisions related to logging, and gathering, in particular where traditional practices and local communities are concerned. The United Nations convention to combat desertification addresses deforestation and reforestation, the Bern convention on the conservation of European wildlife and natural habitats where planning of the Emerald network is concerned or the Economic Development Partnership act which improves management (including logging) in protected areas.

People have been fishing the oceans for centuries. However, in the years following the Second World War fishing effort on the high seas increased greatly, facilitated by technological advances in vessel construction, fishing gears, navigation, and on-board fish processing, and by development of international chains for processing, marketing, and sales. The resultant increase in overfishing was an important factor in negotiation of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS). The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea and the United Nations agreement for the implementation of the provisions of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea of 10 December 1982 relating to the Conservation and management of straddling fish Stocks and highly migratory fish Stocks are the most relevant international agreements pertaining to fishing (**Box 6.14**). The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, signed in 1982 and ratified by 116 countries since, provides the overarching international legal agreement under which activities at sea are regulated. The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea *inter alia* determines the sovereign rights of coastal States and outlines the obligation to conserve and manage living resources and the marine environment (Art. 192). The Fish Stocks Agreement elaborates on these provisions of the United Nations

Convention on the Law of the Sea in relation to straddling stocks and highly migratory stocks. Article 5 of the Fish Stocks Agreement gives conservation and management principles, including the promotion of optimal utilization (i.e., intended to be sustainable), management that is based on scientific evidence, and uses precautionary and ecosystem-based approaches.

The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea includes provisions that entrenched national jurisdiction of the Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) for 200 miles from coastlines. However, neither United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea nor the Fish Stocks Agreement cover inland fishing, which comprises over half of all fish species and nearly 30% of global catches (Funge-Smith & Bennett, 2019). Furthermore, areas beyond the 200 nautical miles (nm) exclusive economic zone from shore are considered by the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea as international waters, or areas beyond national jurisdiction. The regulation of uses of biodiversity (including harvested wild fish) in these areas has been discussed in a lengthy process under the auspices of the United Nations, starting in the early 2000s and resulting in an agreement to hold intergovernmental conferences on the topic starting in 2018. A long-term effort has been underway to get better regulation for the high seas through an internationally legally binding instrument, with negotiations being held in an intergovernmental conference on the topic, with the first session held in 2018 and the second in 2019.

However, the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea did include provisions under the duty to cooperate (Article 117) that facilitated development of Regional Fisheries Management Organizations (RFMOs) in areas beyond national jurisdictions, and laid out the mandates and requirements for operation of Regional Fisheries Management Organizations. The guidance and constraints on Regional Fisheries Management Organizations operations laid out in the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea were refined and clarified in the United Nations Fish Stocks Agreement of 1995. The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) notes at least 50 different regional fisheries bodies have been established.

Under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea and the Fish Stocks Agreement, Regional Fisheries Management Organizations have the mandate and competence to adopt legally binding conservation and management measures, which have to be implemented and translated into actions at the country and regional levels, as appropriate, by the member states. The measures should ensure long-term sustainability and promote optimum utilization of fishery resource, be based on the best scientific evidence available; and decisions must apply the precautionary approach. Correspondingly, Regional Fisheries Management Organizations routinely have science advisory

bodies comprising experts largely drawn from the member states' secretariats which coordinate reporting, oversight and enforcement of regulations, and annual meetings where Parties discuss compliance and regulatory issues, consider the science advice, and adopt measures for regulating harvest levels and methods (Garcia *et al.*, 2014).

The FAO reports that there are now more than 20 Regional Fisheries Management Organizations, of which 12 are generic, 5 consider tuna and tuna-like species, 3 manage anadromous stocks, 1 manages halibut and 1 manages cetaceans (FAO, 2020). Regional Fisheries Management Organizations coverage of oceans in the northern hemisphere is much greater than coverage of oceans in the southern hemisphere, particularly for fisheries for species other than tuna (Figure 3.15). The track record of Regional Fisheries Management Organizations for effectively deterring overfishing and illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing is spotty and contested, but there is evidence of successes and overall improving trends in performance (see section 3.3.1 in Chapter 3). The ongoing negotiations of an implementing agreement for the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea to deal more broadly with biodiversity beyond national jurisdictions may further alter the mandate and measures of Regional Fisheries Management Organizations. Currently all of them discuss issues such as bycatches and impacts of fishing gears in the fisheries they manage, but universal performance standards have not been adopted.

The International Whaling Commission was set up in 1946 under the International Convention for the Regulation of Whaling and is the global body charged with the conservation and management of whales, thus relating to both fishing and non-extractive practices of whaling. Three different types of whaling are recognized by the International Whaling Commission; subsistence whaling, commercial whaling, and scientific whaling. Subsistence whaling for traditional purpose is allowed in some places, but the International Whaling Commission put in place a moratorium on commercial whaling since 1986. A small number of countries have expressed reservations or objections to this moratorium (Norway, Iceland, and Russia), and some continue to catch whales commercially. The International Whaling Commission includes the regulation of whale watching and measurement of the impact of this activity in species population (Sitar *et al.*, 2016). Whale watching is taken as a general description of any marine mammals as indicated by the International Whaling Commission (Parsons, 2012).

6.4.1.2 Legislation, regulations, and rules

Legislations, regulations and rules are implemented at the local, national, and regional level as a means for states and organizations to work towards fulfilling their

international obligations. Local, national, and regional bodies, some of which are advisory and others that have a legal mandate, support this work by enacting legislation through regulations. Regulations are measures undertaken to influence people by means of formulated rules and directives which mandate receivers to act in accordance with what is ordered in these rules and directives (Vedung *et al.*, 1998). National legal and regulatory rules, that apply to the sustainable use of wild species, include bans or limits on what, when, where, how, and by whom extraction can take place. Legal and regulatory instruments often exist alongside, or reinforce other instruments, such as economic and market based, social and information-based, and customary and rights-based. Furthermore, national scale instruments are often supported by, or integrated with international instruments (Box 6.1).

A body of regulation centered on quality control, and safety and efficacy standards, increasingly influences the

harvesting, use, and trade of products from particularly fishing and gathering practices, especially those associated or connected to markets in high income nations. Such policies may be determined at international (e.g., FAO's Codex Alimentarius), regional (e.g., European Union Novel Foods Regulation) or national levels (e.g., United States Food and Drug Administration requirements). This means that wild algae, plants and fungi producers may be required to institute sophisticated procedures for tracking materials that end up as medicinal, cosmetic, personal care products, food and beverages. Although these are intended as standards to protect consumers, particularly in high income nations, there is a risk of these regulations diverting scarce resources away from domestic food safety issues and towards international standards (FAO *et al.*, 2021).

Food safety legislation such as FAO's Codex Alimentarius has often proved a formidable obstacle to international trade for food products particularly affecting fishing and gathering

Box 6.1 Non-lethal harvesting: aquarium trade.

The small-scale and multi-species non-lethal fishing that supply the marine aquarium trade represent important livelihood opportunities for coastal communities, especially in exporting, mostly lower income nations where resources and alternative options for generating income can be limited (Rhyne *et al.*, 2012; Wabnitz, 2003). Species that are part of the marine aquarium trade also provide valuable benefits to hobbyists, and play a role in educating the general public about coral reef ecosystems (Rhyne *et al.*, 2014). The aquarium industry as a whole is of relatively low volume yet very high value, thus potentially providing an incentive to conserve reef habitats from which most species are harvested. Marine aquarium fisheries are extremely selective, with fish for instance typically harvested by hand, snorkeling or using, where permitted, an underwater breathing apparatus such as SCUBA. Sustainable fish harvest involves the use of small mesh nets that seek to not damage the target fish or non-target species, or the habitat (Wabnitz & Wood, 2017). However, the use of cyanide has been widely reported in aquarium fishing, which damages the broader ecosystem and results in mortality rates of up to 90% (Dee *et al.*, 2019; Madeira *et al.*, 2020; Miltz, Kinch, *et al.*, 2018; Raghavan *et al.*, 2018; Vaz *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, reports of over-harvesting, high mortality levels, disease and trade of invasive species remain, raising concern for this trade (Madduppa *et al.*, 2018; Miltz, Foale, *et al.*, 2018).

Management of the trade is daunting due in part to the wide diversity of fish, coral, other invertebrate species, and live rock involved in the trade (Dee *et al.*, 2014) as well as the need to contextualize fisheries management to local conditions. Globally, many strategies to monitor, regulate and manage the aquarium trade exist including, for instance, closures, banned-species lists, quotas, gear restrictions, size limits, licensing, limited entry into the fishery, and regulations on imports. However, monitoring

remains challenging, particularly for small scale aquarium trade (Biondo & Burki, 2020; Biondo & Calado, 2021). As aquarium fishing is export-oriented, Pacific Island Countries and Territories involved in the trade have experienced relatively good enforcement of management measures at the point of export.

In Fiji, for example, current aquarium trade policies include a ban on the export of live rock, a (possibly temporary) ban on the export of coral; a quota system for coral; and a requirement for companies to have an environmental impact assessment, a harvesting area management plan, an export permit from the ministry of fisheries, an export permit for species covered by the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora from the ministry responsible for the environment, a fishing license for the operator of a harvesting vessel, and to regularly submit statistics to the ministry of fisheries. While no official national aquarium fishery management plan currently is in place, existing regulations and policies pertinent to the marine aquarium trade essentially can be considered as a *de facto* management plan (Gillett & Halford, 2020).

Harvesting and export of species for the marine aquarium trade in Australia are managed at state level by a well enforced policy framework, including fisheries management measures such as catch limits; logbook systems; size limits and seasonal closures for certain species; regularly undertaken assessments to evaluate the environmental performance of fisheries as mandated under the Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act 1999 (EPBC Act) and to promote the ecological sustainability of target fisheries; permits; limited entry; list of no take species; legally defined harvest/special management areas as well as types and specifications of gear allowed; and export controls.

practices (Brown, 2005; Burgener, 2007; Iqbal, 1993; Pierce & Burgener, 2010). However, governments tend to act quickly when these obstacles arise. For example, in the 1990s when the European Union and the United States of America set maximum acceptable levels of aflatoxins that threatened gathering for the Brazil nut (*Bertholletia* spp.) trade, the Bolivian government jumped into action, passing a series of food safety measures that created norms for Brazil nut classification, sanitation practices and aflatoxin sampling, drawing upon the FAO's Codex Alimentarius (Cronkleton P. *et al.*, 2008; Soldán, 2003). These steps allowed Bolivian Brazil nuts to maintain access to international markets.

Under Article XIV of the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora, signatory governments are recommended to establish stricter domestic measures on the international trade of the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora-listed species. This includes regulations on the international trade of species listed in the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora Appendix II, for which non-detriment findings studies are required, in order to demonstrate that legal international trade will not threaten the survival of the species. The Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora also enables national scale trade bans for species listed in Appendix I (Conrad, 2012). These measures tend to focus on species in commercial trade, or form part of national efforts to protect endangered or indigenous species or regulate trade under the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (Section 6.4.1.1). Although the impact of these measures can be controversial, some unexpected and undesired conservation outcomes have been documented (Weber *et al.*, 2015). The goal of trade bans is usually to reduce harvesting pressures, such as when fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting, or logging involves threatened wild species (Fischer, 2010). A well-publicized trade ban clearly specifies when a species is no longer legally available. This splits demand, removing the demand of law-abiding consumers, and leaving only illegal demand. To encourage law-abiding behavior, governments can ensure availability of substitutes to absorb the previous demand, impose consequences for non-compliance (fines and penalties), and that a stigma become associated with consuming products obtained illegally (Conrad, 2012; Fischer, 2010). However, the idealized trade-bans described here tend not to happen as bans have often been mismanaged, they struggle to regulate illegal trade, and potentially spur trade by increasing scarcity (e.g., Rivalan *et al.*, 2007).

Most countries, particularly with abundant natural resources, where fishing, terrestrial animal harvesting, and logging practices occur have dedicated sector specific legislation

(e.g., Forestry Act in the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, Magnus-Stevens Fisheries Conservation Act in the United States of America), as well as public bodies regulating the economic, technical, environmental and sometimes social affairs of those sectors. In some cases, countries with very large-scale forestry practices (e.g., Brazil, Russia) all forest-related issues are harvested under the same cover and adopted as a single fundamental legal act, such as a forest code. Although historically developed for logging, forestry legislation, reflecting international policy trends, increasingly covers all activities that occur in the forest (e.g., gathering and terrestrial animal harvesting). Importantly, bodies of forestry legislation of major global forest importers, such as the European Union and the United States of America are not only concerned about national or supranational forestry practices, but also about the legality of imported timber. In the absence of global intergovernmental arrangements regulating logging, the European Union Timber Directive and United States of America National Forest Act effectively play this role in some respects.

The rules and laws in forestry legislation that relate to gathering, intersect with economic and financial instruments to include permits, quotas, management plans, royalties, and taxes. However, the track record for implementing such policies remains poor (Ortiz, 2002; Pierce & Burgener, 2010), largely due to the inappropriate use of timber-based approaches for the diverse, complex and perhaps less lucrative gathering practice (Laird *et al.*, 2010). The scope and definition of the products covered have remained unclear, and few specific actions have been stipulated (Fiji Islands, 1992; Republic of Cameroon, 1994; Republica de Bolivia, 1996). Increasingly, countries have begun to fine-tune such policies to reflect the socioeconomic, ecological and cultural realities of using gathered products. This has resulted in a number of specific improvements in the ways these products are regulated, including re-thinking the use of costly and complex inventories and management plans for gathering, and revising quota and permitting systems (Areki & Cunningham, 2010; Cronkleton & Pacheco, 2010; Kluppel *et al.*, 2010; Laird *et al.*, 2010). Some forestry laws have also included gathering in management plans for logging operations to minimize negative impacts on locally valuable products. In Brazil, national and state governments have passed laws prohibiting the logging of high-value plant, algae and fungi species (Kluppel *et al.*, 2010), and in Bolivia prohibitions on felling Brazil nut trees arrived in 2004 as part of a decree addressing property conflicts (Cronkleton & Pacheco, 2010).

There are many parallels in how fishing and terrestrial animal harvesting practices are regulated across the world. In general, regulations differ based on whether harvesting is for commercial, traditional, subsistence, or sport purposes (Emery & Pierce, 2005). In most of Africa, wild animals

are either owned by the state (e.g., in Kenya), or have no ownership (Lindsey *et al.*, 2013). Fishing and terrestrial animal harvesting are therefore regulated through legal instruments, which stipulate restrictions on who, when, where, what, and how activities can take place. These restrictions are often controlled through licensing, permits, and quotas (Cirelli & Morgera, 2009; Lindsey *et al.*, 2013). Although, in some places, subsistence fishing or hunting does not require a license or permit (e.g., Zambia, Tanzania, Botswana, Malawi, Mozambique) (Cirelli & Morgera, 2009).

Many countries combine legal and regulatory instruments with economic and financial instruments. For example, allocation of ownership or user-rights to private and communal landholders is often under specific conditions, such as building fences that support sustainable use (Barnett & Patterson, 2005; Cirelli & Morgera, 2009; P. A. Lindsey *et al.*, 2013). User-rights in addition allow land owners, or fishing quota holders, to fish or hunt for themselves or to sell these rights to private fishing or hunting operators or tourists (Bond *et al.*, 2004; P. A. Lindsey *et al.*, 2007). However, hunting which is in disagreement with specific permissions is considered illegal in most contexts (P. A. Lindsey *et al.*, 2013).

Yet, in hunting the lack of legal and regulatory approaches has been associated with unsustainable use. For example, for 50 years there was an absence of hunting regulations in Brazil, which led to the unregulated use of wild species, and a general scenario of lack of data on the activity (Fernandes-Ferreira & Alves, 2017). Hunting is allowed when the hunter or their family are hungry and when conducted by indigenous and traditional peoples, but management is generally lacking throughout the country (Vieira de Mattos *et al.*, 2019). In the Malaysian state of Sarawak, the 1998 Wild Life Protection Ordinance banned all commercial sales of wild species.

National regulations of non-extractive, recreational use practices are often centralized, drawing on international guidelines and research, to limit the number of users that the environment can sustain or control their behavior (Avila-Foucat *et al.*, 2013; Parra-López & Martínez-González, 2018). For example, in line with the International Whaling Commission guidelines many national legal regulations concerning whale watching have evolved from voluntary, to formal, to participatory and adaptive (Mallard, 2019) to control the speed and noise from boats, distance from whales, acceptable behavior, and time spent whale watching (Avila-Foucat *et al.*, 2017; Sitar *et al.*, 2016). Specific methods for calculating and regulating the number of visitors are diverse and contested (Avila-Foucat *et al.*, 2013; Wall, 2020). Carrying capacity regulations based on establishing a specific number of visitors and standards have evolved into other management frameworks such as limits of acceptable change, visitor impact management,

visitor experience and resource protection, and visitor activities management process that integrate different management options, are more dynamic and involve different stakeholders (Farrell & Marion, 2002).

International guidelines (e.g., United Nations declaration on the rights of indigenous peoples, see section 6.5.1), national regulations (e.g., native American graves protection and reparation act), and locally developed codes of conduct exist to guide non-extractive use practices at spiritual and cultural sites to ensure sacred sites and practices are protected and norms adhered to (C. Negi, 2013). Many of these regulations protect spiritual practices that involve wild species, or protect wild species that are sacred or found in sacred places. For example, in the United States of America, the Fish and Wildlife Service can issue permits to indigenous peoples allowing them to obtain feathers from endangered bird species for spiritual/ritual uses, the genus *Ficus* is protected in many parts of the world because of cultural and spiritual beliefs, and the sacred species of Shiling (*Osmanthus fragrans*) is found in temples located in the Garhwal hills and Kumaun Himalayas (C. Negi, 2013).

The binding nature of a formal, regulation-based approach to wild species governance relies heavily on the enforcing the rules, including the use of sanctions against violators, such as fines, imprisonment, asset forfeiture, revocation permits and warning letters (Pascual *et al.*, 2021). Such sanctions are intended to deter future violations, reducing repeat offenses and signaling to the broader population that illegal action has repercussions, although the criminological literature highlights the complexities of deterring illegal behavior (Wilson & Boratto, 2020).

For example, penalties and fines can act as a deterrent against unsustainable practices or trade in banned species, and revenues from penalties and fines charged can be allocated to habitat and biodiversity protection (Klasen, 2018). Penalties and sanctions can be applied to all extractive practices, including terrestrial animal harvesting, fishing, gathering, and logging. However, payment is not always allocated exclusively to environment protection or management.

International agreements, conventions and guidelines can support monitoring to ensure compliance with domestic regulations. For example, the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora Database reports the details of >850,000 legal export and imports across the signatory countries, helping to monitor legal, sustainable trade (CITES, 2021). However, such international instruments have notably few opportunities to enforce against violations.

National legislation and domestic government agencies are primarily responsible for enforcement, including monitoring

for compliance, pursuing violators and imposing sanctions. In many countries, violations of many sustainable use regulations, such as the abuse of quotas, are considered comparatively less serious and are treated as administrative offenses or misdemeanors, rather than as criminal offenses. Such violations are typically dealt with by the relevant agencies, such as forest departments, which can often directly issue fines and seize illegal harvest (Pascual *et al.*, 2021). However, some violations, such as those involving protected species, are criminal offenses in many countries that are formally prosecuted *via* the court system and result in both fines and lengthy imprisonment. In some jurisdictions, violations of wild species legislation may also be the object of environmental lawsuits that can provide unique ways to enforcing environmental rights (see below).

The types and scales of sanctions for violating wild species regulations vary widely around the world. For example, the maximum allowable imprisonment term for illegally hunting a protected species in Brazil is 1.5 years, while in Kenya it can result in life imprisonment (Pascual *et al.*, 2021). Approaches to financial sanctions are similarly diverse, with fines ranging from 0 to 200,000 United States dollars, variously set based on default values, market prices of specimen, number of individuals involved, and local salary scales (Pascual *et al.*, 2021). Differences in sanctions handed out can limit the efficacy of these deterrents (Pascual *et al.*, 2021).

Amidst widespread calls to increase sanctions for wild species violations, there are long-standing debates about which approaches are most likely to improve environmental outcomes in ways that are socially acceptable (Wilson & Boratto, 2020). Indeed, there is widespread evidence that enforcement and sanctions are often disproportionately on those involved in harvesting, rather than trading and consuming wild species, and that conservation enforcement disproportionately affects indigenous, poor and other marginalized communities (Duffy *et al.*, 2019; Paudel *et al.*, 2020; L. Wilson & Boratto, 2020).

Despite the formal nature of government enforcement, informal sanctions are also important in the context of wild species use. This is especially true because, in many countries, wild species conservation, management, use and violations occur beyond the sphere of formal government control (Sjöstedt & Linell, 2021). Social norms can serve to reinforce (or actively oppose) government enforcement of regulations, depending on whether the underlying regulations are aligned with local priorities, customs and needs (Kinzig *et al.*, 2013).

Alongside traditional sanctioning approaches based on fines and imprisonment, environmental liability lawsuits can help enforce wild species regulations. Such environmental liability legislation forms part of national legislation in a great many countries. These laws hold responsible parties liable for

the environmental harm they cause, and thus responsible for providing remedies. Environmental liability legislation is important to sustainable use because, where legal trade is violated (illegal trade, quota abuse, inappropriate standards, etc.) there is a need for appropriate enforcement responses that not only punish violation, but provide remedies that meaningfully address conservation impacts and values of nature (Pascual *et al.*, 2021).

Although laws and procedures vary widely, many countries allow different stakeholders to bring environmental lawsuits to court (Pascual *et al.*, 2021), seeking remedies such as:

1. Injunctions to stop harmful activities from continuing, such as the suspension of harvest licenses;
2. Orders for government agencies to act in accordance with the law or review their procedures, such as the processes for setting harvest quotas, or the ways in which government agencies chose to enforce wild species legislation (e.g., (Brosi & Biber, 2012).
3. Orders that the parties responsible for causing environmental harm be liable for providing remedial actions, such as species reintroductions, clean-up or reforestation (Pascual *et al.*, 2021).

As such, environmental lawsuits can be used to seek compensation from illegal traders of wild species resources, or to challenge quotas, the (mis)allocation of permits, failure to implement the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora Non-Detriment Findings, failure to list a protected species, or government failure to allow for traditional harvest of a species. Related litigation can thus not only support sustainable use, but also act as a means of “making nature’s value legible” (6.4.2) and for recognizing human rights (6.4.4.4) through court actions that formally recognize different types of rights that are frequently overlooked or violated in policy processes.

6.4.1.3 National standards and planning

Standards have been developed in several countries that relate to non-extractive uses, including wildlife watching, and other forms of sustainable nature-based tourism. For example, community-based tourism standards, combine legal and regulatory approaches with social and information-based approaches, and in doing so seek to create local enterprises that provide livelihood benefits to communities while protecting indigenous cultures and environments (Simpson, 2009). The aims of community-based tourism include equitable participation in efforts to enhance sustainable use of natural resources and social well-being (Stone, 2015). However, Iorio and Corsale (2014) indicate that communities are not homogenous, and involvement in community-based tourism depends on the resources

and skills of the community. National legislation, such as forestry legislation normally sets standards for logging practices. These include the setting of environmental quality objectives (including forest rotations, logging rules etc.), threshold values, liability rules, impact regulations, technical requirements etc. Other practices covered under standard setting include food quality standards that relate to gathering and fishing.

Planning instruments such as marine spatial plans and land use planning including systematic conservation planning and protected areas have been applied to various ecosystems, covering terrestrial animal harvesting, fishing, gathering, logging and non-extractive use practices. Protected areas are a cornerstone of biodiversity conservation, one of the objectives of the Convention on Biological Diversity. Thus, protected areas play a major role in maintaining key habitats, providing refugia, allowing for species migration and movement, and ensuring the maintenance of natural processes across the landscape. The Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity, at its 7th meeting in 2004, adopted the Programme of Work on Protected Areas. The Programme of Work on Protected Areas enshrines the development of participatory, ecologically representative, and effectively managed national and regional systems of protected areas, stretching across national boundaries where necessary. The Programme of Work on Protected Areas can be considered as the core framework for the designation and management of protected areas. It offers a system for cooperation between multiple actors, including governments, donors, non-governmental organizations and local communities (J.-Y. Park *et al.*, 2019).

6.4.2 Economic and financial instruments

Economic instruments are all those political means of intervention that formally influence social or economic action through the exchange of “economic values” (Krott, 2005). Economic policy instruments involve either the handing out or the taking away of material resources, be they in cash or in kind (Vedung *et al.*, 1998). Economic and financial instruments include any policy option that uses price as a basis for the governance of wild-species, and can be further categorized into centralized instruments and decentralized instruments (see Hahn *et al.*, 2015). Evidently, there is overlap here with some regulatory instruments, in particular sanctions (e.g., fines). Centralized policy approaches include traditional fiscal instruments such as taxes (and tax reliefs), subsidies, fees, charges, and budgetary allocations; whereas, decentralized instruments create new markets for services and goods to guide environmental governance such as through conditional and voluntary incentive schemes (e.g., payment for ecosystem services), compensation payments, and new financing streams (e.g.,

blended finance and blue/green bonds) (Hahn *et al.*, 2015) (Table 6.4). What generally characterizes the broad range of economic policy approaches is that they supplement approaches that outright ban resource use. Financial instruments use market signals to control or direct resource use, as well as to generate flows of finance that can be used to subsidize research, management, monitoring, local livelihoods and initiatives to protect terrestrial vertebrate species.

6.4.2.1 Taxes and Fees

Taxes and fees are economic instruments, whereby users pay to use or access wild species, are designed to incentivize sustainable use or disincentivize unsustainable use while generating funds that can be redirected towards conservation, or the sustainable management of wild species. Taxes can be effective if they are set at an appropriate level, can be administered, and adequately monitored. Although taxes can be perceived as overly top-down and might not be supported by all actors, which can result in problems with implementation due to lack of buy-in or political lobbying (Bräuer *et al.*, 2006). Fees are often applied to non-extractive use practices, particularly when the activity takes place in a natural protected area or when a private company charges for a service, through entrance fees or for example, for conducting safaris on national parks. Fees are similarly applied to wildlife watching, for example whale watching generates 2.1 billion United States dollars in expenditures (including charges for the trip) and 13,000 jobs worldwide (O’Connor *et al.*, 2009), however, standards, codes of conduct, and regulations are more important instruments for regulating non-extractive use practices than price.

Taxes, fees, and royalties are some of the most frequently applied financial instruments to hunting practices, often in conjunction with quotas and permits, such as for wild species capture, hunting, and trade. Similar to fees, taxes and royalties can be used to generate revenue and to support the sustainable use of wild species (Bräuer *et al.*, 2006; Klasen, 2018). One example of such a mechanism has been implemented for hunting, sport shooting or personal defense in the United States of America, through the Federal Aid in Wildlife Restoration Act, popularly known as the Pittman–Robertson Act (1937) (Spidalieri, 2012). The Act provides funding for habitat preservation, harvest management, hunter safety education, research, restoration, and monitoring, not only for game species but for many other species. Funds for the act come from an 11% federal tax on sporting arms, ammunition, and archery equipment, and a 10% tax on handguns (Pack *et al.*, 2013; USFWS, 2013). These funds are collected from the manufacturers and are distributed each year to the states and territorial areas by the Department of the Interior. The state covers the full amount of an approved project and then applies

for reimbursement through federal aid for up to 75% of the project's expenses; the state is responsible for the other 25% of the project's cost (USFWS, 2019). Each year, nearly 200 million United States dollars in hunters' federal excise taxes are distributed to state agencies (USFWS, 2013).

Another example of a fee is that of the federal duck stamp in the United States of America. This is the result of the migratory bird hunting stamp act (or duck stamp act), which specifies that all waterfowl hunters 16 years of age and over must annually buy and carry a migratory bird hunting and conservation stamp. Ninety-eight cents of every duck stamp dollar go directly into the migratory bird conservation fund, which seeks to protect wetlands vital to the survival of migratory waterfowl. Since 1934, some 800 million United States dollars have gone into that fund to protect over 5.7 million acres of wild habitat (USFWS, 2017). One of the reasons for the duck stamp's success is that anyone can purchase the federal duck stamp, not just hunters, so it has become a collector's item.

As these examples demonstrate, through a tax model, hunters have made large contributions to conservation. However, as the United States of America continues to urbanize, and as hunting has drawn criticism from conservationists and animal rights advocates, hunting participation rate has declined over the last decades and average age of hunters has increased (Heffelfinger *et al.*, 2013; Spidalieri, 2012) – although notable increases occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic. Maintaining this system of conservation will require a broader scope. This tax model is referred to as a “user-pay, user-benefit” system, as extractive users (as hunters) both pay and benefit. However, this model has been heavily criticized around the world, for being thought to allocate access to nature on an ability to pay basis. Furthermore, other groups, that engage in non-extractive use practices, such as campers, hikers and wild species watchers (non-extractive users) also benefit from the presence of wild species and conservation programs, yet do not traditionally pay into the system through federal taxes (Pack *et al.*, 2013). However, the duck stamp is now becoming a strong societal norm, and is also the basis of a famous artistic contest (for who will draw the stamp of the year), so that many non-hunters also buy duck stamps. An expansion of the tax model has been proposed, through a new tax on outdoor recreation equipment, which would contribute to wild species conservation. This way, non-extractive users might directly fund conservation efforts. Said additional tax would supplement funding and provide new economic support for the conservation of game and non-game. However, the legislation needed to implement the new tax proposal has not been enacted (Pack *et al.*, 2013; Spidalieri, 2012).

Taxes can also be used to kick-start innovative sustainable use programs. For example, in crocodile/alligator farming, many of the technologies now used were developed by

government research expenditure, and governments had to invest significantly in management and for example in obtaining support from the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora to be able to export (CONABIO, 2021b). That support was gradually withdrawn as industries came on line, and in some countries, even the monitoring programs are funded by industry. Louisiana and Florida in the United States of America with alligators, Northern Territory in Australia with saltwater crocodiles, Zimbabwe with Nile crocodiles, are all examples. Innovative new industries in many fields, considered high risk initially, often depend on interim subsidies to get established. With larger crocodiles (and likely many other predators on people and livestock), a key role of sustainable use programs is to provide commercial incentives for landowners and the public to tolerate crocodiles, representing a pragmatic intervention.

Taxes are equally applied to gathering, to enable the sustainable use of wild species. Through taxes, governments can earn revenue from what is perceived as a lucrative business, or as an incentive to stimulate the practice. Such efforts have had variable effects. For example, in Cameroon, the government instituted new taxes on medicinal plants in the 1990s in response to a widespread belief that the medicinal plants were ‘green gold’ (Laird *et al.*, 2010). In India, tendu (*Diospyros melanoxylon*), which provides as much as 74% of Orissa state's total earnings from forests, was nationalized in several states in the 1960s and 1970s due to its high value and the interest of government bodies in benefiting from its trade (Lele *et al.*, 2010).

Taxation as a policy tool can thus have significant consequences, especially with regard to influencing behavioral change. In some cases, tax relief can help to stimulate the gathering practice, but when used as a tool to collect revenues, government taxation has more often than not led to bureaucratic and confusing gathering measures. This can leave communities and government authorities unclear about proper procedures, providing government officials an opportunity to request additional ‘unofficial payments’ (Arquiza *et al.*, 2010; Laird *et al.*, 2010; Ndoye & Awono, 2010). Inappropriate and burdensome measures can also make unofficial payments or bribes preferable to following regulations.

‘Unofficial taxation’ (i.e., bribery) is a very real cost of doing business in many countries. Bribes are tolerated, and even encouraged, by some governments, and they work like any other policy stick to change behavior. In a number of countries, roadblocks set up by government officials to ‘control’ the transport of goods from rural to urban areas, and check required documents, divert profits from traders and have knock-on effects for hunters, fishers, gathers, and loggers (Arquiza *et al.*, 2010; Ndoye & Awono, 2010; Sunderland *et al.*, 2010). In the Philippines, one study

showed that unofficial payments, or “SOPS” (standard operating procedures), significantly impact the already meagre livelihoods of indigenous peoples’ dependent on wild algae, plants and fungi (Arquiza *et al.*, 2010).

6.4.2.2 Subsidies and incentives

Like taxes, subsidies can work to incentivize sustainable use or disincentivize unsustainable -and illegal- use of wild species (Hahn *et al.*, 2015). However, unlike taxes, subsidies seek to influence behavior through reward, rather than penalty. Subsidies are often used to enable entry into a practice, by reducing the costs of entry or operation, and in doing so enable greater resource extraction.

Beneficial subsidies are those that promote resource conservation (Milazzo, 1998; Sumaila *et al.*, 2016), for example, in Brazil, fishermen receive a salary (minimum wage) for 4 months during the fish reproductive period in order not to fish, and in other instances subsidies are paid to marine protected areas, fisheries management, or research. However, because of the nature of subsidies, they can create perverse environmental outcomes. Such subsidies are referred to as harmful subsidies because they drive overexploitation, include for example through fuel or boat subsidies that lower the cost of unsustainable (Milazzo, 1998; Sumaila *et al.*, 2016).

In a recent global analysis, estimates of beneficial fishing subsidies were found to be considerably smaller than harmful capacity enhancing subsidies (30% versus 63%), furthermore, these harmful subsidies were found to be growing (Sumaila *et al.*, 2019). Global subsidies in fishing, amounts to 35 billion United States dollars, the majority of which are harmful fuel subsidies that drive overexploitation (Sakai *et al.*, 2019), with beneficial subsidies that support sustainability through management and surveillance, accounting for as little as 5% of all subsidies (Sakai *et al.*, 2019). Accordingly, pressure is mounting on the need to remove harmful fishing subsidies, an item that is currently under negotiation in the World Trade Organization talks (WTO, 2018).

However, the removal of subsidies can be challenging. Once subsidies are established, market prices adjust accordingly, and removal is likely to significantly impact the social wellbeing of many local communities, in hitting the poorest fishers hardest (Cisneros-Montemayor *et al.*, 2020; Hicks *et al.*, 2014). Consequently, in discussions around removal of harmful subsidies, exceptions to the rules- or special and differential treatment is recommended to minimize these social impacts (Sumaila *et al.*, 2021).

Compensation payments, which can also be conceptualized as a conservation subsidy, are frequently applied to encourage sustainable hunting. The most-often mentioned

compensation approach in the literature regarding wild species hunting is that of damage compensation (Bulte *et al.*, 2003). A damage compensation scheme is a tool used to mitigate human- wild species conflict, and might, in many cases, deter illegal hunting of conflicting species. It reimburses individuals who have suffered the costs of wild species – damage (to crops, livestock, property or personal safety) through monetary payments or non-monetary compensation such as replacement animals or food and supplies (Nyhus *et al.*, 2005; Ravenelle & Nyhus, 2017). Most compensation programs aim to increase tolerance towards wild species, thereby reducing “retaliatory killing” of wild species and resistance to conservation management actions (Maheshwari *et al.*, 2014; Shilongo *et al.*, 2018). According to an analysis of global patterns and trends in human- wild species conflict compensation, a majority of programs focus on carnivores (large cats, bears, wolves and crocodiles), and livestock losses represent the most common reason for wild species compensation (Ravenelle & Nyhus, 2017). Similarly, there are payments for compensation for damage caused by attacks to people by carnivores, as has been documented in several cases of crocodile attacks in different areas where these species live (Das & Jana, 2018).

A large majority of compensation schemes are based on ex-post compensation (Ravenelle & Nyhus, 2017; Schwerdtner & Gruber, 2007). However, even when they are effective, they have been widely criticized because compensation is not tied to incentives (Maheshwari *et al.*, 2014; Nyhus *et al.*, 2005). This criticism has led to the development of payment in advance and performance payment approaches (Nyhus *et al.*, 2005; Schwerdtner & Gruber, 2007). The key difference between these approaches and ex-post compensation is that the affected receives compensation in advance (prior to predation damage on livestock or agricultural loss) with a grant or subsidized loan (Schwerdtner & Gruber, 2007). Therefore, this approach creates incentives for locals to seek technical support and acquire materials (e.g., electric fencing) to improve husbandry practices and to maintain carnivores in the landscape (Maheshwari *et al.*, 2014; Zabel & Engel, 2010). Positively valuing a species or habitat is a prerequisite for investing in conservation action. Hence, a species or habitat is more secure, if it is valued by as many people in the community as possible for a diversity of different reasons/values, both intrinsic and utility (Webb, 2015).

6.4.2.3 Sustainability finance mechanisms

The last two to three decades have seen an increase in development and application of market-based policy instruments that aim to create new transactions for environmental goods and services, in efforts to merge conservation with profitability (Bresnihan, 2016). Policy approaches that consider managing nature as a question

of managing natural capital are controversial and diverse spanning approaches that aim to make nature's economic value legible to stakeholders to approaches that try to establish novel economic transactions (Bresnihan, 2016; Dasgupta, 2021). Approaches are designed to complement traditional command and control instruments and make sustainable use more attractive to users (Engel *et al.*, 2008; Wunder, 2007). Efforts to make nature's economic value visible include payments for ecosystem services, offsets, and emissions trading, which are most commonly applied to gathering and logging practices and natural capital accounting. Whereas, novel transactions including new financing mechanisms such as blended finance, insurance, and blue/green bonds are increasingly applied to fishing (Christiansen, 2021a; Christiansen & Schutter, 2019).

Payments for ecosystem services are a specific class of approach, used to facilitate voluntary transaction between a provider and a user of a service, conditioned on natural resource management rules for dealing with environmental externalities (Wunder, 2015). Payments for ecosystem services are created to deal with market failures, environmental externalities, property rights problems and asymmetric information between economic actors. Market failure arises due to high transaction costs, uncertainty, and short-term solutions. Two of the most well-known examples of payments for ecosystem services systems are Costa Rica's Pago por Servicios Ambientales and the United Nations-REDD Programme, which both aim to support sustainable use of wild forest species by decreasing logging practices and also impact on gathering practices (Bresnihan, 2016). Payments for ecosystem services differ from other conservation incentives because the payment is direct to the provider but conditional on sustainable use outcomes internalizing the cost (Ezzine-de-Blas *et al.*, 2016).

Even though payments for ecosystem services were originally designed as a market instrument, there exist a variety of institutional arrangements, where private and public sectors cooperate (Ezzine-de-Blas *et al.*, 2016). In some countries, programs are financed and managed by public institutions, as it is the case of the payments for ecosystem services national program in Costa Rica (Pagiola, 2008) and the payments for hydrological services program in Mexico (Giron-Nava *et al.*, 2019) which incentivize sustainable logging. In others cases they have been created as an exchange between private institutions such as the profafor carbon payments for ecosystem services in Ecuador (Wunder and Alban, 2008). However, hybrid or mixed schemes also exist where non-governmental organization, landowners, government and users are part of the institutional arrangement such as the matching funds in Mexico (Giron-Nava *et al.*, 2019). In general terms, it has been highlighted that public sector payments for ecosystem services are more common in Europe and Asia, and in Latin America a high diversity of schemes exists.

Payment in the form of access or entrance fees (see 6.4.2.1 on fees) for wildlife watching – a key non-extractive use practice – or for cultural ecosystem services (Church *et al.*, 2017; Cook *et al.*, 2020) is seldom considered as a payment for ecosystem service, highlighting both overlap between instruments and knowledge gaps in the role payments for ecosystem services can play in non-extractive uses (Bigger & Dempsey, 2018; Christiansen, 2021a, 2021b; Dempsey *et al.*, 2022; Frost & Bond, 2008; Ouma *et al.*, 2018).

6.4.3 Social and information-based instruments

It is generally accepted that the general public should be involved in decision-making processes that relate to the sustainable use of wild species. Consequently, social and information-based instruments have been developed to promote greater accountability and influence, through public attitudes and involvement. Social and information-based instruments are thus interventions that seek to influence practices through greater provisions of information (Krott, 2005). Approaches can be applied in isolation, but are more often either overlap with, or are applied in conjunction with legal and regulatory, economic and financial, rights based and customary approaches to steer attitudes, preferences, and demand and thus shape resource use. Common categories of instruments include certification schemes, (eco)labelling transparency & initiatives education and training and stakeholder engagement and consultations.

However, the development and implementation of social-based instruments needs to also pay careful attention not to bias public perceptions and support towards certain species at the expense of understanding key functions and roles in the broader ecosystem. Such a focus on flag species, common with especially large-sized mammals, can lead to unexpected and undesirable outcomes. Although it is very important to guarantee these species protection, they are not the only ones which need this protection.

6.4.3.1 Certification schemes and eco-labelling

Certification schemes and associated (eco)labelling are social and information-based as well as economic instruments since they are intended to operate, through the provision of information, to exert a market pressure to incentivize more sustainable use practices. They achieve this by developing a transparent process that signals to the market a product is sustainable (Pascual-Fernández *et al.*, 2019). For example, an ecolabel is an official symbol that verifies a product has been evaluated, against a set of environmental criteria by a third party. Certifications and labelling work on the basis that given the necessary information, consumer preference

will shift to demand more sustainable products; in turn, incentivizing and rewarding, more sustainable practices. However, evidence for certification driven shifts in consumer demand is limited. Several types of certifications and labels have been developed and applied that target different dimensions of social and ecological sustainability (e.g., environment, equity, and benefit sharing). When successfully designed and implemented, certification schemes can support more sustainable practices, more equitable distributions of benefits, the development of new skills, more stable markets, and sustainable sources of finance (Cetinkaya, 2009). However, ecolabels have been criticized for setting up parallel systems of policy for sustainable use, and diverting government funds away from, rather than supporting existing structures and processes. This is exacerbated, in lower income settings where the cost and infrastructure requirements mean certifications, may need Government or external support.

Certification and labelling schemes are well established and widely used in large scale commercial fishing, logging, and recreational non-extractive use practices. The Marine Stewardship Council is one of the oldest and well-known certification schemes that covers fishing and is increasingly recognized by industry as an indicator of success in achieving sustainable fishing. The Marine Stewardship Council was formed in the aftermath of the 1992 collapse of the cod stocks, initially in an alliance between the World Wildlife Fund and Unilever. By 2000 the first fishery, the Australian rock lobster, had been certified, and in 2006, the Marine Stewardship Council achieved consistency with the FAO of the United Nations's voluntary guidelines on ecolabelling. Currently, over 20,000 Marine Stewardship Council certified products are available, with entire supermarkets (e.g., Sainsbury's) and even countries (e.g., Netherlands) having pledged to sell only 100% Marine Stewardship Council certified fish products.

However, 80% of fisheries certified by the Marine Stewardship Council are large scale fisheries, despite these accounting for only ~50% of global catches (Le Manach *et al.*, 2012; World Bank, 2012). Furthermore, Marine Stewardship Council certifications have been criticized for certifying already sustainable fisheries rather than supporting unsustainable practices to transition to sustainable ones, and for predominantly (83%) certifying fisheries that employ active gears, despite their greater environmental footprint (Le Manach *et al.*, 2012). Consequently, the harvesters and buyers/processors from fisheries, such as the United States of America west coast albacore tuna, Brittany sardines, and Portuguese sardines' fisheries reportedly seek out certification primarily to expand or maintain their market share, rather than improve sustainability (Anderson *et al.*, 2021).

Within logging, certification and labelling emerged in the early 1990s in an effort to incentivize more sustainable

use. Certifications have since been widely adopted and well-respected, although the anticipated price premiums associated with certification have not materialized. The success of logging is due to consumers' (both primary, i.e., companies acquiring and processing timber and secondary ones at higher segments and at the end of a supply chain) sensitivities to environmental concerns (this is related, in its turn to the effectiveness of information and opinion forming), and legitimacy of certification bodies labelling in ensuring transparency and inclusiveness.

The two largest international forest certification schemes, the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) and the Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification seek to incentivize more sustainable logging practices, through greater information transparency, actor engagement, and corporate social responsibility, but have adopted different governance strategies. The Forest Stewardship Council, is a hierarchical organization with its roots in environmental movements, and similar to many certification schemes, engages a broad range of private sector actors, and open society organizations. The Forest Stewardship Council was first conceptualized after the 1992 Earth summit, after it failed to reach agreement to halt deforestation, with 1994 seeing the first Forest Stewardship Council certified product in the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland.

In contrast, to the Forest Stewardship Council, the Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification works primarily with national quality control and certification bodies, such as the Nordic Swan ecolabel and many national forestry certification schemes offering a relatively flexible compliance framework. Many governments (e.g., in Argentina and Indonesia) prefer the Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification model, but some have resorted to double certification to increase international market appeal. Both the Forest Stewardship Council and the Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification are well respected, but some argue that, where national forest and biodiversity governance frameworks are robust and well-functioning, certification does not bring any added value.

More recent certification schemes include the Union for Ethical Bioproducts (<https://www.ethicalbioproducts.org/about-uebt>) and FairWild (<https://www.fairwild.org/our-story>), born in 2007 and 2008 respectively. Both FairWild and Union for Ethical Bioproducts aim to promote biologically and socially sustainable trade through transparency and accountability, and cover the gathering and harvest of wild species and products.

Certifications and labelling are also widely adopted to support more sustainable non-extractive use practices, by providing the consumer with environmental, safety, or ethical information about the company characteristics, that supports more informed consumer choice. These

instruments guide individual choices towards specific types of markets that match their values. For example, the “Whale Sense” label was created in the Gulf of Maine, to indicate which whale watching tour companies have taken a training course, and have a certificate, to ensure their practices align with obligations set out by the International Whaling Commission (Avila-Foucat *et al.*, 2013; IWC, 2020). However, various nature-based tourism labels have been criticized for failing to adequately account for environmental impacts of for example carbon emissions from travel (Buckley & Shakeela, 2013; Gosling *et al.*, 2017; Margaryan & Stensland, 2017).

In addition to certification, many non-extractive use activities have developed codes of conduct to guide use that are implemented by the sector or the communities. One third of the regulations on non-extractive uses are mandatory with two-thirds entirely voluntary (Garrod & Fennell, 2004). Most codes specify a minimum approach distance (e.g., 50–100m or more), but other aspects such as prescriptions on no feeding or touching cetaceans are not necessarily included. Codes of conduct in birdwatching are also used as an instrument by birdwatchers’ societies or tour companies (Walther & White, 2018).

Certification requires traceability such Forest Stewardship Council in logging and Seafood Business for Ocean Stewardship (SeaBOS) in fishing. Sophisticated traceability system of certification schemes is a barrier for indigenous peoples and local communities to comply with. Although the certification ensures traceability, complexity hampers execution of certification process in the supply chains. For effective implementation of the certification which secures traceability, clarifying and informing the certification process and the required competencies is crucial for active participation by indigenous peoples and local communities.

6.4.3.2 Education, training, stakeholder engagement and consultation

Social and information-based instruments can also be useful to increase knowledge, skills, and awareness, to promote involvement, stimulate control, and generate public pressure which are all important drivers of change in the use of wild species.

Education and training can help move towards more sustainable use of wild species. Education generally has a strong and functional relationship with practice, holding considerable potential for influencing actions. However, education and training are seldom prioritized as policy options, more often appearing as a complementary activity. In many regions, ocean and forest management historically prioritized logging and commercial fisheries, orientated towards maximizing economic yields. This focus resulted in peoples, including indigenous peoples and local

communities, and practices, including gathering, being overlooked. Furthermore, because education and training is a knowledge-intensive field involving topics from many bordering disciplines, that involve considerable amounts of monitoring, technology and policy innovation, education has historically not been very inclusive. This is especially true in countries where education is structured within multiple institutions, and this can be regarded as a challenge. Thus, associated academic fields have historically failed to include the diversity of disciplines (though this is rapidly changing), knowledges (e.g., indigenous and local knowledge), and languages of relevance.

Stakeholder participation, engagement, and consultation are increasingly recognized as essential components of environmental decision-making and policy, often legally mandated in processes (Mease *et al.*, 2018). Ample guidance is now available and effective stakeholder engagement is considered mandatory to achieving social, environmental and economically sustainable standards, and is often a legal requirement. This perspective is also true for the management of wild species, since science alone has not been able to address or reduce unsustainable use of biodiversity. For example, community-based management that involves various degrees of joint decision-making between communities and either governmental or non-governmental organizations (e.g., co-management see section 6.4.4.5) has taken off in fishing, particularly small-scale fisheries which accounts for up to 90% of the world’s fishers, as discussed in section 6.5.1.1.

Indeed, governance arrangements work best when they involve consultation approaches, which seek to understand public attitudes towards the sustainable use of wild species, engage with local knowledge, and thus establish where there is political support for an activity. This approach can help inform the development of more effective policies. Management actions with little public support can be undermined and fail, especially when attitudes and beliefs of stakeholders and the wider public are contrary to the ones of wild species managers or wild species experts (Fulton *et al.*, 2014). Although consultation with stakeholders is an important way to gather information and to set priorities and objectives for policy, in most countries wild algae, fungi and plants harvesters and producers are drawn from the least powerful members of society and typically have little say in policymaking (Alexiades & Shanley, 2004; Hecht & Appelbaum, 1988; C. Shackleton & Shackleton, 2004; Shanley, 2002; R. Wynberg & Laird, 2007). Because such groups are rarely consulted during policy design, their needs seldom drive the policymaking process. Technical experts and even non-governmental organizations (which may not be representative of producers and harvesters, but can provide important assistance) often have more significant input into the design and drafting process than those directly involved in the harvest or trade of products. The

consultations that do take place for gathering law and policy are often with larger and more powerful business interests.

One reason for the limited involvement of harvesters in the policy process is the dearth of producer organizations or institutional vehicles through which their views and concerns can be expressed, and a lack of organizational capacity to do so. Although peasant worker, grass roots worker, and civil society organizations and coalitions (e.g., *via Campesina*, International Collective in Support of Fish Workers, and the Civil Society Mechanism within the United Nations) have formed over the past 3 decades in an effort to redress this balance and gain a political voice to the least represented, but often most affected by sustainable use policies and biodiversity loss. Even in recent decades, Brazil nut measures were drafted and passed in Bolivia without public consultation. It was only in the late 1990s that small Brazil nut producers finally forced their views into the public arena, in part by being better organized (Cronkleton & Pacheco, 2010). In the United States of America, Canada and the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, some effort has recently gone into including harvesters, buyers and processors in proposed regulatory reforms, either through the formation of industry-specific task forces or public hearings (Dyke & Emery, 2010; McLain & Lynch, 2010; D. A. Mitchell *et al.*, 2010).

6.4.4 Rights-based and customary instruments

Customary and rights-based approaches include formal and informal means of intervention that influence social and economic action through locally defined norms, customs, and tradition. Customary and rights-based approaches are often considered and conceived at local scales, however international agreements and guidelines (e.g., FAO small-scale fisheries Guidelines in Chapter 1, United Nations declaration of human rights), often developed through extensive consultation with rights holders, exist to guide new and support existing rights-based approaches. Rights-based and customary instruments at an international scale include treaties and guidelines, whereas at local and national scales they include customary laws, norms, and tenure, human rights-based approaches, and systems of traditional knowledge.

Customary and rights-based approaches, as policy instruments, are constantly developing and evolving in response to social, technological, environmental, and policy changes. However, many customary instruments predate more recent statutory policy options, which have often been introduced unaware that systems of governance were already present. Consequently, perhaps more evidently than the previous categories of instruments, rights-based and customary instruments co-exist with the other

categories in ways that can erode, complement or enhance the sustainable use of wild species. In many countries, customary and statutory laws play complementary roles (Box 6.2), but it occurs for new statutory laws to weaken effective customary systems.

Indigenous peoples' traditional ecological knowledge, traditional systems of control, use and management of lands and resources, and traditional institutions for self-governance are central components of customary and rights-based approaches and contribute substantially to sustainable use (Springer & Campese, 2011). Indigenous and place-based communities engaged in fishing, terrestrial animal harvesting, and gathering worldwide have self-organized to develop effective local-level institutions to conserve biocultural diversity. How communities maintain and adapt these institutions over time offers lessons for fostering more balanced human-environment relationships—an increasingly critical need as centralized governance systems struggle to manage declining biodiversity and ecosystem services (Montgomery & Vaughan, 2018).

An example of traditional ecological knowledge being applied in wild species management -through sustainable terrestrial animal harvesting- on common land, is presented by Rosales-Meda and Hermes-Calderón (2010), who worked with Maya-Q'eqchi' communities that live in the surroundings of Laguna Lachuá national park, in Guatemala. The authors compiled the traditional ecological knowledge of hunters and local inhabitants and gathered information regarding problems with the hunting activity and the solutions proposed by the members of the communities. They proposed and communally validated a calendar of animal breeding seasons that includes temporary bans for the most pressured species, complete bans for some threatened species, hunting grounds, sacred hunting sites, grace periods and wild species refuges (Figure 6.2). They formulated a community management system that allows local residents to make use of their hunting resource, to guarantee food security, according to their cultural practices and based on their own traditional ecological knowledge. Since the process of formulation and management of this proposal was carried out jointly with the people directly involved, it is more likely to succeed in its long-term implementation and sustainability (Rosales Meda & Hermes Calderón, 2010).

In conversations relating to biodiversity, gender is often discussed in terms of the roles, responsibilities and rights of men and women (Gutiérrez-Zamora, 2021; Lau, 2020; Nursey-Bray, 2009; Pfeiffer & Butz, 2005; Poor *et al.*, 2021; Villamor *et al.*, 2013). While this binary often has local relevance, it is important to acknowledge that cis gender identities (gender correlating to sex at birth) are not the only legitimate gender identities that need to be acknowledged through policy and practice (Tulloch, 2020).

Figure 6 2 The calendar of animal breeding seasons was elaborated in Q'eqchi' and Spanish with drawings and in colloquial language for easier understanding.

Copies were delivered to local family and to the authorities so that they could be placed in visible and busy places in their communities. Source: (Rosales Meda & Hermes Calderón, 2010) © 2010 Secretaría de Educación de Veracruz CC-BY NC.

Transgendered people, whether formally acknowledged or not, are members of communities who often face discrimination and are marginalized in decision-making systems (Collins *et al.*, 2015; Hill *et al.*, 2017). It is important to also consider impacts of intersectionality (e.g., gender identity, race, indigeneity, socio-economic status) on participation in biological diversity conservation systems and how particular groups are often disenfranchised (Khalikova

et al., 2021; Lau, 2020). However, gender norms play a key role in influencing what activities are available to whom, with implications for the sustainable use of wild species.

Perceptions of the use of wild species is often dominated by the practices of able bodied men. Yet, women play an important, though often overlooked, role in for example, gathering such as in the Indian Himalayan region (Dhyani,

2018; Dhyani *et al.*, 2011), the use of medicinal plants by urban communities in Tanzania, and fishing all around the world where women account for about 50% of the workforce (Chuenpagdee *et al.*, 2006). However, men and women often use wild species in different ways, for different purposes, and have evolved different systems of governance. For example, in the Australian Martu community, women hunt primarily small, predictable game (lizards) to provide small kin networks, feed children, and maintain their cooperative relationships with other women. In contrast, men hunt as a political strategy, using a form of “competitive magnanimity” to rise in the ritual hierarchy and demonstrate their capacity to keep sacred knowledge (Bliege Bird & Bird, 2008). Similarly, in Morogoro, most men herbalists use roots while women prefer barks (Augustino & Gillah, 2005). In the Loreto region of the northeastern Peruvian Amazon, it is taboo for any woman to hunt (Espinosa, 2010) but medicine women go deep into the forests to harvest medicinal plants. They have the spiritual knowledge and power to negotiate nature and its spirits in ways others cannot, thanks to their knowledge of rituals (Espinosa, 2010). Finally, although terrestrial animal harvesting and fishing are perceived to be dominated by men in indigenous communities in Canada, women play an essential role in food harvesting and gathering (IPBES, 2019a).

These gender differences mean although men and women may agree in principle on the need for conservation approaches, the strategies they will embrace will likely differ. In the Australian Martu community men trade off reliable consumption benefits to the hunter's family for more unpredictable benefits in social standing for the individual hunter (Bliege Bird & Bird, 2008). Systems of sustainable use thus often fall along gendered lines, for example in Thailand, the Karen people have a very strong a matriarchal social system (IPBES, 2019a), and in India, *Mahila mangal dals* (women self-help groups) regulate gathering of wild plants and enforcement of penalties (Dhyani *et al.*, 2011, 2013; Misra *et al.*, 2008). Formal and voluntary policies are beginning to recognize the importance of gender norms and look to rectify the historical oversight. For example, Kenya has committed to introduce laws that will allow girls to inherit land and to get their own title deeds. Whereas, the FAO's small-scale fisheries guidelines contain acknowledgement of the roles of women in the small-scale fisheries value chain, the need for gender equity and equality in access to human well-being resources, and the need for equal gender participation in fisheries governance (Kleiber *et al.*, 2017).

6.4.4.1 Tenure, access, and property rights

Communal ownership of land and wild species is widespread among indigenous peoples and local communities who have traditional ecological knowledge, associated with fishing, hunting, and gathering practices, and for whom wild species are imbedded in their cultural identity and social norms

(Delisle *et al.*, 2018; Guerrero-Ortiz, 2013; Tauli-Corpuz *et al.*, 2020). However, in many parts of the world, governments (often colonial governments) claimed as state land, areas that were traditionally owned and governed by indigenous peoples and local communities, undermining customary systems of tenure, overlaying new rules onto traditional practices (Domínguez & Luoma, 2020). Consequently, where people have maintained continuous attachments to their lands, there are likely to be situations of “legal pluralism” – i.e., overlapping systems of statutory tenure (codified in state law) and customary tenure (derived from ancestral ties and regulated through traditional institutions) (Vanderlinden & Gillissen, 1972).

More recently, there has been growing recognition that weak tenure is a prominent political driver of unsustainable use (see Chapter 4), exacerbating the gap between statutory and customary rights to lands and resources (Tseng *et al.*, 2021). Through increasing recognition that tenure derives from statutory and customary laws and institutions, many national constitutions now recognize some customary rights, though often in limited ways. Elsewhere, statutory devolution of natural resource ownership and management rights and responsibilities, especially of forests and waterbodies, is underway (Magessa *et al.*, 2020).

In some cases, land tenure may be secure, but resource rights are not. In Mexico, most forests are collectively owned, and while local communities have some autonomy in the management of their natural resources, and how they organize their gathering practices, the state sporadically exert control over their use. For example, agave extraction has been regulated for hundreds of years through local institutions within the ejido and indigenous community structure. They have been responsible for regulating access, management practices and the distribution of benefits based on history and traditional knowledge of the species. Norms and agreements are established by general assembly and are continually modified or replaced in a dynamic process that responds to new situations and to tensions of environmental, socioeconomic, cultural or technological origin. Even with such a dynamic and sophisticated system, however, local harvesters are required to present a legal harvesting permit (Granich *et al.*, 2010).

Resource rights are undergoing change alongside broader views of property rights in many countries. For example, in Sweden and Finland, the centuries-old principle of ‘everyman's right’ to harvest wild berries and mushrooms through gathering is being tested by the seasonal immigration of large numbers of non-nordic pickers, raising public concerns about immigration and tax policies, labor practices and benefit sharing (Richards & Saastamoinen, 2010). Similarly, in England, Scotland, and elsewhere tension exists for non-extractive use practices, between customary rights to roam, the codified versions of those rights (Dyke

& Emery, 2010), and potential rising environmental impacts (Beery, 2018; Sandell & Fredman, 2010). In Canada, in a reversal of trends in many other countries, as part of asserting aboriginal fishing and gathering rights and title, First Nations are demanding the return of their right to regulate access to wild algae, plants and fungi (D. A. Mitchell *et al.*, 2010).

6.4.4.2 Customary laws: rules norms, and rights

Local communities and traditional societies have a wealth of approaches to support the sustainable use of wild species that apply to gathering, small scale fishing, terrestrial animal harvesting, logging, as well as some forms of non-extractive uses. Customary laws, which include communal property rights, customary use rights, as well as many unwritten rules, and norms, have often developed for social or cultural purposes, such as feasting (Foale *et al.*, 2010; Foale & Manele, 2004), or to support processes considered locally as fair, but also serve to ensure over-use is prevented and enough will be left for future generations. Furthermore, article 10(c) of the Convention on Biological Diversity states

that “Parties shall: [...] protect and encourage customary use of biological resources in accordance with traditional cultural practices that are compatible with conservation or sustainable use requirements” (CBD, 2010a). Highlighting nations’ obligations to recognize customary laws and ensure legitimate representation of indigenous peoples and local communities in the development of policy.

Many of the customary use rights, communal management systems, and customs indigenous peoples and local communities have provided incentives for efficient use and management of natural resources, but many remain undocumented. These range from water rights in India which influence logging, customary marine tenure in Melanesia that regulates fishing (Cinner, 2007), communal forests and land rights in Papua New Guinea that shape gathering, and hunting practices, to customary fishing rights in Brazil, Sri Lanka, and Côte d’Ivoire (Cinner, 2007; Foale *et al.*, 2010; Zwarteveen & Meinzen-Dick, 2001). These systems, far from being outdated, contain valuable lessons and essential elements for the design of effective systems of managing natural resources. While many customary systems did not withstand historical processes and others

Box 6 2 National and regional recognition of customary law.

Customary law is widely recognized at both the national and international level as having a role to play in the regulation of the rights and interests of indigenous peoples and local communities over their natural resources and traditional knowledge. A number of regions, including in Latin America, Australia, and North America, have historically adopted policies, which promote the integration and assimilation of indigenous peoples, but eliminate their legal systems, languages and cultures. While, these systems dominate in urban centers, traditional systems of law, land rights and cultural relations continue unchanged in the rural areas occupied by indigenous peoples, and where the majority of indigenous peoples continue to maintain their own systems of community life. Attitudes towards indigenous peoples shifted in the 1990’s when all Latin American countries, then part of the Andean Community, adopted new constitutions. These reflected a shift from a policy of assimilation towards one of recognition of the pluri-cultural and multi-ethnic nature of the state. Some constitutions such as that of Peru and Colombia go further recognizing special rights of indigenous peoples to apply their own laws to regulation of their internal affairs (Oviedo & Noejovich, 2007), and recognized indigenous knowledge on living with nature (e.g., Buen Vivir) (Gudynas, 2011).

The Andean Community of Nations has, since the entry into force of the Convention on Biological Diversity in 1993, been one of the leaders in the development and implementation of law and policy on access and benefit sharing (Nagoya Protocol) and traditional knowledge issues (Tobin, 2008). The Andean Community of Nations is a regional economic group whose

decisions are legally binding on member states. In 1996 it established a regional regime on access and benefit sharing, which recognized the rights of indigenous, Afro-American and local communities to control access to their traditional knowledge. Decision 391 requires that, as a pre-condition for approval of bioprospecting agreements, a side agreement be signed with communities for the collection of resources on their land or for use of their traditional knowledge. Countries of the region have championed the debate on disclosure of origin at the World Trade Organization and have been amongst the promoters of the concept of certificates of origin in the international Access and Benefit-Sharing negotiations at the Convention on Biological Diversity (Tobin, 2008). Andean legislation requires prior informed consent of indigenous, Afro-American and local communities for access to and use of traditional knowledge creating an opportunity for communities to apply their customary law to regulate procedures on prior, informed consent. Customary law may also be used to guide decisions on issues of benefit sharing, confidentiality of information, and resolution of conflicts (Tobin, 2008).

Bolivia’s 35 indigenous peoples number approximately 8 million people, or 70% of the national population (De La Cruz Modino, 2007). The Constitution of 1994 recognized Bolivia to be multiethnic and pluricultural. It commits to recognizing, respecting and protecting the social, economic and cultural rights of indigenous peoples, in particular with regard to their traditional lands, the sustainable use of natural resources, their identity, values, languages, customs and institutions (150 Article 171).

are undergoing intense pressure including from population growth, new markets, and modern technologies (indigenous and local knowledge dialogues), they nevertheless act as prototypes of management systems that are attuned with the local cultures and provide insights into the design of modern systems of natural resource management.

Customary law is often unwritten, but flexible, relational, and negotiable in character. Customary norms are seldom used to determine directly who wins and who loses, but are rather used as a starting point for discussions towards mediated outcomes (Lau *et al.*, 2020; Ubink, 2018). Thus, customary norms are inherently participatory, formulated, renegotiated and flexibly applied in administrative structures and dispute settlement institutions. This involves paying attention to issues of representation and participation of marginalized community members in policy and decision-making processes (N. Fraser, 2010), and their ability to make use of these systems to uphold their rights and obtain outcomes that are fair and equitable (Ubink, 2018). The unwritten, negotiable and relational nature of customary law and the variety in normative beliefs and practices within customary communities is characteristic of customary norms, often making them place specific and can result in them being overlooked despite increasing recognized in international conventions, guidelines, national state legislation (e.g., United Nations declaration on the rights of indigenous peoples).

Intact customary law has a significant role in ensuring sustainable and equitable practices. For example, in Fiji, 83 per cent of the total land area, and the sea bed, available for gathering and fishing is under customary tenure ('native lands'). But, even with secure land tenure and resource rights, dramatic social, cultural, technological, economic, and other changes have strained customary and local laws. Similarly, landownership in the Philippines is vested in communities, each with its own rattan territory, and many with strong customary laws that promote sustainable rattan gathering practices (Arquiza *et al.*, 2010).

6.4.4.3 Indigenous peoples and local communities and taboos

Social taboos exist in most cultures, both Western and non-Western. They are good examples of informal institutions, where norms, rather than governmental juridical laws and rules, determine human behavior (Colding & Folke, 2001; C. Negi, 2010). In many traditional societies throughout the world, taboos frequently guide human conduct toward the natural environment (Colding & Folke, 2001). Local habitat taboos provide effective protection of smaller ecosystems in, for example, different parts of Africa (Byers *et al.*, 2001; Golden & Comaroff, 2015; Lebbie & Guries, 1995), India (Sinha *et al.*, 2003), Polynesia (Foale *et al.*, 2010), and China (Hongmao *et al.*, 2002). Colding and Folke (2001)

suggest that social taboos can constitute systems of local resource governance that can lower transaction costs for monitoring and enforcement compared with formal governance systems. Areas protected through informal institutions, such as taboos, have seldom been incorporated into biological conservation schemes, partly because of the narrow definitions of what constitutes conservation (Folke *et al.*, 2002). There is a growing need to identify and analyze resource practices and social mechanisms of traditional societies, such as taboos, and to investigate their possible ecological significance not only of species, but also of ecosystem processes and functions, such information is being lost rapidly (Colding & Folke, 1997).

Some taboos associated with *Hariyali Devi* and *Tungnath* sacred groves in Himalayas, India are to be followed by all (Singh *et al.*, 2017). These include the following:

- Fetching/gathering of fodder and fuelwood and the movement of women (as women are main harvesters of fuelwood, fodder, and other wild species) and *Shudras* (scheduled castes) have been strictly prohibited in this grove since the Mahabharata period (9th and 8th centuries BCE).
- Use of tools in any form (knife, sickle, etc.) on the wild plants and animals will be a step to hurt the sentiments of *Devi* (goddess). The forest fairies in turn are angered and their wrath can make person mad or deformed and also can lead to disaster in the family of offender.
- Killing/hunting of wild animals and plucking/uprooting of wild plants are strictly forbidden in the sacred groves.

"In communities along the Loretoyacu river in the Ticoya reserve or resguardo, a territory shared by Ticuna, Cocama and Yagua indigenous peoples, hunters have stories of encounters with forest spirits that help them find game or keep them from hunting in a certain place. Those encounters, combined with practices related to preparing the meat for meals, are traditional ways of controlling hunting in the territory" (B. Fraser, 2016).

Hunters offer various accounts of places where hunting is permitted, but hunters can only take what they need, or as places that keep hunters at bay, with thunder, lightning and rain if a hunter gets too close. When certain plants are flowering or bearing fruit, the meat of animals that feed on them has an unpleasant flavor and can cause nausea, diarrhea or rashes, so hunters avoid hunting those animals in places where they see those plants. More than two-thirds of the beliefs that limited the hunting or use of wild game were related to consumption. Eating the meat of a tapir, for example, could cause a pregnant woman to miscarry. Women also should not look at or touch the turtle known as a *matamata* (B. Fraser, 2016).

The largest number of “taboos” about meat consumption in Colombia involved the jaguar, a top predator that also has spiritual significance to many Amazonian people. Other animals regulated by traditional beliefs included tapirs and snakes. The largest number of beliefs related to the way meat is handled involved turtles for example, touching the blood of a turtle while preparing the meat is said to produce warts. Failure to respect taboos is considered to cause illness, and could result in a decrease in the number of animals or make hunters unlucky in their search for wild game. Fishermen respect similar practices. One lake in the reserve is known to fishermen as a dangerous place, home to huge river otters, jaguars and giant caimans (B. Fraser, 2016).

The radiated tortoise, *Geochelone radiata*, is endemic to the semi-arid region of southern Madagascar. Despite formal protection by law since 1960 and listing in the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora since 1975, tortoise populations have been reported to be in rapid decline, mainly due to illegal harvesting for food and commercial trade. The Tandroy people, inhabitants of the Androy region, which covers approximately half the tortoise distribution range, do not, however, exploit the species. The Tandroy prohibition against tortoise consumption is expressed as a taboo or fady (Lingard *et al.*, 2003).

Sacred sites are protected by indigenous national laws or codes of conduct by indigenous peoples many times associated to beliefs, and have not been assessed in the literature. However, some authors argue that due to those beliefs sacred sites and consequently the species associated are conserved. In the Ikoma culture, killing a totemic species leads to a community penalty (Kideghesho, 2009). The literature highlights the potential of spiritual sites for conservation however, beliefs can also be detrimental for some species. In Thathe Vondo in Limpopo province, South Africa, the harvest of fuelwood and to extract any products (roots, bark or leaves) from the sacred forests for medicinal purposes (Sinthumule & Mashau, 2020) is a taboo. To get firewood from both the Chirozva and Daramombe hills was considered taboo by the Nharira community in Chikomba district, Zimbabwe. Tree species such as muzhanje/mushuku (*Uapaca kirklandia*), mushuma (*Diosphyros mespilliformis*) and mutohwe (*Azanza garckeana*) were not used as firewood on the pretext that they produce a lot of smoke that causes total blindness. Other forms of mishaps that are associated with the use of fuelwood from such trees included drought episodes, reduction in crop yields and losing field crops to baboons. Yet from a nutrition perspective, the three trees are a source of wild fruits to the community. Hence, the need to protect them from rampant destruction. Muzhanje/mushuku (*Uapaca kirklandia*) bears nutritious fruits during December and January when other wild fruits are in short supply. In drought periods

such wild fruits become an alternative source of food as the trees survive long periods of dry spells (Mavhura & Mushure, 2019).

The following illustrates sustainable use and management of indigenous plant resources by the mantheding community in Limpopo province, South Africa: “Dependency on indigenous plant species necessitated the development of cultural practices to preserve the species. The harvesting of useful indigenous plant species from communal lands is regulated through observance of strict harvesting methods by all community members who harvest the species to satisfy particular needs. The management methods include specific harvesting methods, seed propagation and control of the use of plant species by the local chief. Preservation of sources of vegetables is accomplished through harvesting the tender leaves. Species are left to grow to maturity and bear seeds and fruits, which help in the propagation of the species. Gathering fruits is regulated. The taboo restricting the stroking of fruits limits over-use of the fruit trees. Gathering plant material for construction is limited to straight-stem species. Crooked-stem species are sidelined” (Rankoana, 2016).

Contrasting with taboos, there are other traditional beliefs and practices, such as traditional medicine, which -if not carried out sustainably- can lead to overexploitation of the natural resources they are based on. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), as much as 80% of the world’s population could depend on traditional medicine (based on the therapeutic use of animals, fungi, plants and microorganisms), for primary health care (Alves & Rosa, 2005; World Health Organization *et al.*, 1993). Traditional medicine is protected internationally by many legally binding instruments such Convention 169 of the International Labour Organization (ILO), Article 8(j) of the Convention on Biological Diversity, and, most recently, the United Nations declaration on the rights of indigenous peoples, specifically article 31 which states that: “Indigenous peoples have the right to maintain, control, protect and develop their cultural heritage, traditional knowledge and traditional cultural expressions, as well as the manifestations of their sciences, technologies and cultures, including human and genetic resources, seeds, medicines, knowledge of the properties of fauna and flora, oral traditions, literatures, designs, sports and traditional games and visual and performing arts”.

Some traditional medical practices have been gaining popularity, expanding to new locations and users, highly increasing product demand (Lee *et al.*, 2014). Some widely known examples of animal parts used in medicine include tiger bones, rhino horns, antlers of various deer species, bear bile, salamanders, parts of reptiles such as geckos and turtles, among others (Byard, 2016; Feng *et al.*, 2009; Still, 2003).

An introduction of certification systems for traditional medicine products (e.g., Fairwild, although it is exclusively for wild plants (Antosch & Morgan, 2017), therapeutic alternatives (e.g., chemical remedies, synthetic substitutes) and demand reduction strategies when demand is greater than supply, can be part of the solution (Still, 2003). Also, increasing public awareness through education campaigns and advocating sustainable wild species consumption could have a higher impact (Lee *et al.*, 2014).

6.4.4.4 Human rights-based approaches

Human rights, are evidently, and frequently recognized in international documents and commitments as relevant to the conservation and sustainable use of natural resources. Indeed, millions of people around the world are dependent on natural resources for their food and wellbeing (UNDHR Art 25). In 2004, the Third International Union for Conservation of Nature World Conservation Congress adopted resolution 3.015 of the International Union for Conservation of Nature: “Conserving nature and reducing poverty by linking human rights and the environment”. This resolution affirmed that [...] social equity cannot be achieved without the promotion, protection and guarantee of all human rights...” (Greiber *et al.*, 2010) (Box 6.3). More recently, on the back of decades of campaigning most notably by indigenous groups and environmental defenders, a land mark resolution was passed (UNDHR Res 48/13) by the United Nations Human Rights Council, recognizing a healthy and sustainable environment to be a human right (UN News, 2021).

The centrality of indigenous peoples and local communities’ rights and customary law and international recognition of the rights of indigenous peoples to regulate their

affairs in accordance with their customs, customary laws and institutions has been clearly set out in national and international legal instruments. Since the adoption in 1966 of the United Nations international covenants on civil and political rights and on economic social and cultural rights, recognition of indigenous peoples’ rights to self-determination has progressed steadily in the global policy arena. Other instruments that advance recognition of the rights of indigenous peoples and the role of customary law as both a source of law and as self-standing legal systems governing the affairs of large sectors of the global populace include the Convention on the Prevention of all Forms of Racial Discrimination; the Convention on the Rights of the Child; European, African, and American regional human rights instruments; and the United Nations declaration on the rights of indigenous peoples (Tobin, 2008).

United Nations declaration on the rights of indigenous peoples Articles 18 and 41 affirm, respectively, that indigenous people “have the right to participate in decision making in matters which would affect their rights” and that “ways and means of ensuring participation of indigenous peoples on issues affecting them shall be established” (CITES, 2016). Whereas Article 19 of the United Nations declaration on the rights of indigenous peoples, and Article 10(c) of the Convention on Biological Diversity link biodiversity, customary sustainable use, and traditional knowledge stating “Each Contracting Party shall, as far as possible and as appropriate: (c) Protect and encourage customary use of biological resources in accordance with traditional cultural practices that are compatible with conservation or sustainable use requirements” highlighting the obligation to work with indigenous peoples, through their representative institutions, to uphold customary use of wild species, and cultural value”. The International Labour

Box 6.3 The International Union for Conservation of Nature environmental law centre principles for assuring human rights in conservation.

Source: (Greiber *et al.*, 2010). © 2009 International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources

- Promote the obligation of all state and non-state actors planning or engaged in policies, projects, programs or activities with implications for nature conservation, to secure for all potentially affected persons and peoples, the substantive and procedural rights that are guaranteed by national and international law.
- Ensure prior evaluation of the scope of conservation policies, projects, programs or activities, so that all links between human rights and the environment are identified, and all potentially affected persons are informed and consulted.
- Ensure that planning and implementation of conservation policies and actions reflect such prior evaluation, are based on reasoned decisions and therefore do not harm the vulnerable, but support as much as possible the fulfilment of their rights in the context of nature and natural resource use.
- Incorporate guidelines and tools in project and program planning to ensure monitoring and evaluation of all interventions and their implications for human rights of the people involved or potentially affected which will support better accountability and start a feedback loop.
- Support improvement of governance frameworks on matters regarding the legal and policy frameworks, institutions and procedures that can secure the rights of local people in the context of conservation and sustainable resource use.

Organization, Convention 169, and the United Nations declaration on the rights of indigenous peoples recognize the collective rights of indigenous peoples to their traditional lands and resources, and the requirement to give due regard to customary law.

Recognition of the specific situation of indigenous peoples as maintaining customary institutions and ties to their traditional lands, often in combination with conditions of vulnerability, have resulted in provisions on indigenous peoples in core human rights treaties, as well as international rights instruments specifically addressed to indigenous peoples (particularly International Labour Organization 169 and United Nations declaration on the rights of indigenous people). “Rights of indigenous peoples include collective or group rights, which are linked to their individual rights, as collective rights (such as to territory) often need to be realized in order to fulfil individual rights (such as to food and health)” (Springer & Campese, 2011).

The term “rights-based approach” has been used in various contexts and has been defined in different ways. For example, in fishing, Allison *et al.* (2012) advocate for a move away from governance based on economic incentives to embedding governance challenges in a broader perspective of human-rights. A rights-based approach recognizes that activities and projects related to sustainable use of wild species can have a positive or negative impact on human rights, while the exercise of certain human rights can reinforce and act in synergy with the goals for sustainable use of wild species (Greiber *et al.*, 2010). The concept of developing and applying a human rights-based approach to the sustainable use of wild species could be perceived as such an instrument (Greiber *et al.*, 2010).

While linking environment and human rights issues is not a revolutionary suggestion, the rights-based approach is a relatively new and evolving way of thinking about how to adjust legal and policy instruments in order to acknowledge and strengthen this interrelationship so that sustainable use can be achieved. The harmonization of the two dimensions – sustainable use of wild species and people’s rights – and their integration through a rights-based approach in all relevant policies, legislation, and project activities could even be perceived as concretizing or “simplifying” the concept of sustainable use (see Chapter 1 and Chapter 2).

Implementation of such a rights-based approach to conservation remains slow to date, with the possible exception of voluntary guidelines for securing sustainable small-scale fisheries, endorsed by the FAO committee on fisheries in June 2014. As the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment indicated, continuous environmental degradation still adversely affects individual and community rights, such as the rights to life, health, water, food, and non-discrimination (Millenium Ecosystem

Assessment, 2005). Countermeasures that aim at halting such degradation are often criticized for their negative impacts on people’s livelihoods. Furthermore, the vulnerable communities of the world are both the ones that are suffering the greatest burden of environmental degradation and those least able to mobilize against rights abuses (Millenium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). The Tamshiyacu Tahuayo communal reserve offers an example of community-based conservation in the spirit of a rights-based approach. An area of 322,500 hectares located in the northeast Peruvian Amazon, this reserve was created through a coalition of local communities, researchers, non-governmental organizations and government agencies, which aimed to diminish terrestrial animal harvesting, fishing and logging by outsiders (see Section 6.5 for more).

Sustainable use activities can also generate negative impacts where their links to issues of human rights and well-being are not sufficiently understood or addressed, and weak fulfilment of rights can also undermine conservation outcomes (Kittinger *et al.*, 2017; Springer & Campese, 2011). Integration of human rights introduces new elements into conservation practice, particularly efforts to ground them in defined standards based on international human rights frameworks, as well as relationships of accountability between “rights-holders” and “duty bearers”. The 1972 Stockholm declaration on the human environment was an early trigger for discussions on adopting a human rights approach to environmental protection.

6.4.4.5 Community-based or co-management

The growing recognition of the importance of participation and legitimate involvement of indigenous peoples and local communities has resulted in the growth of support for community based or co-management approaches for the sustainable use of wild species. Co-management systems are a way of use and management of natural resources. They are often formulated in terms of some arrangement of power sharing between the State and a community of resource users (Carlsson & Berkes, 2005). Definitions of co-management can vary across a gradient from centralized management to self-managed (Figure 6.3). Similar to co-management, though closer to categories of self-management, community-based management is a way of natural resource management that involves the community in its management.

Support for such approaches, as highlighted above, can be seen in the United Nations declaration on the rights of indigenous people (2007) Article 8, 18, 19 and 26 that support rights of indigenous peoples on their lands and rights of participation in decision making (United Nations, 2007) as well as, the Convention on Biological Diversity plan of action on customary use of biodiversity (2010) that

ensures just implementation of Article 10(c) at local, national, regional and international levels and to ensure the full and effective participation of indigenous and local communities at all stages and levels of implementation (CBD, 2010). Motivated by concerns about the recent upsurge in the illegal trade in wild species, against a background of widespread unsustainable use of wild species (covering fauna and flora, and including timber and fisheries) (Cooney *et al.*, 2018). Resolution 2/14 passed at the second meeting of the United Nations Environment Assembly in May 2016 (Hub, 2016), called for "...an analysis of international best practices with regard to involving local communities in wild species management as an approach to addressing the unsustainable use of and illegal trade in wild species and wild species products [...]". Whereas, the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora explicitly recognizes the benefits of community based natural resource management for the sustainable use of wild species: "Community-based natural resource management promotes sustainable use of wild species, and reduces illegal use and trade in wild species. It fosters the support of local people for conservation, by generating income and stimulating local economies. The Preamble of the Convention recognizes that peoples and States are and should be the best protectors of their own wild fauna and flora, which is being achieved through community-based natural resource management" (CITES, 2016).

Community-based natural resource management programs have been employed for the sustainable use of wild species and reduction of poverty, for example through the legal trade in wild species and devolved wild species proprietorship as

a crucial solution to fight poaching and consequent illegal wild species trade and achieve the goals and targets of the 2030 agenda for sustainable development (CITES, 2016). The long history of experience in community wild species management remains crucially relevant for current efforts to combat the illegal trade in wild species crisis, but has been largely overlooked in the race for solutions emphasizing a top-down and increasingly militarized approach (Cooney *et al.*, 2018). "Community-based approaches are frequently written off as ineffective, even before the necessary effort has been made to put in place the conditions that will make them effective" (Cooney *et al.*, 2018).

Community-based tourism is a form of community-based natural resource management, applied to non-extractive use practices, and a popular enterprise-based strategy for biodiversity conservation, and a common element in integrated conservation and development projects. Community-based tourism illustrates the compromises involved in trying to meet multiple objectives. For biodiversity conservation, nature-based tourism is a fairly good land use, but not as good as (effective) pure protection. It can generate some income and contribute to community development, but only within limits and with considerable investment of support and time. It can also reduce the need for long term external financing for conservation under some circumstances, but will rarely eliminate it entirely (Kiss, 2004). The sustainability of community-based tourism is expected to come from three sources: (i) an ongoing conservation incentive in the form of income dependent on biodiversity; (ii) reinvestment of some of the income to maintain the business and protect the biodiversity asset base, thereby

eliminating or at least reducing the need for external funding; and (iii) once a basis has been established (community awareness and organization, basic infrastructure, etc.), the entry of the private sector to provide the capital for further development and expansion (Kiss, 2004).

The involvement, participation and empowerment of traditional populations and local communities has grown similarly in the governance of fishing. Here, a wide variety of collaborative arrangements between governments and users exist, in a spectrum ranging from instructive to informative (Sen & Raakjaer Nielsen, 1996) (Figure 6.3) (see section 6.5 for more details on effectiveness). However, the rapid growth of these approaches has meant many co-management arrangements are still more inclined towards government based, than to fully empowered and self-managed. Furthermore, the focus of these arrangements has generally been on small scale fisheries; highlighting the context dependent nature of how governance and management emerges.

Within fishing, the differences in governance and management approaches exist in part because of the lack of resources to monitor fishing and enforce regulations by the central government in these contexts (Begossi, 2008, 2014). For example, in intensively-managed industrial fishing, total allowable catches, established by applying some target exploitation rate or harvest control rule to an estimate of resource abundance, are a preferred instrument for controlling total harvest (Hilborn *et al.*, 2020; Melnychuk *et al.*, 2021). Such approaches require good-quality stock assessments which are usually done using data-rich and complex analytical methods. Regulatory instruments and

sources of information used in support of management tend to be very different in small-scale fisheries, where data and capacity are often limited, diversity of species and gears makes single-species norms impractical, and dispersed landing sites makes it difficult to collect data and enforce regulations (Table 6.5).

Local knowledge, participatory surveys and much simpler indicator-based systems are used to monitor resource status within small scale fisheries, and harvest controls tend to rely more on gear, effort and size regulations. Statutory norms used for granting access to fish resources and for allocating benefits are also in sharp contrast between industrial and small-scale fisheries. While quota shares and individual transferable quotas have been introduced in many industrial fisheries as a form of property right to increase economic efficiency and stop a race to fish (see section 6.5.2.1), statutory access rights in small-scale fisheries have more often taken the form of territorial use rights for fishing granted to local communities or fishing organizations (Christy, 2000; Orensanz *et al.*, 2013). A different form of statutory communal right that has been used in industrial fisheries has involved setting aside a portion of the total allowable catch to eligible communities usually to provide economic and social opportunities to disadvantaged groups and/or in recognition of customary or treaty rights of indigenous peoples. An example of such systems is the community development quota of Western Alaska (Carothers, 2011). In general, the inability to implement top-down command-and-control approaches in small-scale fisheries has led to variable degrees of devolution of power and responsibilities to local communities in community-based or co-management system.

Table 6.5 **Contrasting approaches used commonly for the assessment and management of industrial and small-scale fisheries.**

		Industrial fishery	Small-scale fishery
Resource monitoring & fishing regulations	Stock assessments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Centralized collection of data by fishery government agency Data-rich quantitative, complex models used to evaluate stock status 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participatory surveys Local knowledge Indicators of trends in resource abundance Size-based methods
	Harvest controls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total Allowable Catch (TAC) TACs calculated based on estimates of stock biomass and predetermined harvest control rules 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effort limits and gear restrictions, size limits, closed areas, closed seasons Simple empirical harvest rules that respond to indicators Customary norms
Management Institutions	Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong legal mandates to eliminate overfishing and rebuild stocks Command-and-control approaches 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Devolution of power to local communities Community-based Co-management
	Access regimes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individual Transferable Quotas (ITQs) Quota shares allocated by government agencies to individuals or companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Territorial Use Rights (TURFs) held by communal/fishers' organizations Recognition of traditional forms of tenure

The move towards co-management or community-based management has been motivated by both recognition of the importance of human rights as well as of the “inextricable link” between biological and cultural diversity, whereby they are interdependent and geographically overlapping (Griot & Nietschmann, 1992; Maffi, 2007). This means that most biodiversity-rich areas coincide with the presence of indigenous cultures and traditional communities. This constitutes a key principle for an integrative and transdisciplinary approach to wild species conservation and management (Guerrero-Ortiz, 2013; Maffi, 2005). This context has lent way to the creation of biocultural protocols as useful community-led instruments that promote participatory advocacy for the recognition of, and support for, ways of life that are based on the customary sustainable use of biodiversity (Jonas *et al.*, 2010). Biocultural protocols enable communities to build relationships and bridge the gap between the customary management of their biocultural heritage and external stakeholders (researchers, companies, other communities) (Bavikatte & Bennett, 2015). These protocols have the potential to shift the dynamic of conservation initiatives to becoming more inclusive, locally appropriate processes driven by legally empowered communities (Jonas *et al.*, 2010). For example, a biocultural community protocol was developed based on the internal regulatory systems of the Comcáac People (Sonora, Mexico) (PNUD *et al.*, 2018), as a community instrument for sustainable development, that shows the exercise of community rights and internal participatory processes. It presents strategies for the protection of traditional knowledge, natural, biological and genetic resources found within their territory (common property). With regard to hunting, the community has shifted from subsistence hunting to managing trophy hunting of big-horn sheep (*Ovis canadensis*) (see **Box 6.10**). The protocol provides information on hunting grounds, on traditional authorities

in charge of selling hunting permits, and on the community hunting committee, among others.

6.4.5 Prevalence of policy instruments

The prevalence of policy instruments covered in the systematic review of case studies is shown in **Table 6.6**. The bar indicates the proportion of the cases that cover each policy instrument. Across practices, and based on the selected cases, legal and regulatory instruments were the most commonly applied instruments overall. The exception is gathering, where although most instruments were applied in combination, social and information based were slightly more common. There was a paucity of instruments applied in the non-extractive use practice case studies, where policy instruments other than legal and regulatory instruments were seldom applied. Within non-extractive uses, regulations in the form of national parks were most common, allowing visitors to stay on the authorized trails during walking safaris in Tanzania (Brandt & Buckley, 2018; Mgonja *et al.*, 2015).

Most case studies (81%) reviewed reflect the application of a combination of policy instruments, and gathering practices were most likely to involve all four policy instruments. For example, case study examples from the gathering practice adopted ban on open grazing (Dhyani *et al.*, 2011), tax (Grivins, 2016), organic wild-crop harvesting standards (Brinckmann *et al.*, 2018), and traditional resource rights (Solis & Casas, 2019) (**Table 6.6**). Overall, 8% of case studies involve all four policy instrument categories, whereas 18% only involve one.

The **legal and regulatory** instruments reviewed most often included international conventions, laws and specific rules.

Table 6.6 Prevalence of policy instruments (N=84).

Each bar indicates the proportion of cases, within each practice, that included each policy instrument. A full bar indicates the policy instrument was present in all cases (see the data management report at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4663236>).

Practice	Type of policy instruments			
	Legal & regulatory	Economic & financial	Social & cultural	Right-based & customary
Fishing	██████████	██████████	██████████	██████████
Gathering	██████████	██████████	██████████	██████████
Terrestrial animal harvesting	██████████	██████████	██████████	██████████
Non-extractive practices	██████████	██████████	██████████	██████████
Logging	██████████	██████████	██████████	██████████

International conventions and treaties influence national laws for regulating the use of wild species. For example, the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora and the Convention on Migratory Species influence national laws on fauna and hunting in the case of Mongolia (Dixon & Batbayar, 2010), illustrating that international rules influence domestic policies with binding obligations on states (Bernstein & Cashore, 2012).

Permit and quota systems are common legal instruments in terrestrial animal harvesting, industrial fishing and gathering. With the exception of small-scale multi-species fishing, where quota management is practically impossible, quotas are the main practical basis for the regulation of wild species harvest and trade. Quotas may be established on a per-capita or per-permit basis, and a fee may be charged, or they may regulate the total extraction allowed over a given season. For example, in Mongolia, according to the law on hunting resource use and hunting and trapping, permit fees exist for scientific, cultural, artistic, and medicinal uses in terrestrial animal harvesting, for a Mongolian hunter, the permit fee is 20% to 40% of the animal's economic and ecological value (Article 5.1.2) and for foreigners, it is equal to the international market value, or 60% to 70% of the economic and ecological value (Article 5.1.5) (Janchivamda *et al.*, 2014). For foreigners, it is equal to the international market value, or 60% to 70% of the economic and ecological value. In gathering, Greek legislation allows the extraction of two kilos of fresh plant material per plant species and person per day (Papageorgiou *et al.*, 2020).

Around half (53%) of the selected cases include **economic instruments** across all practices. Fishing and gathering, were most likely to use **economic and financial** instruments than other practices. Terrestrial animal harvesting and gathering cases tended to implement a fee or penalty in the form of a negative economic instruments. In contrast, logging cases tended to implement market incentives as positive economic instruments through certification systems as social and information-based instruments.

Around 61% of the selected cases include **rights-based instruments** across all practices. In many of the case studies, the communities have some degree of rights over the area or resource, some operate with catch shares, others not. However, there is no one combination model that appears more effective than others. While catch shares and strong ownership are often assumed to be beneficial, a case study on Madagascar for instance clearly shows that common property institutions can successfully implement management without property rights over the resource.

6.5 EFFECTIVENESS OF POLICY INSTRUMENTS

A variety of policy options have been introduced to control, or support, the sustainable use of wild species (see preceding section 6.4). Evaluating the effectiveness of these policy options is an important stage in the policy cycle (Giorgi, 2017; E. Young & Quinn, 2002). Effectiveness refers to whether a policy works as intended and meets the purpose for which it was designed (Sadler, 1996). Policy effectiveness can be assessed in terms of objectives, outcomes and impacts (Broc *et al.*, 2018). This section synthesizes the evidence on policy effectiveness for the sustainable use of wild species, evaluates the causal effects of specific policy combinations or programs as well as the conditions under which this effect arises. This chapter focuses on disentangling the impacts and effects resulting from different interventions in diverse contexts. Establishing when and why particular policy approaches are most likely to succeed is key to enabling the sustainable use of wild species. Because effectiveness is context specific, variables through time, practice, place, and culture, are considered. The concept of “enabling conditions” is used, which centers on conditions that facilitate approaches to address social and ecological challenges. They can be defined as factors that increase the likelihood of an intended change in the governance approach, strategy, or management regime. The presence of enabling conditions can facilitate the emergence of a particular environmental policy. In contrast constraining conditions are, factors that create barriers to effective management and policy implementation. These may comprise the absence of key enabling conditions or arise independently (Huber-Stearns *et al.*, 2017). Assessing policy effectiveness contributes to the experts' understanding of what worked as planned and provides input to the redesign or improvement of policies at the stage of policy evaluation. It contributes to narrowing the knowledge gap and supporting evidence-based decision making (Artelle *et al.*, 2018).

Taking advantage of the multi-sector approach Chapter 6's authors adopt in this chapter the analyses of effectiveness is based on a combination of: the general review; the mixed methods systematic review (based on selected case studies, see data management report at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4663236>); and boxes selected to be illustrative of key points (see methodological approach section 6.2); that in combination draw on the best available evidence providing guidance to policymakers that can and should be updated over time.

Many studies made an explicit effort to identify and describe the enabling or constraining conditions for the effectiveness of policy instruments (one example being (McCay, 2014). However, in many cases, and as anecdotally described by

(Jentoft, 2004), sometimes it takes an outside perspective to understand the inside ongoing of a particular situation, or to identify key factors that seemed obvious before, because a culturally embedded institution seemed to be a given. For example, in countries where legal compliance is high, compliance is not usually highlighted as an enabling condition. Information access, technical infrastructure and capabilities may be other such factors that are not emphasized due to their prevalence. Therefore, in drawing information from across case studies on what conditions exist where policies are more effective, and conversely what conditions exist where policies are less effective, we are able identify patterns that enable or constrain policy effectiveness.

Most policies have the potential to be successful, however they also have the potential to fail and even exacerbate existing social and ecological conditions. The success of a given policy depends on the context and history in which it is applied. We identified a number of enabling and constraining conditions associated with the application of different policy instruments across practices. Enabling and constraining conditions were related to the values, norms, and principles (see section 6.5.1, 6.6.1, 6.6.2, 6.6.3), the rules and institutions (see section 6.5.2, 6.5.3), and the power asymmetries (See section 6.5.4) of the governing system and system to be governed (*sensu* the interactive governance framework **Figure 6.1**). These resulted in seven overarching constraining and seven associated enabling conditions (**Figure 6.4**). When rights are not recognized,

power relations are unbalanced, and policies ignore social dimensions whether of the local context social, or policy objectives the effectiveness of policies are constrained. However, in contrast governing systems that are inclusive and participatory, recognize and respect diverse forms of knowledge, and ensure benefits (and costs) are shared equally can result in more effective sustainable use policies. Similarly, when policy approaches overlook the historical context, focus on a limited number of commonly used instruments, rules inadvertently criminalize the most marginalized, and policies are not aligned across scale nor do they facilitate interactions the effectiveness of policies are constrained. In contrast, when governance institutions are robust, sustainable use policies are supported by broader policies, instruments are tailored to the local context, and rules and instruments are adaptive and processes democratic, sustainable use policies are more effective (**Figure 6.4**).

6.5.1 Governance characteristics that enable sustainable use

6.5.1.1 Inclusive & participatory process

Policy tends to be more effective when developed through inclusive and participatory processes that involve representative leaders, transparent institutions, and community-based approaches. Legitimate participatory processes that involve a more equal balance of power,

tend to support more effective policies because they draw on diverse perspectives and forms of knowledge, support collaboration, and increase buy-in. This in turn leads to better self-regulation, particularly for high value species.

The participatory model is built on the premise that local involvement is essential to achieve social justice and the long-term protection of the natural environment (Meola, 2013). Full and inclusive consultations encourage exchange and understanding, and provide awareness and opportunities for indigenous peoples and local communities to share local and scientific knowledge among relevant actors. Legitimate and effective engagement can also help build trust between actors, which is key for the long-term success of sustainable use initiatives. Multi-tiered systems of regulation that incorporate statutory and customary/local rules of use distribute responsibilities among the actors best able to meet them while participatory development of regulations motivates more effective enforcement at a local level. Evidence from the gathering case studies found that local communities are more flexible in adapting

their management approaches for gathering wild species including high value species irrespective of the legal setting of the area, highlighting potential for adaptive management. Participation is achieved when all actors are included, and differences that exist across genders, identities, and abilities are taken into consideration.

Indeed, within terrestrial animal harvesting case studies, effective policy implementation was directly related to multi-actor involvement from the beginning of the policy process (e.g., **Box 6.4**). The successful terrestrial animal harvesting case studies established institutions including government structure, which monitored the regulation and application of norms and rules for conservation and sustainable use. These coincided with a mode of co-governing, through which all actors involved participated in the decision-making process and other activities. There was a similar emphasis in the fisheries case studies, on exchange, dialogue, and conflict resolution. Co-management was found to be more effective where transparency, fairness, leadership, and conflict resolution mechanisms were present.

Box 6.4 Inclusion of actors across multiple scales enables sustainability: Morelet's crocodile (*Crocodylus moreletii*) skins in Mexico.

The Morelet's crocodile (*Crocodylus moreletii*) is distributed in Mexico, Belize and Guatemala. In Mexico it is found on the slope of the Gulf of Mexico and the Yucatan Peninsula (Platt *et al.*, 2010). Morelet's crocodile have historically been overharvested. In the 1970s, because of overhunting and unregulated skin trade, Morelet's crocodile populations were threatened with extinction. This led Mexico to prohibit the commercial harvest of wild individuals (SEMARNAP, 1999).

Consequently, Mexico launched a pilot project to support the conservation of these crocodiles based on scientific evidence, monitoring, and regulated trade. In 2017, the "Cocodrilos Chacchoben" project was sustainably and legally harvesting wild *C. moreletii* eggs, that were later sold to grow in optimal conditions to reach commercial sizes (Mosig, Antaño, *et al.*, 2019). A key factor for the success of the pilot project was the involvement of and collaboration with multiple actors at various scales of governance, from international to local communities.

The Morelet's crocodile monitoring program Mexico-Belize-Guatemala (Sánchez-Herrera *et al.*, 2011), was implemented in Mexico for five breeding seasons (2011–2015). Over this period of time, an increase of the average estimated number of wild Morelet's crocodile was observed: from 44,890 in 2011, to 104,815 in 2015; with a general average for the 5 years of about 74,000 individuals, with an encounter rate of 3.2 ± 1.4 (ind/km), along a total of 22,833 km of potential habitat. In over 70% of the Morelet's crocodile monitoring program sites, a general upward population trend was observed (Rivera-Téllez *et al.*, 2017). The information gathered through the national implementation of the Morelet's crocodile monitoring program on status and trends,

indicates that wild populations of Morelet's crocodile are in good condition and that there is a potential to develop sustainable productive projects for the benefit of indigenous people and local communities, of the species and its habitat.

In 2017, a pilot project was developed to establish an integrated production system of high-quality *C. moreletii* skins, based on the conservation of the species and its habitat, as well as on a sustainable, legal, and traceable scheme, with fair and equitable distribution of benefits throughout the productive chain, particularly for indigenous peoples and local communities (Mosig, Antaño, *et al.*, 2019). Activities carried out by the community members that are part of the pilot project, are guided by the ranching protocol for Morelet's crocodile (Barrios & Cremieux, 2018). The ranching scheme consists in harvesting eggs from the wild and taking them to incubators managed by the local communities, which rises the offspring survival rate from 1% in the wild, to up to 90% in captivity (Barrios & Cremieux, 2018). Through its implementation, standardized information on nests is obtained, which is the basis for defining sustainable egg harvest quotas and non-detriment findings on the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora framework. It also provides detailed guidelines for nest extraction, egg transportation and the incubation processes.

After over 40 years of a national prohibition to harvest crocodiles, in 2017, "Cocodrilos Chacchoben", was the first Management Unit for Wildlife Conservation (UMA) to sustainably and legally harvest wild *C. moreletii* eggs. The hatchlings were later sold to the farm "Cocodrilia" where they grow in optimal conditions until they reach commercial sizes for the production

of high-quality skins for the international leather market (Mosig, Antaño, *et al.*, 2019). A key factor for the success of the Pilot Project has been multistakeholder -multisectorial collaboration; involvement of federal and state governments of both environmental and agricultural sectors, Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora authorities, indigenous peoples and local communities, the private sector, the crocodile specialist group of the International Union for Conservation of Nature, national experts part of the group of crocodylians specialists in Mexico and civil society.

Through the implementation of the pilot project, the community of Chacchoben, has benefited from the sustainable ranching of Morelet's crocodile eggs. Knowledge about the species and population trends continues to be generated through the Morelet's crocodile monitoring pProgram. As a result, the crocodiles that used to be considered a threat, are now valued and they represent an additional income. This income incentivized the community to conserve 4,658 ha of habitat that is also home to about 560 other species of fauna and flora (Mosig, Antaño, *et al.*, 2019).

Photos: Morelet's crocodile (*Crocodylus moreletii*) © Iván Montes de oca Cacheux / CONABIO CC-BY and © Mariana del Carmen Gonzalez Ramón CC-BY.

Similarly, within gathering case studies reviewed, whenever legal and regulatory policies involved local communities along with local non-governmental organizations as facilitators in the process it resulted in an overall positive impact on ecological, economic and social development. Involvement of local communities in legal and regulatory policies along with intermediaries as facilitators emerged as an enabling condition to ensure sustainable gathering and overall positive impact on the socio-economic development of the community.

Empowering more women in local resource decision-making can lead to better resource governance and conservation outcomes. This is in part because women typically use natural resources differently than men, but are often left out of decision making on how local resources are managed, creating gaps in resource management decision making and policy. For example, there is strong and clear evidence from India and Nepal, of how including women in forest management groups results in better resource governance and conservation outcomes (Leisher *et al.*, 2016). In 2006, India had 106,482 registered as "joint forest management groups". Joint forest

management guidelines, issued in 2000, recommended that village forest committees should consist of 50% women members, with at least 33% women on the executive committee-the principal decision-making body. Similarly, Nepal had 17,685 forest user groups in 2011, with approximately 800 women-only groups; government guidelines for community forestry recommended that women comprise 50% of a forest user group's executive committee. In both countries, groups with a higher proportion of women in their executive committee showed significantly greater improvements in forest condition than groups with a lower proportion of women (Leisher *et al.*, 2016). These benefits were likely in part due to greater degrees of cooperation among women, and women using their knowledge of plant species and methods of product extraction (Agarwal, 2009; Leisher *et al.*, 2016). Similarly, women had a significantly positive effect on cooperation in forest management in Paraguay. Women have also demonstrated the ability to mitigate elite capture of benefits during the process of decentralization, which could be particularly relevant during initial stages of the logging project. Therefore, a deliberate attempt to integrate women into project planning (and beyond) would likely benefit

both the process and longer-term outcomes of extractive reserve logging (Cooper & Kainer, 2018).

In contrast, where women remain excluded from governance and decision-making processes, sustainable use can be hampered (Rohe *et al.*, 2018). For example, although women play an important role in small scale fishing communities in Solomons, such as contributing to food security, decisions on how the resource is managed are mostly taken by men. This has impacted social and ecological sustainability leaving women more inclined to break local management rules because: i) they were not involved in decision-making; ii) they had lost trust in the local male leadership, who they perceived had misused the money, and; iii) the management rules constrained the women's activities most as the marine closure was located where the women used to fish (Rohe *et al.*, 2018).

Similarly, some of the least successful gathering case studies did not specify the process followed to consult or include indigenous peoples and local communities or other actors in the development and/or implementation of projects, and as a result inclusive and transparent participation was not achieved. Full participation of all actors is crucial to guarantee that all points of view are taken into consideration and that the project is culturally appropriate and not imposed by an external actor.

Across practices, several successful cases studies involved co-governing or co-management through participation and collaboration by multiple actors. The interaction between different actors has been highlighted as a priority for transparency and participation to build governance. For example, in Costa Rica, three national institutions – the ministry of environment and energy, the institute of marine fisheries and the association for rural economic development – retain responsibilities for various aspects of the project (L. Campbell, 1998). The Ostional integrated development association (community institution), managed by an elected “*junta directive*” (board of directors), is responsible for the day-to-day activities.

In contrast, none of the five least successful terrestrial animal harvesting case studies applied community-based management which seems to be key for successful implementation of the policy instruments, although two of them considered traditional resource rights and traditional ecological knowledge. At the same time, the least successful terrestrial animal harvesting cases tended to exclude indigenous peoples and local communities in managing the resource and within the harvesting practices, either by the imposition of legislation that prohibited harvesting, or by an increase in resource management by the private sector.

The involvement, participation and empowerment of traditional populations and local communities is a particularly

relevant governance approach to promote sustainability of small-scale fisheries worldwide, through a wide variety of collaborative arrangements between governments and users, in a spectrum ranging from instructive to informative (Sen & Raakjaer Nielsen, 1996) (see **Figure 6.3**). Such bottom-up management approaches that include indigenous and local knowledge have been promising, especially in a context of lack of resources to monitor fisheries and enforce regulations by the central government (Begossi, 2008, 2014). A brief overview of management and co-management systems directed to small-scale fisheries worldwide is provided here. Due to the spectrum of local arrangements (see **Figure 6.3**), which are rarely identified, the success and specific results are highly context dependent and not easy to generalize. However, most co-management arrangements are still more inclined towards government based, than to fully empowered and self-managed approaches.

Most of the more sustainable inland fisheries in South America include the involvement of local fishers in co-management schemes aiming to maintain the harvest of valuable fishing resources, such as the pirarucu (*Arapaima gigas*) (**Box 6.5**) and freshwater turtles, in spatially defined boundaries, such as floodplain lakes in the Brazilian Amazon (Campos-Silva *et al.*, 2020; Campos-Silva & Peres, 2016; Castello *et al.*, 2009; Petersen *et al.*, 2016). Some of these co-management systems have shown additional ecological benefits on top of increases in targeted species in the Brazilian Amazonian rivers, including increases in fish, aquatic mammals, birds and even invertebrate species not targeted by the fishery (Campos-Silva *et al.*, 2017; Silvano *et al.*, 2009) and in overall fish diversity in both managed and nearby unmanaged lakes after a period of 15 years (Medeiros-Leal *et al.*, 2021).

These co-management systems consist of formal agreements among local fishers' organizations, fishing companies, local and State governments, and non-government organizations. These agreements recognize the rights of local fishers to exclusive access to fishing grounds, and tenure rights over those fishing resources. A local participatory management board establishes local rules of access and use, recorded in annual management plans. The boards can also apply graduated sanctions when these rules are not met. Local fishers protect, monitor and assess fish stocks, and annual fishing quotas are granted by authorities based on these assessments (Castello *et al.*, 2009; Petersen *et al.*, 2016). These Amazonian co-management systems originated from demands of local communities to reduce conflicts and restrict access of large-scale commercial fishers to harvest large lakes in the Brazilian Amazon, especially in the Middle Solimões and Lower Amazon River regions (Castello *et al.*, 2009; de Castro & McGrath, 2003).

Although widespread throughout the major rivers in the Brazilian Amazon, there are only a few studies on the

efficacy of these fishing accords (Almeida *et al.*, 2009). Moreover, the ability of these co-management systems to improve individual fish catches can be more related to informal local organization and capacity to enforce rules of each community, than to a formal recognition by the Brazilian government (Lopes *et al.*, 2019). Another co-management system in the Brazilian Amazonian rivers is that of the extractive reserves, which have

shown promising evidences of increased abundance of fished resources, when compared to non-managed sites (Hallwass *et al.*, 2019, 2020; Keppeler *et al.*, 2017; Silvano *et al.*, 2014), although some high valued fish species may have decreased in abundance. This decrease, and lack of temporal data, make it difficult to confirm the ecological sustainability in these extractive reserves (Hallwass *et al.*, 2020).

Box 6.5 Participatory co-management enables sustainable use: Pirarucu in the Amazon.

The Pirarucu fishery is an example of a successful participatory, and adaptive co-management initiative, where indigenous and local, and scientific knowledge are used together to guide management and monitoring. The initial alliance formed between fishers and government agencies, established a clearly articulated division of powers, benefits were equitably distributed across the community, and capacity building was a clear feature, together ensuring successful social and ecological benefits.

Pirarucu (*Arapaima gigas*) is among the largest freshwater fishes in the Amazon, reaching 3 meters in length and almost 200 kilograms (H. L. de Queiroz, 2000), playing an important part in the Amazonian economy and culture since the 16th century (de MENEZES, 1951; H. L. Queiroz & Sardinha, 1999; Verissimo, 1895; Viana *et al.*, 2007). As one of the main impacts of the introduction of modern technologies in the second half of the 20th Century, the increase of the fishing pressure and offtake led to the overfishing of pirarucu stocks in most parts of the Amazon (Isaac & Barthem, 1995; H. L. Queiroz & Sardinha, 1999). Official protective measures were first introduced in the 1980s by government agencies, but had little or no effect due to the lack of enforcement capacity of local authorities. Almost forty years after those attempts to protect the species, stocks are now recovered and increasing, due to a more effective protective measure, the community-based management of this fishery, introduced in the 1990s.

One of the main success cases of community-based initiatives of sustainable use of natural resources and biodiversity conservation in the Brazilian Amazon was first implemented by the small riverine communities of Mamirauá reserve, by the Japurá river, in the Amazonas state. The traditional ecological knowledge of the local populations was adopted in the management system, especially in the annual stock assessment technique in place (Arantes *et al.*, 2007; Castello, 2004; Lopes & Queiroz, 2009). To provide technical support to this fisheries management, scientific research was conducted on the biology of the species (Arantes *et al.*, 2010, 2013; Araripe *et al.*, 2013; Castello, 2008a, 2008b; Castello, Stewart, *et al.*, 2011; Coutinho *et al.*, 2010; Queiroz, 2000), on the main aspects of its fishery (Andrade *et al.*, 2011; H. L. Queiroz & Sardinha, 1999) and also, on the social and economic aspects of the fisheries (Amaral, 2008; Lima & Peralta, 2017; Peralta, 2010). The first proposal for a formal management system of pirarucu was approved in an alliance with local fishermen

of Mamirauá Reserve in 1998, and implemented since 1999 (Castello *et al.*, 2009; Figueiredo, 2013; Viana *et al.*, 2007). Members from the local communities agreed to negotiate, approve and adopt sustainability measures, adjust in fishing gear, establishing annual extraction quotas, monitoring and controlling the offtake, adopt a minimum size for the catch and the interruption of the activity during a banning period, at the reproductive period of the species. Management measures also included other participatory action, such as training courses and meetings to establish rules of access and use of fishing grounds.

Between 1999 and 2002 the experience at the Mamirauá Reserve was consolidated and underwent a first phase of expansion, replicated for a larger number of communities and their management associations (Viana *et al.*, 2007). This co-management was based on the division of powers and responsibilities among different institutions (Amaral, 2013; Peralta & Lima, 2012; Silva *et al.*, 2013). The governance system built was based on local management committees that are able to set and enforce rules, conduct and oversee the activity and equitably distribute the benefits generated, ensuring resilience and growth. Several stakeholders are involved in the participatory governance of the pirarucu fisheries. Fishermen provided their traditional knowledge and are responsible not only for protecting of the fishing grounds, the local lakes. Fishermen are also responsible for the organization and distribution of fishing groups in the managed lakes, they perform the annual assessment of the stocks, the capture of pirarucus, they are responsible for marketing and trade, and of the local monitoring of all activities (Viana *et al.*, 2007). After the fishing season, they are responsible for the equitable sharing of benefits. The technicians from the supporting institutions are responsible for building capacity among local fisher's associations (Castello *et al.*, 2009). They also provide guidance to the fishing groups and supervise their actions regarding the compliance to the guidelines established in the annual management plan. Technicians are also responsible for monitoring the sustainability of the management system based on a group of environmental, social and economic indicators. The representatives of the government are responsible for licensing, for the oversight and for the annual evaluation the management. Local institutions maintain research programs that also act as monitoring programs, providing the follow up, assessing the sustainability of pirarucu fisheries, and a continuous evaluation of the ecological, socioeconomic and

Box 6 5

socio-political impacts of the community-based management and the participatory governance system in place. The results of these on-going surveys and evaluations allow the enhancement of the technical guidelines supporting the activity, in a truly adaptive management approach (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2018).

After more than two decades, pirarucu fisheries management proved that conservation of the species can be reconciled with its sustainable use, generating social, ecological and economic results. Management projects conducted in the Amazon are largely successful. In those places where all criteria are met, the stocks of the species increased annually by almost 25%. Income generation by fishermen and women involved more than doubled, and an additional 4 million United States dollars were generated and distributed to local fisher's associations. These very positive results attracted fishermen from urban

areas around the protected areas, and also from other small communities. Federal Brazilian government formally recognized all those participatory fisheries management initiatives (Figueiredo, 2013), and during these processes, local fisher's associations had visibility and social recognition, increased their participation in public policy discussions, and had some access to their social rights. There was an important increase in gender equity. In 2017, 38% of members of pirarucu community-based fishery management were women, but in first years, 1998–2002, they were less than 5% (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2018). As a consequence of all these positive outcomes, a second expansion and replication took place after 2010 (Campos-Silva *et al.*, 2017; Campos-Silva & Peres, 2016; Castello, McGrath, *et al.*, 2011; Figueiredo, 2013). Nowadays the community-based management of pirarucu is performed at hundreds of small local communities spread the Brazilian Amazon, and in some other Amazonian countries, both inside and outside protected areas (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2018).

Coastal fisheries have also been improved by co-management or commons-based management systems, through established territorial rights to local fishers, who exploit highly valuable and resident resources. For example, commons-based tenure systems that recognize rights to fishers to exclusively exploit coastal areas by following well defined management rules have contributed to recover or maintain catches of valuable marine invertebrates, such as shellfish or lobsters, in Mexico (Álvarez *et al.*, 2018; De la Cruz-González *et al.*, 2018; B. Salas *et al.*, 2014), Chile (Defeo *et al.*, 2016; Gelcich *et al.*, 2010, 2017), Uruguay (Defeo *et al.*, 2016), Australia (Mayfield *et al.*, 2012) and in Pacific Island countries (Thaman *et al.*, 2017). Territorial use rights for fishing (TURFs), which are usually suitable for sedentary or low-mobility resources, can vary enormously in area, origin, objectives of the management measure and intensity of resource management within territorial use rights for fishing boundaries (Orensanz *et al.*, 2013). Collaboration with fishers and inclusion of their knowledge had contributed to improve catches of lobster (*Panulirus argus*) through a management program involving artificial habitats in the coast of Mexico (B. Salas *et al.*, 2014). Nevertheless, in some regions the territorial use rights for fishing boundaries coastal co-management in Chile may have caused depletion of shellfish (Aburto & Stotz, 2013), in addition to displacing effort and thus resulting in depleting resources in nearby open access areas (Garmendia *et al.*, 2021). Sustainable coastal fisheries for reef fish have been observed in regions or communities involved in community-based, sea tenure systems, or in bottom-up co-management, especially in some Pacific Island countries (Busilacchi *et al.*, 2013; Cohen & Alexander, 2013; Léopold *et al.*, 2017; Webster *et al.*, 2017) and in Hawaii (Friedlander *et al.*, 2013). These traditionally managed systems incorporate community rules and beliefs, usually showing positive social outcomes (Cinner *et al.*, 2012; Tilley

et al., 2019; F. J. Webster *et al.*, 2017; Yang & Pomeroy, 2017). However, their ability to sustain fish catches will depend on the species being exploited and on the specific management regime, for example the duration and frequency of opening areas periodically closed to fishing (Cohen & Foale, 2013; Goetze *et al.*, 2016; Hamilton *et al.*, 2019; Yang & Pomeroy, 2017).

In Europe, the crisis in the small-scale fisheries demanded urgent reforms that were only put in place very recently. Only a decade ago, more than 60% of all fish stocks exploited in European waters did not include analytical assessment, due to a lack of the necessary information (Macdonald *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, until very recently it was believed that about 90% of all fishing stocks were either depleted or overexploited (Rivera *et al.*, 2017). Since 2013, when the European Union reformed the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP, Regulation N°. 1380/2013), according to which all European fish stocks should be exploited at Maximum Sustainable Yield (MSY), or less, by 2020. This should be achieved through multiannual plans developed with the involvement of all stakeholders (Quetglas *et al.*, 2017) and implementing an “ecosystem approach to fisheries management (EAFM)”. Specific management regulations were introduced to mitigate problems of small-scale fisheries, including “collective actions” for the development of Local Management Plans (LMPs) (Battaglia *et al.*, 2017) and co-management practices. Nevertheless, some of these management regulations and measures, including the establishment of marine protected areas, were not always completely effective, and important problems were identified, such as the inadequate levels of social involvement and participation, and the use of ineffective communication tools (Baeta *et al.*, 2018; Morales-Nin *et al.*, 2017). However, there are examples of very successful management measures adopted by small-scale fishing systems in Europe, including

better fishing practices in many places, and the recovery of many of the exploited fishing stocks, the re-adaptation of old technologies and gears, and even the recovery of lost jobs and of economic viability (Cillari *et al.*, 2012). If co-management practices are potentially very effective in the adoption and promotion of good fishing practices, there are also examples of unsuccessful cases (Morales-Nin *et al.*, 2017; Rivera *et al.*, 2017; Silva *et al.*, 2019), due to the inappropriate governance systems adopted (Braga *et al.*, 2017; Carvalho *et al.*, 2017). In some instances, the reduction or the control of fishing effort, and the enforcement of the rules of protection to vulnerable aquatic habitats are not always related with the governance system in place (Lloret *et al.*, 2018).

6.5.1.2 Policies aligned across scale and interactions supported

Policy instruments that are aligned across modes of governance, spatial scale, activities, and incentives, such that policies complement or reinforce one another, result in more positive outcomes. However, policy alignment is dependent on the effective inclusion and participation (section 6.5.1.1) of all actors which requires the investment of time, resources, and thought into developing governance frameworks and approaches that can successfully coordinate interactions.

Within non-extractive use case studies, international conventions that form part of the international context were not intensively assessed. When national laws were found to link to specific local rules that guide activities, such as with whale watching regulations and permits, this resulted in more successful social and ecological sustainability outcomes for most countries. However, most of the case studies across practice reported a lack of this multilevel interaction among the diverse set of actors involved or affected by sustainable use policy, which resulted in illegal trade, lack of mutual trust, common goal conflicts, gaps in ecological data and conservation status of species due to taxonomic complexity, institutional barriers etc. (*Terminalia chebula*, India; Jucara Palm). Governance processes that pay attention to coordinating interactions thus supported more effective policies. For example, the most effective gathering case studies (Biggs & Messerschmidt, 2005; Brinckmann *et al.*, 2018; He *et al.*, 2011) highlighted the importance of healthy interactions on a common platform for diverse actors from different levels and sectors in gathering, that included the national government, indigenous peoples and local communities, women, local authorities' non-governmental organizations, middlemen, micro/small scale industry representatives, research organizations and if possible international agencies (He *et al.*, 2011; Hopping *et al.*, 2018; Misra *et al.*, 2008; Negi *et al.*, 2015; Poudyal, 2004; Stryamets *et al.*, 2012). Joint stakeholder consultations encouraged exchange and understanding,

awareness and provided the opportunity to local communities and indigenous peoples to share local and scientific knowledge among relevant actors. This helped in closing the gap between the communal and governmental efforts for adaptation and encouraged transformation towards sustainable resource management.

Interactions between actors in the fishing case studies were not always described in detail, but generally were supported by informal or formalized processes, e.g., via some kind of exchange forum. For example, in the case study from Baja California (Mexico) fishing cooperatives banded together into a federation providing a crucial link to the government agencies (McCay, 2014). Whereas, in the Amazonian pirarucu fishing case study (Box 6.5) (Campos-Silva & Peres, 2016), there was an explicit partnership formed between local communities, local associations, and government agencies. In contrast, where interactions are not supported on an equal footing, and management objectives between fishers and government agencies radically differ, as was the case for Lake Victoria inland small-scale fishing, then partnerships deteriorate rapidly to the point of severe conflicts and sometimes power abuse by the government (See section 6.5.4.3, Box 6.15) (Nunan, 2020; Nunan *et al.*, 2015). Dialogue and partnership are thus highlighted as important in ensuring management works.

Examples from Tanzania provide evidence that positive effects on wild species populations were made possible when support to grassroots law enforcement was provided (Lee, 2018; Mgumia & Oba, 2003). Similarly, when customary systems of governance are recognized and legitimized within statutory processes, policies are more likely to align. For example, in Ghana, sufficient local governance capacity was crucial to success. Chieftaincy remains integral to Ghana's electoral system and, as ultimate landowners, the chiefs are a respected authority that external agencies can engage directly. Consequently, the designation of the protected core zone, the establishment of conservation-related by-laws, and the negotiated resettlement of communities were made at the local level. As opposed to decrees passed down by remote government agencies, local representation in the decision process can yield support from even the most disadvantaged individuals. Furthermore, since chiefs challenge one another, a balance of power is established that facilitates accountability, transparency and equitable benefit distribution (D. J. Sheppard *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, a community's governance system should be understood and, if aligned with community based natural resource management approaches, co-management systems should be developed to fully empower community control over revenues and natural resources. In parallel, sufficient time is required for the planning phase to learn about the community's spiritual, cultural and economic connections to nature (D. J. Sheppard *et al.*, 2010).

However, supporting actor interactions and aligning laws and policies acting at different levels requires a considerable investment of time, research, and resources. This level of investment in gathering law and policy is extremely rare. The result is legal frameworks that are inconsistent and confusing, and a lack of clarity about which laws and government departments have jurisdiction over these products and activities. For example, the gathering policy environment in South Africa is characterized by a plethora of inefficient and sometimes contradictory national and provincial laws. These laws are only sporadically implemented, are often incompatible with each other, and are largely unknown by local communities. The laws then interface with customary systems that have eroded to varying degrees as a result of colonial and apartheid administration, but often offer the most effective regulation for wild algae, plants and fungi (Shackleton *et al.*, 2010; Wynberg & Laird, 2007). However, this is not limited to South Africa and legal frameworks were found to similarly lack clarity in hunting cases from other parts of the world.

Sometimes a lack of implementation results when government departments compete with each other, or their mandates conflict or overlap. As a result, no institution delegates the resources or staff needed to implement gathering regulations (Antypas *et al.*, 2002). In Cameroon, the 1994 Forestry Law (Republic of Cameroon, 1994) set up a gathering sub-directorate within the then ministry of environment and forests. This new body was provided with a civil servant to oversee activities, but had no budget and extremely limited power compared to the timber interests residing in the same ministry. Financial returns from taxes and fees on wild algae, plants and fungi went to other departments and ministries (Laird *et al.*, 2010). It is often the case that revenue streams, which could strengthen and build capacity within government to effectively regulate and manage wild algae, plants and fungi, are diverted to other, more powerful, entities in government. In the Western Ghats in India, for example, royalties collected on uppage (*Garcinia gummi-gutta*) went to the state treasury, with no allocation for conservation of the resource, and state efforts focused on policing the movement of material in order to collect royalties, rather than monitoring harvest and trade to ensure sustainability (Lele *et al.*, 2010).

6.5.1.3 Robust institutions

Considerable attention has been directed towards the understanding and evaluating the importance of governance quality as a short hand to understanding the extent to which structures, resources, capacity, and trust exist in sufficient quantities to ensure rules are adhered to and outcomes are monitored and fed back into an adaptive process. Chapter 6's experts draw on the notion of 'robust governance' to capture quality, a concept more often applicable to corporate governance, understood

to be an accountable and adaptive governance system with transparent distribution of roles and command, reporting and communication lines, inbuilt feedback mechanisms and understanding of operated realities (Baret *et al.*, 2013). Robust governance also broadly applies to the concept of policy robustness, which is defined as "the ability of governance arrangements in a policy to maintain performance in the presence of external/internal disturbances" (Capano & Woo, 2017).

Although the focus on governance quality has tended to be on centralized modes of government, this concept is applied across all modes of governance from statutory to customary, and make no judgement on what modes of governance are preferred. A functionally close concept to robust governance is "good governance" which results in a similar outcome (i.e., a policy implemented) (UNESCO, n.d.). However, while robust governance systems, can be considered 'good', they can also deliver outcomes without being considered 'good', e.g., with no orientation towards the consensus-seeking or transparency. This may be the case in top-down or even authoritarian governance regimes that manage to build a functional line of command through discipline.

Legal and regulatory approaches are far more ubiquitous than any other category of policy instrument (Table 6.6). Consequently, there is clear evidence of both failure and success, although government rules and institutions remain a backbone of governing wild species. Some of the best evidence of successful legal and regulatory approaches comes from industrial fisheries in regions with strong, and robust, management institutions, where resources and capacity exist. Consequently, governance is often highlighted in studies on fisheries management, be it through aspects on strong institutions, enforcement, participation, legitimacy or other aspects as a critical enabling condition (Figure 6.5) (Ye & Gutierrez, 2017). Despite recognition of the importance of robust institutions for legal and regulatory approaches, governance is weak in many contexts. Yet, legal and regulatory approaches remain the most commonly applied category of instrument in fisheries management across much of the world, and weak statutory governance remains a significant limiting factor.

In contrast, where robust governance institutions exist, a suite of management regulations have been adjusted and applied in response to changes in the status of exploited populations resulting in improved stock status of assessed fisheries (Hilborn *et al.*, 2020; Hilborn & Ovando, 2014; Melnychuk *et al.*, 2021; Worm *et al.*, 2009). The latter studies highlight, for instance, that where fish stocks are assessed and centralized institutions are strong, stocks are increasing or at target levels, and many are in good condition and suggests the overfishing problem and the need to identify alternative appropriate strategies mainly lies

with the unassessed stocks (Hilborn *et al.*, 2020). However, it should be noted though, that if a stock is unassessed, it is also impossible to judge if the level of fishing is appropriate and thereby determine whether it is overexploited or not.

According to one model-based metanalysis that included assessed and unassessed stocks, median fisheries were estimated to be in poor health and business as usual would likely lead to more collapses (Costello *et al.*, 2016), but according to estimates in the same study, it would take less than 10 years to recovery with simple management. A recent evaluation of the effect of historical management interventions on the status of 288 assessed marine populations found that explicit harvest control rules used to set quotas and formal rebuilding plans were most effective and that the benefits of co-occurring management measures at the local, national and international levels were cumulative (Melnychuk *et al.*, 2021). However, more successful outcomes associated with legal and regulatory fisheries management tend to be found in countries with stronger central governance, and large industrial fisheries where enforcement and monitoring is possible. A higher

redundancy in management tactics were also present in such countries with stronger central governance and having a high Human Development Index, thereby contributing to success (Gutiérrez *et al.*, 2011).

Robust formal or informal institutions, including clear mechanisms to monitor, detect, and enforce rules, are relevant across various forms of governance. In the dry forest of southern Madagascar, southern Androy, 188 forest patches were mapped and characterized, revealing 174 “taboo forests”, ranging in size from, 1 to 142 hectares. All of them were protected by taboos and referred to as *ala kibory*, forests that are burial grounds for the ancestors and thus highly respected and protected. Human interaction with and resource extraction from the taboo forests are highly restricted by the taboos, with heavy sanctions enforced by the local community as well as through beliefs in spiritual powers. Enforcement of the taboos is responsibility of the clan that owns the patch. If forest damage is found, a clan meeting is called to establish guilt and sanctions. Regulated hunting, grazing, honey harvesting and gathering of wild species are permitted. Taboos were applied to

a variety of forest types, including areas with a weak association to spiritual beliefs, such as honey groves and private forest, which illustrates the generality of taboos as a rule mechanism in the society. Thus, they can be seen as a component of a local governance system for forest resources that receives additional legitimacy through the respect for the ancestors, shared by non-Christians as well as Christians in the community. In addition to belief systems, the study also shows how other mechanisms play a key role in maintaining the protection of the taboo forest, such as the well-established and recognized physical sanctions decided on by the clan elders and functioning enforcement including mechanisms for monitoring, detection, and conviction. The local faly, meaning forbidden or “you shall not,” is a component of the laws inherited from the ancestors. These rules are thus more restrictive than the state rules and sanctioning is much stronger and more efficient (Tengö *et al.*, 2007).

Thus, secure forest resource tenure and management rights; systems for monitoring and regulation; systems for adaptation and control; and greater access to markets repeatedly emerge as enabling sustainable use across gathering case studies. *De facto* community tenure systems for wild species enable an important opportunity for initiating community-based resource management that can be complementary to state policy efforts.

Although democratic decentralization has improved levels of public participation and, in some cases, government accountability, its ability to address rural inequality and poverty has been relatively modest (Johnson, 2001). Effective decentralization requires the construction of accountable institutions at all levels of government and a secure domain of autonomous decision making at the local level. The political dynamics in policy reforms usually play a crucial debilitating role. It creates a divergence between the rhetorical claims for decentralization and the institutional changes that take place (Ribot *et al.*, 2006).

While top-down robust governance systems can quickly achieve setting objectives, they are usually less effective on post-project sustainability and strategic oversight. Bottom-up robust governance approaches in contrast, are often slower (Niedzialkowski & Shkaruba, 2018). For example, the Solability 2020 governance efficiency ranking (Solability, 2021) based on good governance indicators places Belarus on the 90th position, while Ukraine is on the 81st and Romania is on the impressive 18th. Both Ukraine and Romania have sustainability concerns with devastating impacts on biodiversity, including large scale illegal logging in the Carpathian Mountains (including logging in protected forests) (Schlingemann, 2017). Yet, this is not a problem in Belarus (which also boast a large forest stock), arguably due to the stern discipline in the chain of command in this autocracy. In contrast, governance systems for both

democracies, Romania and Ukraine, is weak and highly susceptible to corruption. The scale of the problem can be illustrated by the non-governmental organization Earthsight's investigation ‘flatpacked forest’ (Earthsight, 2020). This investigation highlighted a clear connection between illegally harvested beech timber from protected forests in Ukrainian Carpathians, and Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) certified beech timber sold to IKEA. Despite the presence in Ukraine of national forest and biodiversity conservation monitoring and oversight agencies, the globally most relied upon mechanism of private governance in the trade of sustainable timber (FSC), a business globally renowned for its respect for the environment (IKEA), and the European Union global mechanism for preventing illegal timber imports (European Union Forest Law enforcement, Governance and Trade action plan), sustainability policy is failing because of the absence of a ‘robust’ governance framework.

6.5.2 Institutional arrangements that enable sustainable use

6.5.2.1 Tailored to the context

For sustainable use of wild species, specialized policy instruments focusing on the use of wild species, that are tailored to the local social and ecological context are necessary. However, in many cases, strategic policies for managing use of wild species are not well established or implemented. Oftentimes, policies effective in one timescale and context are applied uncritically elsewhere with mixed outcomes. More effective policies: i) are targeted to the species or group of species context; ii) ensure the costs of management do not exceed the benefits; and iii) direct resources to where needed.

Different management schemes work better -and are more effective- depending on the different groups of species hunted (vertebrate classes). For example, for reptiles, ranching has proven to be a very effective sustainable use scheme, which increases the survival rate of the harvested eggs, while increasing the production of crocodile skins and providing incentives for indigenous peoples and local communities to conserve the whole ecosystem under management (**Box 6.4**). However, for big mammals, mixed-use management that involve hunting or harvesting individuals in the wild, while also reproducing or raising them in captivity to reinforce wild populations when needed, has proven to be effective, as this scheme enables a bigger offer and a higher benefit for indigenous peoples and local communities and the involved stakeholders, while maintaining healthy populations and habitats.

‘Sticks’, such as permits, quotas, taxes and restrictions on trade are often employed to regulate wild product use, particularly in a perceived overharvesting crisis. However,

'carrots' in the form of incentives and supportive legal frameworks, such as government support for producer, trade and processing groups; market access and premium prices *via* certification; tax breaks; and outreach and education on new policies and laws usually work best for this category of products. In some cases, particularly when there is sudden and high commercial demand, both approaches are necessary.

The effects of installing private property rights will vary depending on the ecological and country context. The introduction of individual quotas within fisheries inevitably means a change in the structure of fishing and who can access the resource. This has implications for equity and social cohesion of the communities that are affected. Individual transferable quotas or catch shares assign private property rights on a fraction of the total allowable catch or effort to individuals or firms who can use them, lease them or trade them. They have been advocated as a way to eliminate the "race for fish", increasing economic efficiency by rationalizing access to a common-pool resource, improving safety at sea, and promoting a long-term view on the sustainability of the fishing. As a relatively new but increasingly used tool in management of industrial, data-rich fisheries, they have been highly controversial, with divisive arguments raised from both philosophical and empirical grounds. Opponents have questioned on ethical principles the *de facto* privatization of an otherwise public resource; whereby initial quota recipients are granted shared ownership at no charge while future entrants have to purchase or lease quota to access the resource. Individual transferable quotas are used in industrial, data-rich fishing that manage with total allowable quotas based on biomass estimates and harvest control rules. Small-scale fisheries most often lack the data required to implement conventional fisheries management. This hinders or precludes the use of some management approaches that rely on data, such as individual transferable quotas – which are generally considered inappropriate for small scale fisheries.

In terms of performance, the implementation of individual transferable quotas entails clear trade-offs between different sustainability dimensions, and outcomes vary depending on program design and fishing characteristics. On the one hand, increased economic efficiency associated with consolidation of the fishing power into a reduced number of more efficient vessels has been supported by several studies (Arnason R., 2002; Fox *et al.*, 2003; Grafton *et al.*, 2000; NRC (National Research Council), 1999) although others have found that quota leasing may introduce inefficiencies (Pinkerton & Edwards, 2009). On the other hand, concentration of quota ownership has raised equity issues (Donkersloot & Carothers, 2017), as deck hands and fleet sectors have been displaced, as illustrated by the Pacific halibut case study (Box 6.6). They may lead to skewed power relationships, which may increase conflicts

and result in 'poaching' instead of controlled extraction. While there is abundant anecdotal evidence that secure catch shares promote increased fishers' participation and stewardship (Grafton *et al.*, 2006), it has been argued that the theory that quota ownership may promote stewardship remains unproved (van Putten *et al.*, 2014) and may break down when quotas are increasingly leased and quota owners are separated from fishing operations (Edwards & Pinkerton, 2019b).

The extent to which individual transferable quotas contribute to ecological sustainability is hard to evaluate because of confounding effects of other regulatory measures, mainly a total allowable quota or an effort quota, that are a prerequisite for the introduction of individual transferable quotas. In other words, the ecological effects of the individual allocation of transferable quota shares are hard to separate from the effects of the total allowable quotas *per se* (i.e., the benefits from setting and enforcing an adequate total allowable quota) (van Putten *et al.*, 2014). While Costello *et al.* (2008) concluded that well-designed catch shares may prevent fishery collapse, other empirical studies have failed to find clear evidence that the implementation of individual transferable quotas has led to improved resource status (Essington *et al.*, 2012; Thébaud *et al.*, 2012). A more recent global empirical analysis of 800 stocks conducted using a different methodology to attribute causality (Isaksen & Richter, 2019) found that property rights may have a positive ecological effect, reducing the probability of a stock collapsing, but the effects depend on attributes of the quota system, the resource and the institutional context. Individual quotas were found to be more effective when they are transferable, when there is high ownership protection and trade openness, and when the species have high value and high growth rate. The positive effects of quotas materialize around 10 years after implementation, as it takes time to rebuild stocks, species with high turnover responding faster to policy. An interesting result of the analysis was that many fisheries have either favorable ecological condition to introduce private property rights, or institutional conditions, but rarely both. Therefore, due to feedbacks and interactions between different forces a clear prediction of effectiveness cannot be generalized.

The focus in gathering, fishing, and logging certification schemes on large scale enterprises is due to the high cost of the certification process. However, successful policies ensure the costs of management do not exceed the benefits. Candidates for certification must pay for certification and have well developed infrastructure and finance to support marketing needs and reporting requirements. As a result, certification is less likely to be pursued, awarded, or sustained for small-scale fishing, small-scale logging, gathering, or terrestrial animal harvesting (especially community-managed ones). For example, within terrestrial animal harvesting and gathering, a limited number of species

Box 6 Pacific halibut case study.

The Pacific halibut fishery has been considered a poster child for how the introduction of individual transferable quotas led to increased economic efficiency and safety at sea, together with improved product quality and availability. However, clear trade-offs exist with social impacts of individual transferable quotas implementation.

Pacific halibut is distributed on the west coast of the United States of America and Canada, from California to the Bering Sea. The directed fishery is intensely monitored and regulated by the International Pacific Halibut Commission, established by convention in 1923. Total allowable quotas are set for each of several regulatory areas based on annual assessments of stock size, supported by a rich data base including coast-wide setline surveys of abundance and intense monitoring of fishing operations. While the stock has been declining and the global total allowable quotas is at its lowest level since the 1980s, a responsive management system is in place and the latest stock assessment report (IPHC, 2021) concluded that the resource is not overfished nor subject to overfishing. The fishery from Alaska and Washington has been certified by the Marine Stewardship Council since 2006.

Individual quotas were introduced in Canada starting in 1991 and in the United States of America in 1995. In the United States of America, prior to the introduction of individual transferable quotas, there was no limit in the number of fishing licenses that could be issued, which led to an increase in fleet size and a concomitant reduction in the duration of the fishing season as the fishery was closed when the total allowable quotas were caught. In the end, some regulatory areas in Alaska had openings that lasted less than two-days a year, which resulted in difficulties to control the total allowable quotas, lost gear and unsafe fishing conditions, and glutted markets and reduced prices. With the implementation of individual transferable quotas, the fishing season was extended

to 9 months, fresh fish became available to consumers, prices increased and there was a 50% fleet consolidation (Donkersloot & Carothers, 2017). The situation was less extreme in Canada, where a limited-entry program existed prior to individual transferable quotas.

While the concentration of quota ownership into fewer hands following individual transferable quotas implementation increased economic efficiency, it redistributed benefits and resulted in equity issues, displacing labor and smaller-scale fleet sectors and disproportionately affecting small, mostly indigenous communities in Alaska and Canada. Restrictions on quota trade between sectors have been introduced to address community goals at the cost of decreased economic efficiency (Kroetz *et al.*, 2015). The community purchase program established by the North Pacific fisheries management council to allow small communities to purchase quota collectively has failed to redistribute quotas due to high quota price and lack of quotas for sale (Donkersloot & Carothers, 2017). While traditionally the halibut fishery was operated by owners, the majority of the catch in Canada is now leased out by processors and larger fishing companies (owner-operators own only 16% of the quota in 2016) (Edwards & Pinkerton, 2019b), and it is hard for new entrants to purchase quota. The increase in lease prices and the disconnection of quota owners from fishing operations conflict with the rationale for individual transferable quotas as an efficient market-based management instrument and erode the effectiveness of ownership to incentivize resource stewardship (Edwards & Pinkerton, 2019b; Pinkerton & Edwards, 2009). The Canadian government has been buying licenses since 1997 for repatriation of fishery access to indigenous peoples. In 2018, there were 76 such licenses making up 16% of the total allowable quotas (Edwards & Pinkerton, 2019a). As a whole, these authors have argued that the program has failed to meet stated objectives for distribution of benefits.

are legally tradeable (hunting), or have sufficient tradeable value (gathering) to sustain market-based mechanisms. For example, some of the wild species' products on the market that can be successfully and legally commercialized, that come from hunting, ranching and farming, and in which the costs of certification are considered justified, are crocodile and alligator skin, meat, and eggs.

Consequently, certification programs that account for the reality that many collectors' livelihoods (and conservation) strategies are based on the absence of a market mechanism for harvesting activities are more likely to succeed, this has been found to be particularly relevant for the gathering of wild plants for trade. Certification programs that can support the overall livelihood strategies of wild plant collectors are more likely to be effective at supporting sustainable use (Box 6.7). Local adaptability of wild plant certification is grounded in an understanding of

what ecological and economic sustainability mean to the target community and individual collectors (Makita, 2018). For example, certifications and labeling schemes have been developed that recognize the value of indigenous and local knowledge which have been used to support local economies and community well-being, associated with gathering wild edible plants, seaweeds, and mushrooms which have a tradable value.

Around 30% of the total selected cases, across all five practices, include community-based management. Community-based management is particularly prevalent in the gathering and non-extractive use practice cases. (D. E. Lee, 2018). For conservationists, the real question is whether community-based tourism provides an effective incentive for communities to take conservation action. This incentive can take several forms. The ideal is a direct linkage, in which nature-based tourism earnings are so

Box 6.7 Gathering – FairWild (India).

The FairWild certification system was implemented to enable tribal community members to sustain Haritaki trees (*Terminalia chebula*) scattered in their private plots and the forestland's vegetation by benefiting from the commercial value of the tree species in Bhimashankar wildlife sanctuary, India. By providing economic incentives through certification, FairWild aimed to induce a shift from the harvest of immature berries to mature berries. Due to an increase in demand over the last decade for immature berries in local markets, the majority of collectors increased their harvests of mature berries for the FairWild project while continuing to harvest the same quantities of immature berries for local traders. This unanticipated project outcome was attributed to the unique nature of wild plants as an uncertain income source without any financial, physical, or human investments. Collectors developed their own concepts of ecological and economic sustainability derived from this unique income source endowed by nature, and incorporated the new economic opportunity into their own natural resource management strategies that evidently differed from those designed for the FairWild project.

FairWild certifications are applied in many ways but, collectors have their own objectives for introducing certification within a specific setting. FairWild primarily benefited the most vulnerable members of the community but also ironically increased the net amount of Haritaki berries harvested. It was difficult to dislodge the collectors' belief of sales of immature berries being more lucrative, despite the introduction of the FairWild project for mature berries. Although, increase in value added to mature berries secured recognition of the importance of Haritaki trees within the community, the certification does not relate with the community concept of ecological sustainability. Confirmation of the higher value of immature berries could have resulted in increasing ecological sustainability but, collectors believed that their gathering practices were already sustainable with the belief that they cannot increase the harvests of immature berries with the aim to sell the available quantity of immature berries at a higher price. FairWild strategies contributed to economic sustainability but the income was insufficient and required introduction of another stable income source complementary to FairWild certification and an alternative or a direct intervention in the harvest of immature berries (Makita, 2018).

high that people deliberately protect biodiversity to protect that income. Nature-based tourism can also draw local labor and capital away from biodiversity unfriendly activities (Wunder, 2000).

A ban is a stringent legal instrument, and although wild species trade bans may be necessary and are valuable tools in specific cases, their effectiveness depends on many context-specific factors that should be considered including: demand for wild species, capacity to enforce regulations in exporting and importing countries, governance, the species conservation status, local customs, traditional use, and alternatives for indigenous peoples and local communities' livelihoods, among others. In the short term, hunting bans can be effective by giving threatened species time to recover, while drivers of population decrease are identified and remedial actions are implemented. In the long-term, a hunting ban is a costly conservation measure that requires large enforcement efforts and heavy budgets, while providing disincentives to conserving ecosystems, often resulting in land use change to promote other activities that provide revenues to local communities (see [Table 6.7](#) for the list of cases studies on terrestrial animal harvesting).

Rowcliffe *et al.* (2004) investigated the effectiveness of species protection law in the Democratic Republic of Congo, where limited hunting was allowed, with the exception of some mammal species. The authors tested if species legal protection was in any degree effective, by comparing a prey choice model to collected data. Data was collected in a protected area (Garamba National Park),

where hunting was prohibited, and in a hunting reserve (Azande Hunting Reserve), where some species could not be hunted. Use of automatic rifles was illegal in both areas. In the study, the authors conclude that legal protection has had no effect on hunters' prey choice decisions in the analyzed system. This means, protected species were equally or more hunted than unprotected species. The authors indicate as a main reason the minimal enforcement of species protection laws registered in the area during the duration of their study and indicate that selective protection is likely to be extremely difficult to achieve in the absence of robust institutions. They also indicate that the effectiveness of species protection laws could be improved most dramatically by increasing the probability that violations will be detected, rather than by increasing penalties.

The idea of directing investments more towards active fisheries management worldwide has been proposed, however depending on definitions, this may lack realism due to the amount of money and logistics required to carry out the major elements of conventional fisheries management such as fisheries surveys, stock assessments, etc. in areas that are not equipped to invest into such processes, without clarity on who would pay for such processes and their effectiveness. It is also a recurring question whether the conventional management approach developed for large-scale single species industrial fisheries, is suitable and applicable in small-scale multi-species fisheries (see [Table 6.5](#) for a contrast in assessment and management approaches used in industrial *versus* small-scale fisheries). The conventional tools such as effort regulations and

Table 6 7 Example list of cases from terrestrial animal harvesting regulations.

Other case studies to be in the data management report at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4663236>.

Case study	References
Bighorn Sheep	Félix, 2006; Flores, 2015; Gobierno del Estado de Sonora, 2012; R. Lee, 2008; Luque Agraz & Doode Matsumoto, 2009; Luque & Doode, 2007; Mosig, Muñoz-Lacy, <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Polar bear	Tyrrell & Clark, 2014
Saltwater crocodile harvest & ranching	Fukuda <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Lions (countries A: Namibia & Mozambique)	P. Lindsey, Alexander, <i>et al.</i> , 2012; P. Lindsey, Balme, <i>et al.</i> , 2012
Lions (countries B: Zambia, Zimbabwe & Tanzania)	P. Lindsey, Alexander, <i>et al.</i> , 2012; P. Lindsey, Balme, <i>et al.</i> , 2012
Subsistence Hunting (Mayas)	Rosales Meda & Hermes Calderón, 2010
Kangaroos	Chee & Wintle, 2010; Descovich <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Gilroy, 2004; Lunney, 2010; Olsen & Low, 2006; Williams & Price, 2010; G. R. Wilson & Edwards, 2019
Turtle eggs harvest (Ostional)	Ballestero <i>et al.</i> , 2000; brenes Chavez & Cedeño Solis, 2017; L. Campbell, 1998; L. M. Campbell <i>et al.</i> , 2007, 2012; Cedeño Solis, n.d.; Garcia & McHugh, 2005; Klopfer, 2014; López, 2012; Sardeshpande & MacMillan, 2019; SINAC, 2012; Valverde <i>et al.</i> , 2012
Ritual maya	Santos-Fita, 2015
Falco trapping (artificial nests)	Dixon, 2011, 2016; Dixon & Batbayar, 2010; Janchivlamdan, 2014; Naranjo <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Rahman <i>et al.</i> , 2014
Subsistence hunting Brazil	Antunes <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Bragagnolo <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Tomas <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Vieira de Mattos <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Spectacled and black caiman	Botero-Arias & Regatieri, 2013; Franco <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Marioni <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Mendonça <i>et al.</i> , 2016; Pimenta <i>et al.</i> , 2018
Hunting in a region of China	Jia <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Lundberg & Zhou, 2010; Yin, 2006; Y. Zhou & Lundberg, 2009
Hunting in Congo	Mavah, 2011; Smith <i>et al.</i> , 2019a
Bear hunt in Croatia	Knott <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Majić <i>et al.</i> , 2011

in particular catch quotas and size limits are difficult to implement due to lack of data and general resistance among fishers, and more community-based approaches are more likely to succeed. This, however, requires acceptance among policymakers that the industrial-scale framework is inappropriate, which is rarely the case (Kolding & Zwieten, 2012).

Available money can be spent in various ways, including on subsidies capacity enhancement (with negative ecological effects) or limiting fishing pressure (positive ecological effects) – and monetary investment can support reaching management objectives if focused on the latter rather than the former (Melnychuk *et al.*, 2017). Money could also be invested into active management of world's unmanaged fisheries (capacity development towards conventional fisheries management in more places). Rather than focusing on creating conventional data-driven conventional fisheries management situations (which seems highly unrealistic from a financial point of view, and have severe ecological side effects such as fisheries induced evolution and disturbed ecosystems from selective harvest patterns), other options may include: (i) invest in creating leaders, social 'capital' (Gutiérrez *et al.*, 2011); (ii) support low-income countries'

efforts to transition away from capacity enhancing subsidies (Gill *et al.*, 2017; Sumaila *et al.*, 2021).

Additional measures could include area-based measures. There is something to be said about establishing marine protected areas all over the world as currently happening also due to the push within the Aichi targets framework (note the % in Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) has been achieved but not the networking of marine protected areas, which is also part of the target) without providing sufficient capacity to enforce them (Gill *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, the term "marine protected area" can have a broad variety of meanings and affect many dimensions of marine uses (fisheries, mining, shipping etc.) so the type of marine protected area (as well as the process by which it is put in place of course) would have a strong influence on whether it can be viewed as adding to sustainability of fishing. In addition, marine protected areas are systematically set up in areas with low political opposition (Stevenson *et al.*, 2020), sometimes reducing their capacity to fulfil the biodiversity goals they were initially intended for.

Of the 33 analyzed gathering case studies, 22 cases (67%) involve legal or regulatory instruments, however in all cases

these were applied in combination with economic, social, and/or rights-based instruments. Laws specifically tailored towards the different types of wild plant and fungi use (e.g., subsistence, local trade, commercial trade, recreational) are most effective. This would mean, for example, that subsistence use is only regulated in cases where there are clear risks of overharvesting, but that attention is paid to internationally traded industrial-scale products. Linked to this is greater attention towards understanding the relationship between wild product use and agriculture, the importance of harvest timing for subsistence and cash income, and other critical features. In general, regulatory instruments have the potential to generate positive ecologically sustainable outcomes and are reinforced when accompanied by codes of conduct and community-based instruments with social and economic aspects. Within gathering case studies, flexibility in measures was found to enable adaptation to accommodate shifts in market demand, safety concerns, climate change, other land-use activities and other common disruptions to wild product trade.

A few governments have developed gathering law and policy in a more strategic manner. This includes undertaking research and building ecological, economic, social and cultural understanding of species, incorporating comprehensive consultations with stakeholders, and developing a strategy for the resulting legal framework. In the past decade, for example, Namibia has taken a proactive and progressive approach towards gathering policy and regulation, recognizing that these products provide vital income and livelihoods for communities in an environment characterized by extreme aridity and few economic opportunities (Bennett, 2006; Cole & Nakamhela, 2008; Nott & Wynberg, 2008; R. P. Wynberg, 2010).

Finland is also a notable exception to the rule of government neglect for wild algae, plants and fungi. The Finnish government has supported scientific research on wild berries for decades, including studies of their cultural and economic importance, as well as biological and ecological research (Kangas, 1999). At the same time, it has actively promoted berry and mushroom harvesting as an economic activity and cultural practice. Indeed, rather than discouraging harvesting as many countries have done, the government has developed programs to promote harvesting and related industries. These include a berry crop forecasting system and income-tax relief favorable to harvesters, providing them with the information and incentives they need to participate more effectively in gathering industries (Richards & Saastamoinen, 2010).

Successful social and information-based approaches within gathering case studies include a strong focus on ecological, economic, social and cultural understanding of species, incorporating comprehensive consultations with stakeholders and developing an overall strategy for

implementation. Within non-extractive use case studies, local codes of conduct in addition to normative rules are very useful and result in more positive outcomes of social and economic sustainability. The effectiveness of community-based nature tourism is context dependent since there is often a lack of skills and education limiting the economic potential of this activity and sometimes social conflicts can emerge, but in general they are successful in economic and social aspects.

One example where (ecological) effectiveness may be improved by social and information-based tools come from catch and release recreational fishing. This has gained increasing attention during the last decades both due to its potential impacts on fish populations (Cooke & Cowx, 2004) and the environment (Lewin *et al.*, 2019), but also because of its high socioeconomic importance engendering substantial social and economic benefits (Hyder *et al.*, 2018; Lynch *et al.*, 2016). Recreational fishing takes place in freshwater, saltwater and brackish water environments, and recreational fishers use a range of fishing gear including traps, nets, longlines, and spears, but most commonly rod and line. Harvest of the catch for consumption is an important component of recreational fishing (Cooke *et al.*, 2018), however, a large proportion (in many cases more than 50%) of the catch is released both in freshwater and marine environments (Cooke & Cowx, 2004; Ferter *et al.*, 2013). Releasing a fish alive to the water where it was caught with rod and line is termed “catch-and-release”, a practice performed both due to management regulations (i.e., regulatory catch-and-release) and personal motivations (i.e., voluntary catch-and-release) (Arlinghaus *et al.*, 2007).

While the underlying assumption of catch-and-release is that the released fish survive without major impacts, catch-and-release practice can lead to unintended sublethal impacts or post-release mortality. Post-release mortality varies substantially by fish species and fishery, and depends on many factors including, but not limited to, anatomical hooking location, capture depth, fighting time, air exposure duration, and water temperature (Bartholomew & Bohnsack, 2005). Anatomical hooking location is one of the most important factors influencing post-release mortality. When fishes are hooked in the lips, hooking injury and associated bleeding is often limited, but deep- and gill-hooking can cause severe injuries and bleeding which often causes mortality of the released fish. Capture depth plays an important role for some fish species with a closed swim bladder. When these fish are pulled to the surface, the air in the swim bladder expands due to decompression causing so-called barotrauma which results in swim bladder rupture, gas bubbles in the blood, and “pop-eyes” (Ferber *et al.*, 2015).

While some fish species recover from barotrauma, others experience high post-release mortality rates. When

practicing catch-and-release, minimizing negative Catch-and-Release impacts is essential if the aim is to reduce fishing mortality while maintaining recreational fishing opportunities. This can be achieved by developing species-specific best-practice guidelines based on scientific knowledge (Cooke & Suski, 2005). These guidelines can inform recreational fishers about the survival capability of their target species, environmental conditions when catch-and-release should be avoided, and specific fishing and handling practices which can be adopted to minimize post-release mortality. While catch-and-release practice is not appropriate for all fish species, for some species, its practice can come close to a “non-lethal” extractive use when best practice is followed.

6.5.2.2 Clear and aligned ownership rights, responsibilities, and goals

For successful policy formation and implementation, policy goals and instruments need to be clearly identified, aligned, and shared with stakeholders. Yet, often legal uncertainties, opaque policies, and a lack of resources inhibit the effectiveness of sustainable use policies (Box 6.8). There is

thus a need for access and ownership rights to be clear, for roles and responsibilities to be defined, and to articulate and align the purpose of both policy and instrument.

Evident across the gathering case studies the importance of clarifying access and ownership rights to resources and land when developing regulatory frameworks for the gathering of wild plants and fungi. Providing an enabling environment for traditional knowledge protection and local industries and producers helps to support sustainability outcomes. In this regard, customary laws can often provide a more nuanced approach to regulation, integrating unique local cultural, ecological and economic conditions in ways that better suit this category of products. Gathering case studies found where land tenure and resource rights are secure, customary laws are still strong, and local capacity exists to manage the resource base and deal with commercial pressures. Conversely, in cases where customary law has broken down to a significant degree, or outside commercial pressure has intensified well beyond the carrying capacity of traditional measures, governments can offer important and necessary complementary levels of regulation. Interventions should thus be crafted to

Box 6.8 Legal uncertainties and lack of resources constrains hunting policies: Brazil.

There is consensus among conservationists that wild species hunting is a major conservation issue in Brazil. Hunting is a widespread and culturally embedded activity throughout the Brazilian territory (Bragagnolo *et al.*, 2019; El Bizri *et al.*, 2015), but decisions on wild species management has historically disregarded the knowledge, interests, necessities and perceptions of those who practice hunting in the country (El Bizri *et al.*, 2015; Pezzuti *et al.*, 2018; Vieira de Mattos *et al.*, 2019). While new integrated landscape management policies were developed in Brazil to encourage sustainable production systems, i.e., agroforestry (Miccolis *et al.*, 2011), and to strengthen management strategies of value chains, i.e., wood and non-timber forestry production and fisheries (Campos-Silva *et al.*, 2017), hunting governance in the country remains weak, and formal hunting management systems are still virtually inexistent. In addition, the country faces a lack of land tenure regularization, especially in remote areas such as the Amazon, that affects the autonomy of rural, traditional and indigenous peoples in managing their territories according to their traditional practices (Constantino *et al.*, 2018; van Vliet *et al.*, 2019). The uncertainty in terms of land possession, along with the political invisibility of local cultural norms and management systems, weaken the decision power of local actors and allow illegal activities to flourish (Vieira de Mattos *et al.*, 2019).

One of the main drawbacks to hunting management in Brazil is the contradictory national legislation. The current legal framework on hunting is composed of a diffused set of policy instruments loaded with ambiguities and lacking crucial

definitions of terms, concepts and rights, causing many people to live under legal uncertainty (Antunes *et al.*, 2019; Vieira de Mattos *et al.*, 2019). Indigenous peoples of Brazil (here, exclusively the people considered “Brazilian índios”, around ¼ of all indigenous peoples in the country) are the only group unquestionably guaranteed by law (Law 6,001/73) of “the exclusive exercise of hunting and fishing in the areas they occupy”. All other human groups, including traditional and rural people who often live in remote areas with poor access to urban goods and depend on wild meat for subsistence, are subject to the conflicting interpretation of the laws.

The main law regulating wild species hunting in Brazil is the wildlife protection law (Law 5197/67), which since 1967 prohibits the “use, persecution, destruction, hunting, or harvest” of wild species. The environmental crimes law (Law 9605/98), enacted in 1998, included an exception to hunting whenever it is carried out in a “state of necessity, to satiate the hunger of the agent or their family”. One could state that this exception would be sufficient to permit subsistence hunting (hunting to obtain an essential source of food) to be carried out in Brazil. However, there is no clarity by these laws of what a “state of necessity” entails, meaning that environmental control agencies have the discretion to judge whether a person is hunting out of the need for food or not (Antunes *et al.*, 2019; Coad *et al.*, 2019). The lack of clarity of these laws drove Brazilian environmental control agencies to adopt criminalization and suppression of any type of hunting in the country as their main approach (Pezzuti *et al.*, 2018). Consequently, subsistence hunting is often regarded as a

crime, which generates food insecurity to and imperil the culture and traditions of millions of local peoples (Pezzuti *et al.*, 2018).

On top of these legal uncertainties, surveillance and control of wild species crimes in Brazil is ineffective due to the country's extensive territory and lack of investment. For instance, in the Brazilian Amazon, only 1,229 officials are responsible for surveilling more than five million km² of forest, a rate much lower than that recommended by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (Oliveira *et al.*, 2020). Hunting is responsible for almost a quarter (18.2%) of all environmental infractions in protected areas of the Brazilian Amazon (Kauano *et al.*, 2017), but prosecutions and payments of fines related to these infractions are rare (Barreto *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, even if hunting were kept being considered as a crime, the Brazilian government would not be able to enforce the legislation

and curb this activity in the long-term (El Bizri *et al.*, 2015). Meanwhile, there are very few formal plans or regulations for managing hunting implemented in the country, what means hunting is *de facto* open access.

Considering the challenges posed above, researchers advocate that to improve wild species management, strengthen local governance mechanisms, and reduce the impacts of hunting in Brazil, there is a critical need to amend national legislation and offer legal, political and technical support to community-based and co-management initiatives aimed at managing wild species (Campos-Silva *et al.*, 2017; Morcatty & Valsecchi, 2015). These steps, they claim, would increase democratization and decentralization of management decisions (Campos-Silva *et al.*, 2020), and consequently increase empowerment of local people, producing fair outcomes.

Photo: A lowland tapir (*Tapirus terrestris*) hunted for subsistence in a local community in the Brazilian Amazon. © Thais Morcatty CC-BY.

include local-level institutions and management systems where these are effective. Building on, aligning with, or complementing traditional resource rights is an important approach to minimize paperwork, avoid duplication of existing laws and enhance sustainable use. However, this requires real commitments of time, money, research, and extensive stakeholder consultation.

Clearly defined rights support more sustainable use policies; however, these rights may take many forms. In many of the successful fishing case studies, the communities have

some degree of rights over the area or resource, some operate with catch shares, others not. However, there is no single combination model that appears more effective than others. While catch shares and strong ownership are often assumed to be beneficial, a case study of octopus fishing in Madagascar (Oliver *et al.*, 2015) for instance clearly states that common property institutions can successfully implement management without property rights over the resource. In other instances, indigenous peoples and local communities may have the rights to fish but government encroaches on this *via* creeping regulations or permit

requirements (case studies on Sami fishing rights, Finland and Torres Strait islanders fishing). Court cases then reaffirmed the constitutional rights of indigenous peoples and local communities to e.g., maintain and develop their culture (Sami fishing rights, Finland). Clearly defined roles and boundaries, whether intentional or *de facto* - i.e., through isolation, can help with ease of enforcement. In the Baja California (Mexico) fishing case study, it was hypothesized (McCay, 2014) that the relative isolation of the fishing cooperatives on the Vizcaino peninsula contributed to the successful management of local benthic resources. Had they been closer to urban areas and with more people, enforcement costs and failures would likely have been higher and there may have been pressure to open the cooperatives to more members. However, there was not yet (in 2014) an actual comparison of the location with other locations at that time to really support this hypothesis. In the pirarucu fishing case study in the Amazon, a study showed direct impact of walking distance to nearest village on the ecological outcomes, as this related to the enforcement capacity of the protection of the lakes. Adjacency effects are also mentioned in the Baja California (Mexico) case study as leading to positive reinforcement of good practices when adjacent communities/cooperatives also care for their wild species (McCay, 2014). And in a coral reef fishing case study (East Africa), it is also suggested that there is a negative impact on own behavior if an adjacent community doesn't manage well.

The Convention on Biological Diversity addresses and highlights the role of protected areas for biodiversity conservation. However, protected areas are designated for conservation as well as sustainable use of wild species highlighting the need for clarity between goals and policies. At the national level protected areas clearly play a role as a key strategy for conserving biodiversity. Thus, the cases which adopted protected areas in terrestrial animal harvesting, non-extractive use, and gathering showed positive effects to ecological sustainability. However, there are few specific regulations which stipulate possible and prohibited activities for the use of wild species in the management of protected areas. Thus, specialized and sub-divided legal instruments are necessary to manage the use of wild species.

Designation of protected areas are effective for regulating wild species non-extractive use when a clear conservation objective and management program are applied that identify the number, zoning and appropriate activities for nature-based tourism. Natural protected areas in some cases have entrance fees but the number of visitors is estimated using different techniques such as visitor impact management between other techniques. The measurement of the number of visitors determines the success of the protected area in regulating nature-based tourism, especially in terms of environmental impact.

Total hunting bans have been proven to have limited effects when applied over the long-term. If applied, they should be evaluated on a case-by-case basis that takes into consideration the conservation status of the targeted species along with local traditions for species use. In most cases, it is preferable to apply temporary bans based on reproductive seasons of target species, or specific bans in key areas, for specific goals such as to promote species recovery and conservation. Restrictive hunting regulations, with no or insufficient options/alternatives for species use, are generally not effective in protecting species in the long-term, especially when areas or islands are very remote and more so when the state has weak enforcement capacity (Table 6.7). In these cases, hunting is often *de facto* open access, as evidenced by case studies from Brazil (Antunes *et al.*, 2019), Congo (Smith *et al.*, 2019a) and Tanzania (Haule *et al.*, 2002). Without regulation, overhunting and wild population declines have been the common outcome. There is strong evidence that total bans can negatively affect species conservation (Dickman *et al.*, 2019) and that in turn they tend to generate conflict in local communities, leading to reduced interests in species conservation, increasing resistance and undermining the voluntary participation of residents in conservation efforts (Strong *et al.* 2020). Restrictive regulations can however be an effective policy when they are used in the transition to a new arrangement for human livelihoods and the sustainability of wild species use, as shown in a case from Brazil (Freitas *et al.*, 2020).

Thus, restrictive hunting regulations can be effective at supporting sustainable use (i.e., through species recovery) when used in the transition to a new arrangement such as while conducting population studies for the establishment of limit harvesting (trade) quotas (e.g., in the case study of bighorn sheep in Mexico (Box 6.9)). Within the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species and its significant trade review process, it is a very common practice that the parties subject to this review adopt voluntarily bans, while they have enough elements to establish a limit catch or take quota). In other cases, bans are established temporarily while populations recover, and later on, sustainable harvest limits are set.

6.5.2.3 Broader policies to support sustainable use

High level policies, such as in education and development, that align with targeted sustainable use policies such as those related to land tenure and resource access rights can create enabling conditions for the sustainable use of wild species. In contrast, when these policies do not attend to sustainable use, they can inadvertently exacerbate the drivers of unsustainable use (Chapter 4).

Fishing is inherently a complex system with many moving and interacting parts that rarely operate in isolation. Often,

Box 6.9 Transitional policies can pave the way for longer term policies: Bighorn sheep (*Ovis canadensis*) trophy hunting in Mexico.

Sustainable trophy hunting of Bighorn sheep, mostly managed by indigenous peoples and local communities, is generating community well-being and leading the population's recovery and habitat protection in Mexico. During the 19th century and up to the mid-20th century, Bighorn sheep was extirpated from Northeast Mexico, and the population decreased significantly in the Northwest and the Baja peninsula (Sandoval *et al.*, 2014; Valdés Alarcón & Segundo Galán, 2007). In 1975, 45 Bighorn sheep were reintroduced in Isla Tiburón (Sonora, Mexico); which turned into 1,500 individuals by 2020 and served as nursery for repopulation purposes and hunting activities (Sonora, 2012; Valdés Alarcón & Segundo Galán, 2007). Bighorn sheep in Mexico can only be harvested in management units for the conservation of wildlife (UMA), which guarantee that habitat conditions continue to be favorable for the species and to ensure that hunting activities will be self-sustaining in the long term. More than half of the 60 management units for the conservation of wildlife of wild Bighorn sheep in Mexico are managed by rural dwellers (in "ejidos" – communal land), and some by indigenous peoples. Population monitoring and harvest rate estimations are based on aerial surveys funded by Government and stakeholders (communities). Once a Bighorn sheep is hunted, the meat is consumed in the site or left to the community, while the carcass (skull, horns and sometimes skin) is taken by the hunter (Félix, 2006). Only Mexico's populations are included in the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora Appendix II, and hunting trophies are offered in international auctions with prices up to 40,000 United States dollars per trophy, being the main drivers of international trade (CONABIO, 2021a). Each year legal harvest rates (10-20% of oldest males) of Bighorn sheep in Mexico are based on the best scientific

information available, approved by the General Directorate for Wildlife (DGVS-SEMARNAT), which is also the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora Management Authority, and reviewed by CONABIO, the "Comisión Nacional para el Conocimiento y Uso de la Biodiversidad" (CONABIO, 2021a). Hunting was suspended in the whole country (i.e., temporarily banned) in 1993 because of lack of reliable information on the population numbers, and re-opened in 1995 for some states once aerial surveys were conducted (Mosig, Muñoz-Lacy, *et al.*, 2019). There is a high revenue per trophy. Seri's communities traditionally have hunted Bighorn sheep populations, and a trust fund was constituted to compile earnings and share their benefits, which are distributed among stakeholders, with economic and social impacts; either directly (earnings) or indirectly (temporary jobs, scholarships, investment in infrastructure, etc.) (R. Lee, 2008; Luque & Doode, 2007). The Management Units for the Conservation of Wildlife framework maintains ecosystem benefits for the species and its habitat, and is key for the maintenance of corridors (Sanchez, 2006). There is some level of co-management in the system, as stakeholders are involved in monitoring the species (CONABIO, 2021a).

With a legal framework of National and International regulations, hunting in management units for the conservation of wildlife has helped maintain the species stability and its habitat connectivity for the last 20 years. This scheme of legal and sustainable use, with fair distribution of benefits throughout the trade chain and with investment in the conservation of Bighorn Sheep and its habitat, is already an example of best practice in terms of sustainable use and conservation of wild species in Mexico.

Photos: Bighorn sheep (*Ovis Canadensis*). © Carlos Javier Navarro Serment / CONABIO CC-BY.

multiple different stakeholder groups interact with each other, relying upon the exploitation of numerous species. These species are subsequently traded along supply chains of varying lengths, often to several final destinations. When

evaluating the sustainability of fishing and mechanisms to improve it, it is important to look for answers both within and beyond fishing policy. The inter-connected nature of fishing systems means that they are influenced both by fishing-

related policies but also by non-fishing-related policies. For example, the fishing activity of an isolated community who rely on the small local markets and lack of access to the larger and more populous markets may be impacted by a policy that changes national road infrastructure. While the intent of that policy may be to improve road transport and connectivity, there are likely secondary impacts for the fishing community that may subsequently gain access to better markets with better prices, or result in the exploitation of fish stocks (Cinner *et al.*, 2016). In theory this could lead to a reduction in fishing effort because the same pre-policy revenues can be maintained with less fishing effort overall. Conversely, better markets with better prices could lead to increased fishing effort. The exact outcome in such scenarios would likely depend on the size of the market, stewardship of the community towards the fishing resources upon which they rely, the status of those resources, and the ability of the resources to support increased levels of fishing pressure. This illustrative example is just one of many that highlight the potential of non-fishing related policy to impact the sustainability of fishing both positively and negatively.

The complexity of social-ecological systems and the interrelatedness of their components are increasingly recognized (Young *et al.*, 2006) particularly in terms of fishing sustainability (McClanahan *et al.*, 2009). The impacts of policies from one sector/part of society on other sectors/parts are, however, seldom recognized and/ or evaluated. Some progress has been made within the telecoupling literature in terms of highlighting the interconnectedness of systems across geographical scales (Lewison *et al.*, 2019; Liu *et al.*, 2013), including for fisheries (Carlson *et al.*, 2017, 2018); however, studies that link various policies specifically within and across distant systems are rare (though policy is identified as an important factor affecting telecoupling of systems: (Hull & Liu, 2018). The following illustrates some examples that specifically link non-fisheries policy to measurable impacts (positive or negative) on fisheries sustainability.

Freshwater fishing comprises 51% of the world's fish species, and approximately 30% of total landings. Freshwater ecosystems face a devastating combination of threats driven by human activities not related to fishing – including habitat destruction, such as drainage, river regulations, hydropower dams, over-abstraction of water for irrigation, various types of pollution, the introduction of invasive species and ongoing climate change. As such, one third of freshwater fish species are threatened with extinction and the multi-faceted drivers of change in freshwater systems highlight the ease with which these systems and their fisheries can be impacted by policies that do not directly relate to the fisheries that they support.

The institutional water framework of most national and international entities does not effectively address cross-sectoral issues relating to freshwater use and integrated

management. The responsibilities for agriculture, water management, nature conservation, and inland fishing are often separated over multiple agencies (Cowx, 1998 as cited in (Cooke *et al.*, 2016). As a result, today a growing number of rivers run dry along part of their course for all or part of the year, including the Colorado (United States of America and Mexico) and the Huanghe River (China). While use of river water driven by non-fishing policy has brought enormous benefits to drinking water supplies, agriculture, and the hydro-electric industry, in many cases such policies have also brought costs. This is particularly so for freshwater fish populations. Over thirty-five years ago, Welcomme (1985) examined the relationship between river flow and fish production in Africa and illustrated it is possible to predict catches in river systems from regression analyses of the past performance of the fishing against discharge. Within decreased river flow comes decrease fish production, and the same is observed in natural lakes and reservoirs (Gownaris *et al.*, 2018; Kolding & van Zwieten, 2012). The positive correlation between river flow and fish production is also mirrored in coastal fisheries many of which benefit from high estuarine discharge, impacting both commercial and recreational fishing sectors (Loneragan, 1999). For this reason, Dugan *et al.* (2006) note the benefits of integrating water requirements for fish into water allocation decisions which very commonly do not account for impacts on freshwater fish stocks.

Governments aiming to meet broad economic objectives such as high employment, sustainable growth in industry and price stability often look towards economic development policy. This can encompass a suite of tools including fiscal policy, the regulation of trade, financial institutions, and taxes, and investment in infrastructure and services. The primary objective of these tools is largely economic growth. In many cases, this is often counter to the conservation of natural resources and biodiversity (Meng *et al.*, 2019). Economic growth generally constitutes a policy priority, whilst environmental protection often remains an ambitious goal and, in some cases, an unperceived need (Ferraro & Brans, 2012).

The commonly reported negative correlation between economic development and successful conservation, does not, however, always appear or need to be the case. Policy focused on the creation of jobs and/or alternative livelihoods can, in some cases, alleviate anthropogenic pressures on natural resource systems. In fisheries, the most linked alternative livelihood is that of aquaculture. Development policy that promotes growth in aquaculture sectors can, in some cases, reduce fishing pressures on wild fish stocks. For example, the trade of reef fish is known to be a significant threat in both marine and freshwater systems (Moreau & Coomes, 2007; Nañola *et al.*, 2011; Pomeroy, Parks, *et al.*, 2006) but the promotion of local aquaculture and aquarium practices to rear target species

has been shown to lessen pressure on coral reef systems (Pomeroy, Parks, *et al.*, 2006; Pouil *et al.*, 2020). Similarly, policies that promote dive tourism, in many cases have shown significant positive impacts both in terms of reduced pressure on wild stocks and increased total revenues for fishing communities that have switched livelihoods either full or part-time (Lowe *et al.*, 2019). In Mexico the recreational diving industry generates between 455-725 million United States dollars per year, whilst the wild capture fisheries sector that generates 700 million United States dollars (Arcos-Aguilar *et al.*, 2021). Direct comparisons of such total revenues are, however, crude because they do not account for total livelihoods, employment numbers and individual full time equivalent values, and therefore require more in-depth case-specific understanding.

Development policy that is designed to promote growth in non-fishing-related sectors is advised to account for the profitability and feasibility of the transition to any alternative livelihoods available. Without the correct economic incentives, particularly in developing contexts, such policies are often unable to successfully complete the transition to alternative livelihoods rendering them unsustainable and, in some cases, practically futile (Pham, 2020; Pomeroy, Ratner, *et al.*, 2006). Now, with an increased drive from the blue economy, the so-called blue revolution, it is important that such issues are considered. Although aquaculture or tourism policy has the potential to alleviate pressure from wild capture fisheries, without holistic approaches that account for more than just the theoretical economic gains and transfer of worker effort, the success of such policies over the long-term will likely remain limited. It should also be remembered that both aquaculture and tourism are economic activities that are heavily dependent on, and therefore vulnerable to, changing demand drivers outside the control of the local initiatives.

Whilst it is commonplace to assume practical answers to fishing-related problems will come directly from the fishing sector in the form of fishing tools, management and policy, the analysis of how non-fishing-related policy can and does impact the sustainability of fishing requires more attention. More concerted cross-sectoral awareness should also help mitigate the risk of policy implementation that benefits policy outcomes unrelated to fishing to the detriment of sustainable fishing. Considering the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals interrelated framework (Singh *et al.*, 2018), it is surprising that more work has not been undertaken to formally analyze links between non-fisheries policy and fisheries. Combining efforts across sectors with the above ideas in mind will likely facilitate meeting more of the Sustainable Development Goals' targets. Moving away from single stroke policy efforts focused only on single targets will require considerable collaboration between traditionally unrelated sectors both in industry and in policy.

6.5.3 Rules and institutions that can constrain sustainable use

6.5.3.1 Overlooking available breadth of policy options

Across case studies from all practices most successful sustainable use outcomes involved a mix of policy instruments, highlighting the need for complementary and synergistic strategies in order to regulate and incentivize good practices. Although, across all practices, the use of legal and regulatory approaches dominates (see section 6.4.5, **Table 6.6**). Most successful cases in gathering exercised a mix of legal and regulatory policies along with social and rights-based instruments.

The main constraining condition in terrestrial animal harvesting highlighted through the case studies, and also reflected in the fishing case studies, was the focus of policies on a limited number of high value species or commercialized products. This focus led to policies that overlooked the diversity of species harvested and products commercialized. Indeed, five out of the six most successful cases in terrestrial animal harvesting involved reptile and big mammal species with a high demand in the international market and with a high revenue per harvested specimen. In contrast, for the remaining cases, the resource was highly abundant and the main market was national, with less lucrative economic returns. This strong connection between the market and policy, whereby the market determines the success of the policy creates a vulnerability, as if there are any changes in the patterns of international/national demand (fashion industries, changes in wild species use or food consumption habits, etc.), the income received by the communities, and therefore their welfare, could be at risk. Similarly, if prices are to shift, the stability of the harvest could vary. For example, if prices drop, there could be an increase in the harvest volume in order to maintain the same level of income.

The focus of hunting policies on a limited number of high value species also plays out in fisheries to limit the approaches considered available, resulting in an overemphasis on legal and regulatory instruments (**Box 6.10**). Fisheries management approaches are heavily influenced by the data selected and available to guide assessments and as well as what is considered the bounds of the system of interest. Conventional fisheries management, which has predominantly emerged from evaluations of industrial fisheries from temperate regions of the Global North (Kolding & van Zwieten, 2011), has tended to focus on single species stock status assessments. Such industrial fishing is often (intentionally) highly size selective, yet it is increasingly acknowledged that this can lead to changes in body size, reproductive size, (which both negatively impact recruitment) and evolutionary effects (S. M. Garcia *et al.*, 2012; Jørgensen *et al.*, 2007). Possible

management interventions include reducing harvest rates and selectivity (which only exacerbates the problem); refuges and protected areas; integrating trait-changes into management (Palkovacs *et al.*, 2018).

More recently, a number of alternative approaches and assessments have emerged, from a diversity of contexts, that emphasize broader changes in ecosystem structure. For example, balanced harvesting has been proposed as an alternative which would counteract both phenotypic and genetic consequences of fishing, as well as increasing overall yields (**Box 6.10**). However, this approach has been mainly applied in theoretical studies or observed in small-scale inland fisheries, and no examples exist from large-scale fishing, except the overall findings that they are significantly unbalanced (Kolding, Bundy, *et al.*, 2016) (**Figure 6.6**). One example seeking to illustrate the complexity of this endeavor in the industrialized Barents Sea fishery concluded the theory is great but in practice may be more challenging due to economic preferences and may require a pragmatic approach to implement only the most feasible aspects (Howell *et al.*, 2016; Zhou *et al.*, 2019). For less selective small-scale fisheries more aimed for maximizing food production, a balanced fishing pattern is feasible and can evolve organically (**Box 6.10**).

A global assessment of fishing patterns and fishing pressure from 110 different Ecopath models, representing marine ecosystems throughout the world and covering the period 1970–2007, showed that human exploitation across trophic levels is highly unbalanced and skewed towards low productive species at high trophic levels, which are around

two trophic levels higher than the animal protein received from terrestrial farming (**Figure 6.6**) (Kolding, Bundy *et al.*, 2016). In contrast, exploitation levels from low trophic species represent <15% of total catches, while only 18% of the total number of exploited groups and species were technically overharvested (annual catches exceed >40% of the total annual production) (Pikitch *et al.*, 2012).

This work also compared temperate *versus* tropical fisheries, and found no difference in overall fishing pressure. However, while fishing pressure in temperate fisheries increased with trophic level, in tropical fisheries fishing pressure generally decreased at the highest trophic level, indicating a tendency to fish lower in the food web, where production, or species turnover, is also higher. These data further suggest that tropical fisheries, overall, are slightly more balanced (Garcia *et al.*, 2012) than temperate and that there is less evidence of general overfishing in the global South.

Another factor in the least successful terrestrial animal harvesting cases that has limited success in some cases is the lack of robust information (either traditional ecological knowledge or scientific knowledge) and of population and ecosystem monitoring. This is in part because terrestrial animal harvesting case studies tended to focus on harvested species, and as a result their effect on the habitat is not always taken into consideration, and much less their impact on broader nature's contributions to people, which is not considered in any of the evaluated case studies. The consideration of these three aspects could help gain a better and more integral understanding of ecological relationships and on how the policy instruments impact them.

Box 6.10 **Balanced harvest in Lake Kariba.**

Conventional fisheries management has been predominantly informed by fishing patterns in industrialized fisheries from the global north. These approaches, developed for single species fisheries that target high trophic level species that tend not to be very productive, focus on controlling inputs (e.g., effort) or outputs (e.g., total allowed catch or size of species) associated with the use of highly specialized and selective gears. The diversity of contexts in which fishing occurs has resulted in many instances in which conventional fisheries management has failed. As a result, alternate paradigms have emerged that question conventional logic and propose alternate approaches to fisheries management and governance. The contrast between conventional and alternate fisheries management paradigms have played out in Lake Kariba.

Lake Kariba, is a human-made lake on the Zambezi River in Southern Africa. The fisheries of Zambia and Zimbabwe, on opposite sides of the lake, have been subject to different types of management regimes. This situation creates a grand-scale

ecological laboratory that can be used to study the impacts of exploitation. It offers a unique test of a well-managed system, in the conventional sense, against an open access “laissez faire” situation, which is conventionally believed to result in collapse and the tragedy of the commons (Kolding & van Zwieten, 2011).

Long-term data (1960–2000) collected from both sides of the lake have shown the unmanaged system in Zambia to evolve into one reflecting a ‘balanced harvest’ approach where all species and sizes are harvested in proportion to their productivity (S. M. Garcia *et al.*, 2012). The Zambian inshore fishery, with open access and no enforcement of regulations, has gradually experienced a much higher fishing intensity and a changed fishing pattern towards increasingly smaller mesh sizes resulting in a higher exploitation level and reduced stock sizes. However, the yields, per unit area, are 6 times higher, than in Zimbabwe while the ecological impacts in terms of demographic structure and relative species abundances are minimized (Kolding, Jacobsen, *et al.*, 2016).

Box 6 10

In contrast, the Zimbabwean side, where conventional tools of management regulations, controlling effort and enforcing minimum mesh limitations, have been implemented, have resulted in fishing pressures and fishing patterns, that while fluctuating due to environmental variation, have not changed much over time (Kolding & van Zwieten, 2012). The overall fishing effort, in terms of number of nets, is about seven times higher in Zambia than in Zimbabwe. However, the average artisanal catch rates are more similar (1.8 and 2.8 kilograms per net in Zambia and Zimbabwe respectively) and this is because the Zambian fishers are using small mesh sizes on average.

Thus, by ignoring mesh size regulations, the Zambian fishery appears to produce a high sustainable yield, in accordance with the United Nations Convention on the Law of the

Sea (1982), while maintaining the relative fish community structure, in accordance with the Convention on Biological Diversity (1992). These positive counter-intuitive results of non-compliance evolve by a rational individual response to the open access regime. When effort grows in the open access Zambia fishery, and catches per unit effort decreases (Figure 6.7 B), it is a logical and necessary reaction of individual fishers to gradually decrease some of their mesh sizes (Figure 6.7 C) to maintain an acceptable catch rate. The range of mesh sizes and their relative abundance will eventually be proportional to their individual catch rates, which becomes an ideal free distribution (Plank *et al.*, 2017) (Figure 6.7 D), where all species and sizes are harvest in accordance to their productivity and thus maintains the overall size-structure of the fished fish community compared to an unfished situation (Figure 6.7).

Figure 6 7 The inshore fishery in Lake Kariba.

(A) Catch rates in the regulated Zimbabwean fishery. (B) Catch rates in the open access Zambian fishery. (C) Average mesh sizes in the Zambian fishery between 1960 and 1999. As capture per unit of effort decreases with time, so does the mesh sizes. (D) Relationship between relative number of nets (mesh range 76-178 mm) and relative capture per unit of effort per mesh size in the Zambian fishery. The strong relationship indicates an ideal free distribution where the fishing pattern is proportional to productivity, which results in balanced harvest (Figure 6.8). (A) and (B) from (Kolding, Jacobsen, *et al.*, 2016) under license CC BY 4.0, See data management report for the figure at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6453483>

6.5.3.2 Overlooking social context

The most successful cases are those that monitor and consider all sustainability domains (social, economic, and ecological) and that implement adaptive management based on these considerations. However, in many instances social dimensions of sustainable use are often overlooked. Of the five most successful terrestrial animal harvesting case studies, ecological outcomes have tended to be a focus; however, these cases have also managed to focus on social outcomes. In contrast, the least successful cases are characterized by a lack of balance between the three domains of sustainable use (economic, ecological

and social). For these cases, one of the domains is typically favored over the others, which has proven to be inefficient. In such cases, public policies can even become counterproductive and lack proper implementation, which discourages sustainable use. A clear example of this situation is that the only case with good economic outcomes does not consider the social dimensions of the activities carried out.

Reflecting these patterns and drawing on the 84 case studies examples from the chapter's adapted systematic review, examples of effective sustainable use policy most

often reflect economic or ecological success, and were most likely to reflect social losses (Table 6.8). For example, total Allowable Catch (TAC) and Individual Transferal Quota's (ITQ) that limit overfishing, result in improvements to stock status and economic efficiency (Donkersloot & Carothers, 2017; Edwards & Pinkerton, 2019a, 2019b; Kroetz *et al.*, 2015; Pinkerton & Edwards, 2009). Reviews of fisheries status and performance of conventional fisheries management have a similar focus on ecological effects over economic and social effects, with economic factors often playing a stronger role (Hilborn *et al.*, 2020; Melnychuk *et al.*, 2021).

The most common negative outcomes were found in the gathering cases which appeared across all sustainability domains (social, economic, ecological) (Table 6.8). This is in part, because legal and regulatory instruments were found to be most commonly applied to high value species within gathering, where these policies are vulnerable to market fluctuations and thus tend to be less effective than other options. In several cases of gathering, overharvesting was not controlled by national regulations, such as penalty and permit schemes, and resulted in a loss of species and habitat degradation (Chatterjee *et al.*, 2011; Wallrapp *et al.*, 2019). Excessive harvest of wild plants can lead to a decline of resources such as lichen (Chatterjee *et al.*, 2011; Gokhale & Negi, 2011). In contrast, the logging cases reflected a higher proportion of cases with both positive and negative outcomes than other practices, suggesting logging cases simultaneously exhibit successful and unsuccessful outcomes within a sustainability domain, associated with

the adopted policy instruments, such as Forest Stewardship Council certifications.

The most commonly ineffective terrestrial animal harvesting policies (the majority of least successful case studies) involved prohibitions (e.g., bans) on the use of wild species imposed unilaterally by government authorities (hierarchical government context). These referred to specific prohibitions not related to those implied in some natural protected areas where harvesting is frequently prohibited, but which have proven to be successful conservation instruments. This is likely compounded by the fact monitoring seems to be stronger when there are government authorities involved. However, the ecological domain is usually the one more closely monitored (particularly the hunted species' population status); as opposed to the social and economic domains which are not always fully evaluated.

6.5.3.3 Overlooking customary practices, rights & indigenous and local knowledge

Even where there are clear statutory provisions, lack of knowledge or enforcement of tenure laws, or poor governance in general, can leave people vulnerable to violations of their rights (Springer & Campese, 2011). For example, in Bolivia, small-scale gathering producers maintained strong *de facto* control over the resource base for decades through a customary system of tree tenure. Access rights were based on rubber trails and later, when Brazil nuts became important, on access to Brazil nut

Table 6.8 Policy effectiveness of economic, ecological and social sustainability (N=84).

The darkness of color represents relative strength of positive or negative outcomes within each practice judges against. The color has three levels. Hatched cells mean that the practice has over 15% of the cases of both positive and negative effectiveness. The relative distribution of positive and negative effectiveness was divided into trisection with color darkness. The value of positive effectiveness has three ranges; over 75% (dark green), between 75% and 57% (green), under 57% (light green). The value of negative effectiveness has three ranges; over 25% (dark red), between 25% and 8% (red), under 8% (light red). See the data management report at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4663236>.

Practice	Economic sustainability		Ecological sustainability		Social sustainability	
	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
Fishing	Green	Light Red	Green	Light Red	Light Green	Light Red
Gathering	Green	Dark Red	Light Green	Dark Red	Green	Light Red
Terrestrial animal harvesting	Light Green	Dark Red	Green	Light Red	Hatched Green	Hatched Light Red
Non-extractive practices	Green	Light Red	Hatched Green	Hatched Light Red	Light Green	Light Red
Logging	Hatched Green	Hatched Light Red	Hatched Green	Hatched Light Red	Hatched Green	Hatched Light Red

trees (*Bertholletia excelsa*) and related infrastructure. All these activities operated in the absence of statutory policy. However, in 1996 the Brazilian government introduced an Agrarian Reform Law that superimposed a new layer of rights over the region's forests by allocating logging concessions which led to conflict. Conflicts were further exacerbated when well-intentioned efforts to modify the 1996 Agrarian reform law to expand the size of land grants to more communities further undermined customary tree tenure arrangements. Land reform gave smallholders formal recognition of their tenure rights, but by basing it on control of contiguous territory (allocating each family 500 ha), it undermined the effective traditional tenure arrangements and access rights based on key resources (once rubber, and now Brazil nut trees) (Cronkleton & Pacheco, 2010; Stoian, 2005).

Traditional resource management systems can thus enable greater community participation. However, in many instances these customary systems have been bypassed resulting in sustained conflicts with communities (McClanahan *et al.*, 2005). For fishing in coastal Kenya is partly regulated by a largely successful network of marine protected areas, with the exception of one park that remains a paper park. This failure was largely due to a lack of communication and collaboration between resource users, managers, customary and statutory systems of governance. The failure to engage with local actors, recognize, and respect the local customary context became the cause of mistrust, leading to serious conflict, violence, and slow implementation of management (McClanahan *et al.*, 2005).

The challenge of developing environmental outcomes acceptable to stakeholders with different values is required as it affects decision making. A turtle and dugong hunting management plan was developed by the Hope Vale aboriginal community in the great barrier reef world heritage area, Australia. The discourses of the environmental managers and community members were very different. Hope Vale's primary discourse was based on the assertion of the superiority of "traditional" cultural knowledge over western science, while the management agency discourse was based on the presumed superiority of the scientific discourse. This imbalance reflects inequity within both the power and knowledge arenas. Hope Vale people prioritized cultural well-being; the staff of management agencies prioritized biodiversity outcomes. Hope Vale participants conceived traditional hunting as the apex of their contemporary expression of traditional culture because a hunt is the physical manifestation of a cultural right and an ancient tradition.

The importance of the practice was not diminished by the realities that: (i) hunters may not now need the meat to survive; (ii) green turtles and dugongs might not be found and caught; and (iii) some cultural methods and

cultural weapons have changed or are no longer used. Thus, hunting culture is about relationships with country, place, clan estates, and the associated responsibilities that those relationships bring: a palimpsest of the indigenous knowledge domain as exemplified by the following quote: "Traditional Hunting? Well, it's us. It's our culture. It's who we are. Well, it is just in the blood I suppose. It is like, like it is carried on from the Elders and like we grew up, the Elders showed us and we know the skills now we show our nephews, our sons, and our daughters, show them those skills. We got to keep all them things alive, no matter what techniques we use, it's still our traditional culture today" (Nursey-Bray *et al.*, 2010).

These differences precluded effective outcomes despite considerable investment in hunting management over more than 20 years by both groups. Understanding the discursive terrain within environmental management domains can inform environmental decision making and the implementation of agreed management arrangements, enabling biodiversity objectives and indigenous cultural aspirations to be met in a socially just, economically viable, and environmentally sustainable way (Nursey-Bray *et al.*, 2010).

Unimplemented policy measures can be worse than no measures. In some cases, they weaken traditional structures that might better promote sustainable management or equity in trade; even cursory government regulation of wild algae, plants and fungi can undermine community institutions and control over resources (Arnold & Pérez, 2001; Michon, 2005). Confusion, conflict and corruption can also result when laws are unclear or unenforced, making the lives of producers, harvesters, and traders more difficult and encouraging unsustainable harvests of species (Arquiza *et al.*, 2010; Laird *et al.*, 2010; Ndoye & Awono, 2010).

Within the gathering cases reviewed, co-operation and sharing of rights and responsibilities emerged as key enabling conditions. Effectiveness was particularly noted among the community led organizations and government authorities that followed institutionally-mixed resource governance systems and where there was multi-level interaction as well as shared responsibilities and rights among different institutions and actors.

Successful examples of gathering case studies involved the integration of biodiversity conservation into livelihood development, recognized both indigenous knowledge and scientific knowledge, and brought together natural sciences with social sciences for better outputs. Integration of ecological and socioeconomic factors and different knowledge systems provided effective solutions. In one case study on wild mushrooms (Yunnan, China) the promise of economic and ecological benefits motivated the provincial government to scale up the adoption of appropriate

technologies and catalyzed their willingness to further invest in participatory action research.

Awareness of the relationship between human rights, conservation, and the rights of indigenous peoples and local communities has grown. This growth has also brought increased scrutiny of the impacts that protected areas can have on rural communities – such as evictions and lost access to natural resources (Roe, 2010). Increasingly, it is understood that conservation and a quality environment are fundamental to realizing human rights – particularly where indigenous peoples' and local communities' livelihoods and wellbeing depend on ecosystem goods and services. It is generally recognized that conservation approaches are strengthened by adopting principles and standards related to human rights and mechanisms to monitor and enforce adherence to them (Järv *et al.*, 2021). The benefits of integrating human rights concern into conservation practice include improved security for local and indigenous communities, as well as more effective and sustainable conservation.

Building robust opportunities for indigenous peoples and local communities to be heard and to exercise their rights at all levels is critical in promoting more effective and equitable strategies of wild species conservation. Rights of indigenous peoples are often particularly relevant for conservation and sustainable use of natural resources, due to the frequent overlap of high-biodiversity areas and indigenous lands, and the vulnerability of natural resource-dependent customary livelihoods to changes in access or use. Indigenous peoples' traditional ecological knowledge, traditional systems of control, use and management of lands and resources, and traditional institutions for self-governance also contribute to conservation substantially (Box 6.11).

In the successful terrestrial hunting cases, the main enabling condition was that resource use is implemented as part of the indigenous peoples and local communities' culture (i.e., respect to local culture) and is based on traditional ecological knowledge. In these cases, indigenous peoples and local communities are organized around the use of the resource, and national and international regulations have acted as levers to reinforce good practices of local management. The resource under use has a healthy population level and, based on traditional ecological knowledge and scientific information, use has not been detrimental. One factor that has boosted the continuation of the long-term use in the most successful cases is a multi-stakeholder approach around the process (indigenous peoples and local communities, non-governmental organizations, government, hunters, etc.).

Indeed, there is ample evidence of a link between taboos and sacrifices and resource scarcity of ritual plants. In Benin (West Africa), the use of 63 of the 414 ritual plant species was restricted; while in Gabon (Central Africa), 23 of the 256 ritual plants were associated with taboos and sacrifices. In Benin, restricted plants were significantly more often officially threatened, perceived as scarce, and actively protected than non-restricted plants. In the more forested and less densely populated Gabon, plants that were perceived as scarce were more often associated to local restrictions than officially threatened species (Quiroz & van Andel, 2015).

Colding and Folke (1997) analyzed the role of taboos for the protection of species listed as "threatened" by the International Union for Conservation of Nature, and also for keystone and endemic species. The study was limited to specific-species taboos that totally avoid or prohibit any use of particular species and their populations. It was found

Box 6.11 Aspects of indigenous rights especially relevant in conservation contexts.

Source: (Springer & Campese, 2011) under license CC-BY.

- Rights to traditional lands, territories and resources – including the "right to the conservation and protection of the environment and the productive capacity of their lands or territories and resources."
- Rights to self-determination and to free, prior, and informed consent – Self-determination is a collective right reflecting indigenous peoples' status as distinct peoples. United Nations declaration on the rights of indigenous peoples establishes (Article 19) that "States shall consult and cooperate in good faith with the indigenous peoples concerned through their own representative institutions in order to obtain their free, prior and informed consent before adopting and implementing legislative or administrative measures that may affect them."
- Rights to control and management of lands and resources – through customary institutions and laws.
- Rights to development and equitable benefit-sharing – including to determine the development or use priorities and strategies on their lands, territories and resources and to benefit equitably from conservation and sustainable use of such areas and resources.
- Rights to traditional knowledge and indigenous heritage – redress United Nations declaration on the rights of indigenous peoples includes provision for redress for deprivation of indigenous peoples' means of subsistence and development, and for lands taken without free, prior, informed consent.

that around 30% of the identified taboos prohibit any use of species listed as threatened by the International Union for Conservation of Nature. Of the specific-species taboos, 60% are set on reptiles and mammals. In these two classes, around 50% of the species are threatened. Both endemic and keystone species that are important for ecosystem functions are avoided by specific-species taboos. Specific-species taboos have important ecological ramifications for the protection of threatened and ecologically important populations of species.

Similarly, in the dry forest of southern Madagascar, a region of global conservation priority, the continued existence of unique forest habitats in the Androy region is directly dependent on informal institutions, taboos, which regulate human behavior and ensure the continued existence of the forest patches and their associated biodiversity. For example, in southern Androy, 90% of the total remaining forest cover is protected through taboos; these informal institutions represent an important, and presently the only, mechanism for conservation of the highly endemic forest species. The social organization of rural Madagascar is a blend of the fanjakana, the formal institutions of Malagasy society, and the fokolonana, traditions and customs such as the clan leadership structure and taboos. The taboo or faly, meaning forbidden or “you shall not”, is a component of the laws inherited from the ancestors. Respect and reverence for the ancestors and other spirits requires the Tandroy to follow the prohibitions of the faly. In southern Androy, analyses were made of taboo forests with strict restriction for human access and use, ala kibory; taboo forests with some restrictions on human use, salata; and public forests with few restrictions on human access and use (Tengö *et al.*, 2007).

The failure to recognize historical rights and practices of gathering wild species as an important livelihood in legal and regulatory policies widens the gap between community and government bodies within gathering case studies reviewed. Similarly, building on or complementing traditional resource rights in gathering wild species was an important approach to minimize paperwork, avoid duplication of existing laws and enhance sustainable use. This requires real commitments of time, money, research, and extensive stakeholder consultation.

The combination of scientific and customary knowledge can be particularly powerful. In rights-based instruments, community-based management is significant in all practices where diverse forms of knowledge are integrated. For example, in the gathering case study in China (J. He *et al.*, 2011), villagers used scientific data to formulate mushroom management practices to obtain the best production including sustainable harvesting. Tilling and debranching was conducted to reduce canopy density to 0.6 (canopy density is dense between 0.7 and 1.0). The litter depth was managed through adding or removing the litter to reach

2 to 4 cm. Farmers took information as critical criteria for targeting the areas where intensive management should be applied. In targeted areas, most of the households invested in installing a field guardhouse to stay overnight during the mushroom season to monitor the mushrooms. The improved harvesting technique has enabled better quality and higher quantity of mushroom gathering.

6.5.4 Power dynamics can impede sustainable use

6.5.4.1 Power imbalance

Bureaucratic hierarchy, power dynamics, conflicts and struggles between formal and informal governance arrangements are common in practices involving the use of wild species. Therefore, understanding the power dynamics and the alignment of objectives between stakeholders prior to policy formulation and implementation is likely to enhance the effectiveness of policies. However, understanding the influence of power requires comprehending a vast array of factors, from top-down state control, to the more dynamic and relational influences of economic value, ownership, and knowledge.

Power dynamics have a crucial influence for high value fish, plants, and fungi that have a significant international and national market demand. All actors (government, community, intermediaries and distant collectors) involved in using wild species have an interest in receiving benefits from high value wild species. An increase in market demand and price of wild species modifies access demands of all actors that in turn can trigger power struggles and conflicts. Gathering case studies found that policies that reduce monopolistic tendencies in wild plant and fungi markets are important but need to be implemented so that all stakeholders are supported along the value chain in a way that does not set them against each other. With shifts in corporate culture towards sustainability and equity there is increasing scope for reducing the length of value chains to alleviate state capacity constraints and improve producer income. Interventions that target gathering of wild species should thus not ignore malfunctioning market mechanisms and should implement other forms of assistance to complement certification, especially those that stabilize income sources to ensure sustainable use.

Policy action can result from both top-down processes, or through bottom-up processes made through customary systems of governance including contemporary cooperatives, such as is evident in the Baja California cooperatives (Mexico). In situations where the state has a strong say, even if along with a few other actors, acting to protect the State's interests or that of their allies, can result in other actors' interests being outweighed, ultimately

undermining the sustainable use of wild species. This has been found to be particularly problematic where a clientelist network has formed, wherein goods and services are exchanged for political support, and the government is unable to respond in an unbiased and pragmatic way (Box 6.12). The over dominance of the influence of the state can also be an issue for marginalized groups, such as indigenous communities and their rights. For example, indigenous communities including the Torres Strait islanders and the Sami were forced to take their governments to court to maintain their constitutional rights to fish (Lantto & Mörkenstam, 2008).

In instances where nations' national governance is weak, and the state has less power to start with – respective to other governance institutions, a power void may become filled in ways that undermine sustainable use. In general, effective and equitable co-management that empowers actors to participate on equal grounds can help equalize unequal power dynamics. For example, in the Amazonian case, local communities who successfully managed pirarucu acquired a greater sense of pride as their story became well known and spread (Box 6.5). Similarly, where a legally pluralistic situation exists and customary rules are recognized, such as in the Madagascar fishing case (octopus fishing case study),

Box 6.12 Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) certification and state-dominated forestry – Belarus and Poland.

Belarus and Poland have the third and fourth largest areas of certified forest in Europe (FSC, 2021) but their experiences with implementing the Forest Stewardship Council process differ considerably. Belarus' implementation was smooth whereas Poland's mired in conflict, ultimately resulting in closing of the Forest Stewardship Council national office (Jabłoński, 2015). Both countries have strong, centralized governance structures, with forestry practices highly regulated and considerable capacity to sustainably manage the almost entirely state-owned forests. Both countries were interested in Forest Stewardship Council certification because of the improved access to international markets certification affords. Certification also made sense because of the scale of the operation and concentrated state forest management and ownership. Despite many structural similarities, the reaction of the governments differed due to different policy and historical contexts, resulting in vastly different outcomes.

In Belarus, the state was firmly in charge of forest policy and forest administration (Forest Europe, 2020), while non-governmental organizations were relatively weak and mostly ignored (Dawson *et al.*, 2021). The status quo was characteristic for bureaucratic policy networks with state domination, formal, hierarchical arrangements and mandated regulations. However, the government was also a sole owner of forests and had an economic stake in Forest Stewardship Council certification connected with large multi-national clients, potential increase in exports and price premiums. This motivated the government to organize conditions for a possibly frictionless implementation of the Forest Stewardship Council and left little room for power-play between foresters and conservationists. Public organizations did not appear to pressure non-states, and the actors involved (auditors, forest management units and non-governmental organizations) exhibited constructive interactions. Environmental non-governmental organizations were satisfied with the process and its outcomes, which strengthened their role as participants of decision-making processes and increased input legitimacy of the scheme. The facilitatory role of the state allowed for some adjustment of legal rules to the Forest Stewardship Council

principles. Additionally, past conservation conflicts in forests were addressed in line with conservationists' suggestions. Nevertheless, the legitimacy of the Forest Stewardship Council rests solely on the pragmatic support of the state and could easily collapse if the support is withdrawn. A genuine (i.e., not moderated by the state) actor interest and consensus would be needed for making the Forest Stewardship Council arrangements sustainable in a long-run (Niedzialkowski & Shkaruba, 2018).

In Poland, the policy network in forestry practice was similarly top-down and bureaucratic but it also displayed characteristics of a clientelist network, wherein goods and services are exchanged for political support, (e.g., between the public forest agency and state forest holding) and had a quasi-corporate status with considerable financial and organizational autonomy (Blicharska *et al.*, 2020). The state's forest policy was shaped by state forest holding, which also benefited from it enjoying a monopolist position in the internal market (Forest Europe, 2020), which suggests a mechanism of "agency capture". Still, on several occasions, including nature conservation conflicts and financial relations between the government and state forest holding, the interests of the government and state forest holding clashed. Existing formal rules, securing the privileged position of state forest holding and limiting impact of non-state actors, were brought up by foresters to undermine unwanted stipulations of the Forest Stewardship Council. The Polish government, unlike Belarusian, did not attempt to adjust those formal rules or to press State Forest holding to comply. Foresters protected their management paradigm and perceived conservationists as competitors over forest resources (Blicharska *et al.*, 2020). Apart from treating the Forest Stewardship Council as a market instrument, foresters also perceived it strategically – first as a way to dismiss non-governmental organizations' criticism, and later mainly as non-governmental organizations' attempt to undermine forest practices of State Forest holding and to strengthen negatively perceived preservation. Consequently, foresters accepted new rules only to the extent they did not change established assumptions and practices (Niedzialkowski & Shkaruba, 2018).

regional management can be formalized by government at a later date, resulting in the bottom-up implementation of policies and more successful outcomes. In this case, the local Vezo community in Madagascar were also more empowered – economically, and perhaps also in being ahead of the government regulations.

In contrast, ill thought through policies, in certain contexts, have been shown to create or exacerbate unequal power dynamics between actors, such as the cases of halibut

individual transferable quotas fishery (see **Box 6.6**) and the Lake Victoria Nile perch fishery (see **Box 6.15**). Individual transferable quotas were shown in the example of halibut fisheries (**Box 6.6**) to cause a more unequal distribution of benefits. These systems were found to remove power from the owner-operators who conducted fishing activities, but who were dwindling in numbers, in favor of patterns of investment that lease permits and contributes to the corporatization of the fishery and concentration of power in the hands of a few actors.

Box 6.13 **Uncertainty or lack of knowledge can undermine sustainable use: Atlantic bluefin tuna case study.**

Atlantic bluefin tuna has been sustainably exploited for two millennia by various traditional fisheries (Ravier & Fromentin, 2001). As for many other fish stocks worldwide, the development of modern and more industrial fisheries occurred after the Second World War in both the North Atlantic and the Mediterranean Sea and took the lead on the traditional fisheries (Mather *et al.*, 1995). The rise of the sashimi market during the 1980s generated a new and strong demand for fresh Atlantic bluefin tuna from Japan, resulting from an increasing domestic demand, but also from the overfishing of the southern bluefin tuna stock, which used to be the main source of fresh tuna for the Japanese market (Polacheck, 2002). Consequently, the value of Atlantic bluefin tuna increased and became, in the media, the fish that was worth its own weight in gold (as shown by the New Year auction of the Tsukiji fish market where a single bluefin tuna can be sold up to 3 million United States dollars).

The growing value of Atlantic bluefin tuna has led to a sharp increase in the fishing efficiency and capacity of various fleets as well as the entrance of new storage technologies and farming practices. This severe and uncontrolled overcapacity also due to deficient governance at both international and national levels generated a critical overexploitation of the resource and a severe problem of illegal catch (Fromentin & Powers, 2005). The management failure of Atlantic bluefin tuna at that time was partly due to the multilateral nature of the International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas (which is the regional fisheries organization that has in charge to monitor and manage tuna and tuna-like species of the Atlantic Ocean) and to a decision-making process based on consensus. Indeed, conflicts of interests between the numerous countries that fished Atlantic bluefin tuna impeded strong decision-making, especially to limit catches. Furthermore, as Atlantic bluefin tuna market was highly profitable, economic interests took precedence over conservation-based ones, which is an unfortunate but quite common situation (Aps *et al.*, 2007).

The International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas' scientific body had alerted the International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas management body about

critical Atlantic bluefin tuna stock status in the 1990s, but the scientific advice had little weight against fisheries lobbies, which were most influential at maintaining high catch levels. In particular, questioning the Atlantic bluefin tuna scientific advice through the issue of uncertainty has been commonly used by different lobbies that wished to push their own agendas. During the 2000s, the environmental non-governmental organizations became, however, more powerful and efficiently used communication tools to call the attention of the public to the poor stock status of Atlantic bluefin tuna (Fromentin *et al.*, 2014).

Following public interest, managers started to pay more attention to the scientific advice and implemented a first rebuilding plan in 2007, which was reinforced in the following years. The final Atlantic bluefin tuna rebuilding plan was ambitious, including the reduction of the fishing season for the main fleets, an increase in the minimum size, new tools to monitor and control fishing activities, a reduction of fishing capacity and of the annual quota (Fromentin *et al.*, 2014). It was also strictly enforced and rapidly led to the rebuilding of the Atlantic bluefin tuna population. Although the scientific advice is impaired by unquantified uncertainties, all of the latest scientific analyses clearly showed that Atlantic bluefin tuna is not overfished anymore and that the stock size is strongly increasing (ICCAT, 2017).

The Atlantic bluefin tuna case clearly shows that effective management of international fisheries that exploit highly valuable species that have been overexploited for decades is possible when there is strong political will. It also shows that uncertainty that is inherent to any scientific advice is also a source of misunderstanding (sometimes manipulation) between scientists and managers for whom uncertainty often means poor advice. Furthermore, these uncertainties can be weaponized by powerful political lobbies, whether intentionally or not, to advance a particular cause. Like in all scientific fields, fisheries scientists cannot provide certainties, but only probabilities and sometimes a consensual interpretation. More science is thus needed to deliver less uncertainty and better management recommendations (Mäntyniemi *et al.*, 2009), which is a pre-requisite to long-term sustainable use.

Indeed, when ownership changes so do power relations, altering system dynamics. For example, when The Nature Conservancy bought fishing licenses in the California United States of America case (Californian groundfish/ trawling) (Gleason *et al.*, 2013), this conservation non-governmental organization had a very different seat at the table than before when it was 'only' an activism voice. In addition, the fishery had already been worn down (and declared a 'disaster') making space for change and this may also have given more power to this new actor bringing in innovative ideas.

In addition to state and ownership power, knowledge can be weaponized for influence. Ecological knowledge applied and generated from a management framework is a significant condition for designing policy instruments for sustainable use of wild species. When the species' ecology is well understood, and management scenarios are taken into account, these make for relatively high predictability of species population dynamics and also predictability and reliability of the anticipated impacts of management action (Scott & Seigel, 1992; Webb, 2015). The Baja California (Mexico) fishing case study with its fairly sedentary or habitat-attached benthic species (abalone, lobster) strongly highlighted this factor (McCay, 2014). When, on the other hand, there is high uncertainty in the understanding of a stock dynamic, this can make for lots of room for interpretation as well as doubt about the (necessity for and) anticipated effects of particular management action. This uncertainty and doubt can also be weaponized by actors from both sides of the spectrum between prioritizing use and conservation. This was the case in the Atlantic bluefin tuna case study (Fromentin *et al.*, 2014) (see **Box 6.13**)

where first governments in the International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas were using scientific uncertainty to delay action for protection, and later, when the tuna rebuilding plan had shown successful effects, some non-governmental organizations used the same tactic to try to prevent increase in fishing quota again.

Gender, or rather locally prevailing patriarchal power dynamics were highlighted in, e.g., Madagascar (octopus fishing case study) as playing a role in maintaining women fishers in a less influential position with regards to influencing fishery decision making and exercising their human rights overall. One of the positive aspects of the Pacific halibut case study's individual transferable quotas transition was the government repatriating fishing rights to First Nations, thereby also empowering these communities.

6.5.4.2 Neglecting history

Understanding the historical context, and learning from the past, is critical to supporting effective sustainable use policies and avoiding conflict. For example, although a range of factors contributed to the relative success of how Norway handled the 1989 Northeast Arctic cod fishery crisis in comparison to how the The Northern cod fishery crisis was handled in Canada around the same time (1992). The fact that the Norwegian government was able to learn from the historical collapse of the Norwegian herring fishery in the late 1960s and early 1970s placed it in a better position to rapidly respond, furthermore it had developed though this history better conflict resolution mechanisms, had learnt the limits of the oceans, and there was a greater trust in science (**Box 6.14**).

Box 6.14 Crises and (lack of) transformation towards sustainability – The case of Atlantic cod.

Atlantic Cod, *Gadus Morhua*, is one of the most commercially important marine species on this planet, with 1.2 mil tons landed in 2018 (FAO, 2020). Atlantic cod comprises 27 different stocks, most of them having been fished for thousands of years. Only from the 1950s on, when offshore trawling was adopted widely, biomass levels declined and first signs of unsustainable use became visible (D. G. Webster, 2015). Even in light of growing awareness that persistent overexploitation may undermine the viability of the population and may trigger a fish stock collapse, transforming fisheries towards a regime of sustainability can be difficult in practice (Hilborn, 2007). Using the Northern cod fishery in Canada and Northeast Arctic cod in Norway as cases, we illustrate several key factors that play an important in facilitating or impeding sustainable use. First, even though fishing pressure is a key driver, it will always act in concert with various other drivers, such as climatic changes, which will determine the size of the fishing pressure that is sustainable (Hilborn & Litzinger, 2009; Winter *et al.*,

2020). Second, scientific evidence is usually incomplete and sometimes gives an incoherent picture of the state of the stock and which actions would be required to ensure sustainability (Finlayson, 1994). Building a solid knowledge base, rooted in fundamental science, and a clear separation of scientific advice from the policy process are important to facilitate sustainable utilization of fisheries resources (Winter & Hutchings, 2020). Third, notwithstanding how clear and complete the science advice may be, the policy process may be unresponsive, slow, or dysfunctional, each possibly making management responses avoided or delayed (C. J. Brown *et al.*, 2012; Scheffer *et al.*, 2003).

The Northern cod fishery in Canada is a widely cited example of a resource collapse due to unsustainable exploitation (Haedrich & Hamilton, 2000; R. A. Myers *et al.*, 1997; Rice, 2006). In 1992, when biomass levels were less than 1% of their historical peak, a moratorium was implemented. The

end of the cod fishery caused also economic and social hardship in the local communities. Until today, the stock has not fully recovered. What caused this unprecedented resource collapse and could it have been prevented? Going back in time, Northern cod was fished extensively by foreign fleets – mostly Portugal and Spain – well back into 1400's or earlier. Exploitation intensified from the 1950s when offshore trawling became the predominant practice. When the United Nations Convention of the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) was implemented and the national jurisdiction was extended from 12 to 200 miles in the late 1970s, the stock was already greatly depleted. Canada adopted a long-term recovery plan for the stock, which included an annual allowance of 90,000 tons for the inshore fishery taken off the top of each year's quota. Canada also built up an offshore fleet of trawlers, very much like the Europeans have used before. All went well for most of a decade. An increase in Catch per unit of effort (CPUE) even seemed to suggest a swifter recovery than was expected. However, in 1986 the catches of the inshore fishery failed dramatically, although the offshore fishery was doing fine – and also scientific surveys were continuing to show rebuilding of the stock. In the late 1980s, the inshore fishery generally deteriorated, and also surveys indicated that the rebuilding had ceased and decline was highly likely. In hindsight, climate change played a key role as a driver. Rising temperature, and particular melting of the Greenland glaciers and arctic ice led a strengthening of the cold intermediate layer of the Labrador current. As a result, the plateaus for most of the Grand Banks were covered in waters too cold for cod to enter more than briefly to feed on their key prey, capelin. Therefore, the cod did their spring migration inshore without being able to replenish their energy reserves. This led to higher natural mortality and lower weight at age, probably reinforced by fisheries-induced evolution, which may have led to higher predation by seals and also implied that more cod were taken per ton of quota. Individually, these different drivers may have been minor, but when added to the high fishing pressure, taken together the impact on the stock was no longer sustainable.

In hindsight, a much more drastic and early reduction in fishing pressure would have been required to prevent collapse. Why did this not happen? Back in the mid 1980s, fisheries science did not have tools to include oceanographic data directly in the population assessments and there was little consensus how to interpret the data at hand. There was high certainty the stock was declining, but high uncertainty about the speed and the causes of the decline, and if the decline might reverse as oceanographic conditions may change (Drinkwater, 2002; Hilborn & Litzinger, 2009; Hutchings & Myers, 1994; Hutchings & Rangeley, 2011; Myers *et al.*, 1996; Shelton *et al.*, 2006). In addition, the consultative advisory processes that involved all stakeholder groups was rather unconstructive, very much centered around blaming, rather than finding sustainable solutions. In the end, the combination of a scientific advisory body not fully understanding what was going on, and a dysfunctional political process under severe pressure, made the collapse inevitable. Quick and decisive action would have ameliorated the decline and made a rapid recovery more likely.

But facing advice filled with uncertainties from science and an inclusive consultative process that could find consensus on almost nothing, no politician was going to make quick and draconian decisions (Alverson, 1997; Finlayson, 1994; Harris, 1990; Hilborn, 2007).

The Northeast Arctic cod fishery in Norway faced a major crisis almost at the same time. In 1989, an unexpected decline in the cod stock led to a reduction in quota to 340,000 tons from 630,000 tons in the year before (Hersoug, 2005). In that year, the cod was very close to shore and therefore fairly easy to catch. As a result, the quota was filled already very early in the season, when some fishers just had started. While some fishers had made good catches, others almost didn't catch anything. On 18th of April 1989 the fishery was closed. That day marked a regime shift in Norwegian fisheries policy (Holm & Finstad, 2020). Unlike in Canada, there was an immediate reaction by policy makers and the broader public to avoid a collapse and what was perceived as an outcome. There was a strong will to transform Norwegian fisheries, as described in Hersoug (2005, p11): "Never again 18 April" was the slogan, all along the coast.. from an administrative point of view this was a godsend. Now the time was ripe for a change...". Today, Northeast Arctic cod has recovered and supplies 57% of all global Atlantic cod catches in 2018. Also, Norway is seen as a role model for modern fisheries management (Gullestad *et al.*, 2014).

So, while the initial conditions in Norway and Canada seem similar when the crisis struck, the trajectories and outcomes could not be any more different. What caused those differences? First, very much like in Canada, in Norway, the coastal fishers received some preferential political treatment, particularly when it comes to weighing their interest over the interest of the offshore fleet of trawlers. However, in Norway, the fishing industry had already been through a process of rationalization, where the number of fishers declined between 1945 and 1990 from 118,000 to around 28,000, while they stayed the same in Canada throughout that same period (Hersoug, 2005). Holm and Finstad (2020) described the closure of the Norwegian coastal fishery as a shift of focus from social sustainability (employment) to environmental and economic sustainability. Tragically, the Canadian experience illustrates that the trade-off between social and ecological sustainability is illusive in the long run, as a collapse of the stock tends to go hand in hand with a collapse of the fishery.

Second, the Norwegian cod fishery has a very long history in conflict resolution, particular when it comes to distributional issues. Also, the collapse of the Norwegian herring fishery in the late 1960s and early 1970s has been an important lesson about the sustainability limits of the oceans. As a result, the destructive effects of overfishing, and the accompanied impacts on fishing communities, may have caused a greater awareness and alert when the cod was in crisis. Canadian Atlantic fisheries had also experienced serious declines, but foreign fleets were a ready target for blame, and the United Nations Convention of the Law of the Sea was viewed as a

Box 6.14

universal solution to safeguard sustainability, promising enough cod for everyone – inshore and offshore, and internal dispute resolution mechanisms weren't a priority.

Third, the role of science was very different in Norway and Canada. In Norway, the collapse of the herring fishery has played a big role in advancing the science of stock assessments and giving bigger weight to scientific assessments in the policy process. As phrased by Holm and Finstad (2020, p121), during the cod crises “there was no strong movement to attack the credibility of the scientific advice”. This was a stark difference with the loss of trust and legitimacy in science observed in Canada, where two independent reviews of the science, one highly politicized, were called for between 1986 and 1990.

Fourth, in Canada distributional questions and sustainability question were highly convoluted and intertwined, with a

stronger focus on who to blame than what to do. In Norway, distributional questions were discussed equally controversially and fiercely, but without trumpeting the sustainability discourse. To illustrate that point, Odd Nakken, director of the Institute for Marine Research during the cod crisis said “a dead cod is a dead cod regardless of the gear it was caught with” (Holm & Finstad, 2020).

Finally, and perhaps most importantly, environmental conditions in Norway were very different compared to Canada. While in Canada, temperature changes were unfavorable for recruitment of cod, the opposite happened in Norway, especially during the recovery year. In the end, in Norway a transformation towards sustainability was greatly facilitated by independent science, a constructive political process, but certainly also a good portion of luck in the form of favorable environmental conditions just at the right time (Diekert & Schweder, 2017).

Several further fishing case studies highlight how successful policy attends to the historical context and backdrop against which the finally considered-to-be-effective policy instrument (or combination thereof) are identified and described. For example, the Amazonian Pirarucu case study highlights the pre-existence of (sustainable use and sustainable development) reserves and the strong socio-political self-organization that had already been developed during the establishment of these reserves (Campos-Silva & Peres, 2016) (see **Box 6.7**). In the groundfish/trawling case study in California (United States of America), when a conservation non-governmental organization (The Natural Conservancy) bought-out fisheries licenses, it was critical to present the suggestions for protected area locations (developed together with fishers) at the right time with respect to the government/federal regulatory process for essential fish habitat identification and protection along the entire west coast of the United States of America (Gleason *et al.*, 2013).

Historical context should thus be considered and reflected in policy design for sustainable use of wild species. However, this is often not the case. In the case of terrestrial animal harvesting, it is highly recommended to take into account the historical context in which the policy instrument was designed and implemented. For example, in many regions of Africa, fishing and hunting was regulated by informal norms and rules from local and traditional communities (Haule *et al.*, 2002; Marks, 1984). When the European colonists settled, they introduced many factors which changed these pre-colonial systems of sustainable management, such as a strong market economy, firearms, and protected areas (DeGeorges & Reilly, 2009; Haule *et al.*, 2002). Even after independence, the new governments adopted the management systems already established, which resulted in the erosion of existing communal systems, and resource decline (Haule *et al.*, 2002). Colonial and state division of

resources in different sectors also made it even more difficult to access common resources, especially in the case of wild species where local rights were typically appropriated by the states and hunters became poachers (Smith *et al.*, 2019b). This tendency to overlook the historical context has often led to conflict (e.g., **Box 6.10**).

6.5.4.3 Criminalizing local practices

The least effective terrestrial animal harvesting case studies, amongst other practices, have in common that they do not consider the practices, needs, traditional ecological knowledge and/or culture of the indigenous peoples and local communities involved. The result is existing prohibitions in these case studies involve all species in the area -even non-threatened species- and are usually not accompanied by alternatives for indigenous peoples and local communities' livelihoods and welfare. As a result, these policies tend not to work in many cases because they inadvertently criminalize local practices (**Box 6.9**) or when there is a weak law enforcement component- trigger illegal activities that are counterproductive. Furthermore, wild species populations subject to prohibitions are barely monitored, as there are no incentives to allocate resources and time to this. Local communities are more flexible in adapting their management approaches of high value species irrespective of the legal setting of the area. Despite legal and regulatory policies in place there is insufficient monitoring and management by government authorities unless it has high market value and demand associated (Yarshagumba, Nepal) (Gauli & Hauser, 2009).

Policy enforcement is challenging in many African countries, and to alleviate the problem, co-management has in principle been introduced in many places. However, as most of these are still of the more instructive type, which

Box 6.15 Failed interactions constrain sustainable use: Lake Victoria.

Lake Victoria in East Africa is the world’s largest tropical lake and one of the largest freshwater fisheries, with annual fish landings of one million tons. The fishery is dominated by small pelagic fishes known locally as Dagaa/Mukene/Omena (*Rastrineobola argentea*) and Nile perch (*Lates niloticus*), that together constitute more than 80% of the total catch and 80% of total biological production (Figure 6.9).

For Nile perch, 97% of production and 70% of the catch consist of juveniles, which are currently illegal to catch. Fishing effort on the lake has increased almost exponentially since the 1970s, but neither the catch, nor the surveyed biomasses of the exploited stocks have shown signs of decrease (Kolding *et al.*, 2014). However, this observation is unsupported by all stock assessment models, which uniformly suggest that Nile perch, a 350 million United States dollars export industry, is overfished (Kolding *et al.*, 2008, 2014, 2019). The perceived overfishing is consistently blamed on illegal catch of juvenile

fishes (< 50 cm total length), resulting in huge investment and support into management interventions and enforcement.

Co-management was initially introduced to address this perceived problem, but attempts failed to curb illegal fishing. Consequently, the co-management arrangement has deteriorated (Nunan, 2020) and in Uganda, in 2015, was replaced by severe military enforcement (Mpomwenda, Kristófersson, *et al.*, 2022; National Geographic, 2019). What all the assessment models failed to detect was that Lake Victoria was undergoing rapid eutrophication from agricultural run-off, and that productivity had followed suit (Kolding *et al.*, 2008). Despite concerns of overfishing, the three largest producing stocks, consisting of small indigenous species, including juvenile Nile perch, produce 11 million tons per year, but are only lightly exploited (Figure 6.5). These stocks alone could sustainably yield 4 million tons per year to a riparian population suffering from chronic malnutrition (Kolding *et*

Figure 6.9 Harvest relative to total biological production (on logarithm scales) for species harvested in Lake Victoria based on the Ecopath model of 2014 (Natugonza *et al.*, 2016).

Exploitation rates equivalent to 10, 25, and 50% of production are given as dotted parallel lines. Blue boxes give the exploitation rates for the three most productive species groups. Dotted regression shows the unbalanced fishing pattern relative to production. Modified from (Kolding *et al.*, 2019) under license CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO.

Box 6.15

al., 2019). The mismatch between observed data and the conventional models, based on steady state assumptions, that fisheries managers use to develop policies risks undermining local food security.

Power imbalances and fundamental mistrust between partners has led to the breakdown of co-management in Lake Victoria (Medard Ntara *et al.*, 2015; Nunan, 2020; Nunan *et al.*, 2015, 2018). The fishers do not see any evidence of the lake being overfished, as their catch rates are maintained (on average higher than other African lakes). They therefore do not

understand why one of the most abundant resources cannot be fished (although officially they will agree if asked) (Kolding, personal knowledge). The policymakers, on the other hand, tend to focus solely on the value of the intensively exploited export industry of large Nile perch (1% of total production) and are doing everything they can to eradicate illegal fishing (Mpomwenda, Tómasson, *et al.*, 2022). Lake Victoria, probably the most productive lake in the world (1.6 ton/ha/year), has turned into a humanitarian tragedy with increasing conflicts and fatal hostilities, ignoring that a major driver of the observed changes, eutrophication, are coming from outside the fishery.

means that mechanisms exist for governments to consult with users but all decisions are taken by government (Nunan, 2020; Nunan *et al.*, 2015; Sen & Raakjaer Nielsen, 1996) (Figure 6.3), there is a mixed degree of success. In most cases, it seems that co-management is a form of crisis management (Sen & Raakjaer Nielsen, 1996), where governments, witnessing the failure of their own management regime, decide to bring users into the management process. However, predominantly to simply assist in the enforcement of the already top-down decided regulations. In many cases, this approach has not succeeded in curbing the perceived illegal fishing (Kolding *et al.*, 2019) and has even resulted in the total abandonment of co-management and renewed calls for centralized enforcement (See Box 6.15 on Lake Victoria Fisheries). Thus, there are many instances, especially in inland fisheries, when management measures, or governance models in place, may lead to a set of additional problems, instead of solving the current ones (Kolding *et al.*, 2014). Most of

these are based on fundamental disagreement between fishers and managers on the appropriateness of the top-down gazetted regulations, and the lack of empowerment of stakeholders to influence these (Kolding *et al.*, 2019). In many African countries, inland and coastal participatory experiences in fishing management, such as the beach management units have been implemented and have shown some degrees of success and growing stakeholder engagements. During the last few decades, rights-based management strategies are becoming increasingly important, especially those strategies based on the indigenous local knowledge and performed by indigenous peoples and local communities (Gaspere *et al.*, 2015).

6.6 LEVERS OF CHANGE AND POLICY OPTIONS

Drawing on the seven enabling conditions (Figure 6.4) for the sustainable use of wild species identified through this chapter, we present seven key elements that can be used to leverage more effective policies to support the sustainable use of wild species (Table 6.9). Local, national, and regional governments; local and customary institutions, the private sector, and civil society organizations can transition towards more sustainable use of wild species by: strengthening inclusive and participatory processes; recognizing and supporting multiple forms of knowledge and rights; ensuring equitable distributions of benefits; tailoring policies to the local context; monitoring practices and conditions; coordinating interactions and aligning policies; and building robust institutions (Table 6.9).

These levers, represent the enabling conditions for effective sustainable use policies identified in this assessment, and align with a number of “key elements of sustainable use” compiled in Chapter 2 based on the Addis Ababa Principles and Guidelines for Sustainable Use of Wild Species (Chapter 2, section 2.2.6.2). Drawing on 25 international standards (Figure 2.3), including six legally binding national agreements, six private sector certification schemes, and 12 voluntary agreements, Chapter 2, evaluated how sustainable use is conceptualized at the international level (see Chapter 2, section 2.2.6.2 for the full method). We draw on this analysis to determine progress across practices in engaging with the seven enabling conditions that emerge from our analysis and identify priority areas for action.

Based on the documents reviewed in Chapter 2, we find integration of these seven key elements into voluntary agreements, certification schemes and binding agreements differs among practices. Binding agreements that relate to fishing display good integration of these key elements, although inclusive and participatory processes and ensuring equitable distribution of benefits (the latter being key to greater support small-scale fisheries) are only reflected in certification schemes and voluntary agreements. Certification schemes for gathering and logging integrate most of these key elements, while these key elements are only reflected in voluntary agreements for terrestrial animal harvesting and observing (Table 6.9). Integrating all seven key elements into future certification schemes for terrestrial animal harvesting and observing and into binding agreements for all practices is necessary for the future of sustainable use of wild species.

6.6.1 Strengthen inclusive and participatory decision-making

When procedures are adapted to support the inclusion of all actors, traditions, knowledges, and contexts, transformative change in sustainable use is possible. When approaches work to ensure the capacities of indigenous peoples and local communities, and all marginalized genders and identities are recognized, inclusion is possible. Full and effective participation in sustainable use of wild species can support effective learning and reduce redundancy (e.g., via knowledge brokers, mediators, facilitators), outcomes are likely to be better supported by communities, and damaging power dynamics can be illuminated and navigated. Stakeholder diversity promotes buy-in and collaboration, and expands the knowledge base for decision making (e.g., co-management), provided that power imbalances and conflicts are managed. Specific actions to promote inclusive and participatory processes include enacting policies with clear guidance on procedures for decision making and representation (e.g., specifying membership roles and responsibilities) and building capacity that enables all actors to participate fully.

6.6.2 Recognize and support multiple forms of knowledge and rights

Recognizing and supporting multiple forms of knowledge and human rights is crucial prerequisite for constructing foundation in forming and implement policy strategies for sustainable use of wild species. The knowledge of indigenous peoples and local communities, such as on wild species, is often undervalued and underrepresented in policy documents. Yet, this knowledge can provide extensive, additional information about the relationships between living beings and the environment, especially with regards to natural resources and nature’s contributions to people that indigenous peoples and local communities depend on (also see Chapter 1). Ensuring the continuity and relevance of indigenous and local knowledge is necessarily linked to rights, access, recognition, survival (cultural, linguistic, spiritual, and material). The failure to include indigenous and local knowledge and indigenous languages in policy processes results in loss of language, community cohesion, and indigenous and local knowledge related to species and sustainable use. Sustainable use of wild species is integral to people living well and within their means and supporting human rights, including access to food, work, leisure, and a clean, healthy and sustainable environment. Thus, international laws, guidelines, and commitments exist to protect local food systems and livelihoods of indigenous peoples and local communities in recognition of both a moral obligation, and pragmatic reality that these can help support the sustainable use of wild species.

Table 6.9 **Seven key elements of effective policy for sustainable use of wild species, their presence in current international agreements and examples of policy options.**

Color coding based on the data drawn from analysis of the Chapter 2 (see Figure 2.3). Pictograms represent (from left to right): fishing, gathering, logging, terrestrial animal harvesting and non-extractive practices.

Key elements		Policy options				
Inclusive and participatory decision-making						Enact policies with clear guidance on transparent processes for decision-making and representation
						Build the capacity of all actors
						Develop national, regional, and international contact points, platforms and community facilitators, mediators
Inclusion of multiple forms of knowledge and recognition of rights						Ensure that decision-making processes are mandated to draw on diverse forms of social and ecological knowledge
						Develop measures to gain free, prior and informed consent for the use of knowledge and to ensure knowledge holders benefit
						Promote the obligation to secure the substantive and procedural rights that are guaranteed by law for all potentially affected persons
Equitable distribution of costs and benefits						Incorporate the contents of voluntary guidelines on fair and equitable sharing of benefits into legally binding agreements
						Distribute costs of management through social safety nets while ensuring that costs of management do not exceed benefits
						Apply governance and institutional frameworks that promote equitable benefit-sharing
						Ensure that policies do not inadvertently remove access for indigenous peoples, local communities or marginalized individuals
Policies tailored to local social and ecological context						Develop science- and evidence-based policies according to specific local ecological and social contexts, and follow the precautionary approach as appropriate
						Respect local communities' rights and access and customary rules
						Empower local communities
Monitoring of social and ecological conditions and practices						Incorporate guidelines and tools in project and programme planning to ensure social and ecological monitoring and evaluation of all interventions and their implications for the rights of people involved
						Invest resources in coordinated social and ecological monitoring programmes
						Support scientific and community-based social and ecological monitoring programmes
Coordinated and aligned policies						Coordinate international, regional, national and subnational policies and governance
						Integrate policies across sectors
						Coordinate policies across practices
Robust institutions, from customary to statutory						Design adaptive and dynamic institutions capable of adjusting to ecological and social changes
						Develop conflict resolution mechanisms and manage conflicts
						Integrate transparency measures into formal, legally mandated accountability policies
						Ensure all relevant customary and statutory policies, laws and institutions are respected in national and international agreements

VOLUNTARY AGREEMENTS
 VOLUNTARY AGREEMENTS AND CERTIFICATION SCHEMES
 NOT PRESENT
 VOLUNTARY AGREEMENTS, CERTIFICATION SCHEMES AND LEGALLY BINDING AGREEMENTS

More sustainable use of wild species will benefit from policy processes that protect indigenous and local knowledge and draw on diverse forms of knowledge, bringing scientists and indigenous peoples and local communities together in a co-learning process. However, it is essential that such efforts include measures to ensure that indigenous and local knowledge holders have provided consent for, and receive benefits from, the use of their knowledge.

6.6.3 Ensure fair and equitable distribution of costs and benefits

Policies that overlook social equity increase the risk of unsustainable use of wild species. Specific actions include enacting guidelines on access and benefit sharing that are currently common in voluntary agreements, applying governance and institutional frameworks that promote equitable benefit sharing, and ensuring that policies do not inadvertently put local communities or marginalized individuals out of access.

In contrast, although successful non-extractive use policies are found to generate incomes for local communities, little attention is paid to benefit sharing, undermining long term success (G. He *et al.*, 2008; Kirkby *et al.*, 2010) (Table 6.9, Chapter 2). Similarly, the least successful terrestrial animal harvesting cases, it has been found that there are problems in terms of transparency in benefit distribution. Involvement in gathering practice policies of socially responsible companies, pro conservation, micro and small enterprise models, community consensus on boundaries and other rights, monitoring of sustainable gathering, conservation status, simple practical and enforceable rules, followed by penalties on breaking agreeable rules, equitable sharing of benefits, sound mechanisms for conflict resolution, and support from the local government concerned were important considerations discussed in most effective case studies.

6.6.4 Tailor policies to local social and ecological contexts

Context-specific policies are needed to ensure the sustainable use of wild species. Effective policies are purpose-built to local social and ecological conditions in which uses take place.

Tailored policies to the local and governance context include consideration of the ecological characteristics like species-specific conditions and the social pattern in using wild species. It is necessary to design a policy suitable for administrative capabilities. Actions to empower local communities and respect their rights, access and customary rules are fundamental to the development of context-specific policies. Context-specific policies including

consideration for local communities are needed to ensure the sustainable use of wild species. Therefore, it is crucial to diagnose the ecological, economic and social conditions of use of wild species at the local level for designing tailored policies to the local contexts.

6.6.5 Monitor social and ecological conditions and practices

Monitoring wild species and practices will be crucial to prevent species decline and control unsustainable use of wild species. Regulatory instruments including international and national agreements and guidelines regulation and financial instruments including budget for technology and training can support monitoring of practices and conditions. In addition, monitoring can facilitate equitable participation of the different key actors. Monitoring requires both indigenous and scientific methods. In particular, community-based monitoring facilitates understanding of conditions of wild species and sustainable practices in use of wild species.

6.6.6 Coordinate and align policies

Policy instruments that are aligned at international, national, regional and local levels, and that maintain coherence and consistency with existing international obligations and take into account customary rules and norms, will be more effective. Policies outcomes will also be more effective and will lead to fewer negative and unintended consequences when attention is paid to coordinated interactions between approaches, actors, and scales. Following the same goal of sustainable use of wild species, national regulations can reflect international conventions and agreements agreed by many countries. Policies between different sectors are needed to coordinate. Relationship between wild product use and agriculture needs to be considered in designing and implementing policies of use of wild species. Fishing practice interlinks with non-fishing sectors such as agriculture, water management, and the hydro-electronic industry. In particular, logging, terrestrial animal harvesting and gathering are interconnected: forests are habitats of animals, and wild plants are food for animals. Thus, these three practices interact closely with each other. Therefore, inter-sectoral policy design will support sustainable use practice with consideration for multiple drivers to wild species conditions.

6.6.7 Build robust institutions, from customary to statutory

Robust institutions, including customary institutions, will be essential to future sustainable use of wild species. Institutions that are structured around collaborative and

decentralized learning and shared interests in sustainable use are more effective than centralized systems aimed only at top-down governance. Adaptive and dynamic institutions capable of adjusting to changing circumstances will be needed to face current and future challenges of sustainable use of wild species. The integration of conflict resolution mechanisms will make institutions more effective, while transparency initiatives connected to legally mandated measures of accountability will enhance trust in institutions.

6.6.8 Enhance capacity building

Capacity-building emerges as an important enabling condition for the sustainable use of wild species in all practices. There is little evidence of value chains from concept to execution of sustainable practices reported in the successful practices from case studies. However, as these tend to include all stakeholders from the conception of the practices and throughout its different aspects/links, it is likely that some of these could be considered as such. Capacity-building of actors throughout the links of the production and commercial chains is also key for transforming these into value chains. Building the capacity of local and indigenous peoples helps producer communities to organize, navigate wild plant and fungi permitting procedures, and assert their rights against more powerful players.

6.7 KNOWLEDGE GAPS

(i) Policy effectiveness is under studied

Many studies described policies for regulating and supporting use of wild species. But only a few studies have evaluated directly the positive and negative effects of policies in using wild species. In particular, few studies measured effectiveness of economic instruments for regulating use activities in five practices. Within non-extractive use case studies, economic instruments such as nature-based tourism certification and fees effectiveness have not been studied extensively. Certification helps to reassure tourists about the responsibility and sustainability of the operator's activities but its effectiveness is not clear.

(ii) Evaluation of the influence of broader policies on sustainable use lacking

While direct and indirect drivers are clearly linked to practices, the effects of broader policies on the sustainability of the practice are lacking. It is necessary to design a comprehensive and integrated policy for controlling diverse drivers to unsustainable use of wild species in practices. The institutional framework of most national and international entities does not effectively address cross-sectoral issues such as those relating to sustainable use, health and sanitation, economic development, and education. The responsibilities of these sectors are separated over multiple agencies that seldom interact and may need to compete for finite resources.

(iii) Gaps in policy scope

Policies for supporting sustainable use of wild species are formed at the multiple levels; international, regional, national and local and interacted each other. In particular, at the global society new policy instruments for controlling use of wild species have been developed through collective intelligence. In practice, for following international conventions or agreements the national and local policies are required. Gaps between international agreements and national policy instruments emerge in implementing the agreed activities at the same time. Although countries agree the goals of international conventions and agreements, reflection of international agreements to domestic policies is limited. There is a time lag in regulatory enforcement between international agreements and national laws. As well, international agreements have limitation to include specific national conditions.

(v) Gaps between practices (cross-sectoral gap)

Multiple drivers exist in sustainable and unsustainable use of wild species. They influence five practices. At the same time, practices interact with each other. Logging influences the

potential areas of gathering and terrestrial animal harvesting. Therefore, logging policies include policy instruments for gathering and terrestrial animal harvesting. For example, forest regulations include control of gathering and terrestrial animal harvesting. In fishing, whilst it is commonplace to assume practical answers to fishing-related problems come directly from the fishing sector in the form of fishing tools, management and policy, the analysis of how non-fishing-related policy can and does impact the sustainability of fishing requires more attention. More concerted cross-sectoral awareness should also help mitigate the risk of policy implementation that benefits policy outcomes unrelated to fishing to the detriment of sustainable fishing. Considering the interrelated framework of Sustainable Development Goals under the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (G. G. Singh *et al.*, 2018), it is surprising that more work has not been undertaken to formally analyze links between non-fisheries policy and fisheries. Combining efforts across sectors with the above ideas in mind will likely facilitate meeting more of the Sustainable Development Goals' targets. Moving away from single stroke policy efforts focused only on single targets will require considerable collaboration between traditionally unrelated sectors both in industry and in policy.

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